

BARRIERS AND ENABLERS FOR OPEN SCIENCE IN COPYRIGHT LAW

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This study was conducted by Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute (ODIPI) with the support of the Knowledge Rights 21 programme. The study starts by analysing barriers and enablers for Open Science in the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act (Slo. *Zakon o znanstvenoraziskovalni in inovacijski dejavnosti*),¹ providing a foundation for further comparative research. Building on this groundwork, the study then includes analyses of two other pilot countries – Italy and Croatia – where researchers applied the Slovenian model to examine their respective national copyright law frameworks. The work of the researchers was guided by a comprehensive questionnaire prepared by ODIPI, ensuring a structured and methodologically consistent examination of their respective copyright law frameworks. This approach not only facilitates a comparative evaluation but also provides a replicable methodology for identifying barriers and enablers for Open Science in different jurisdictions. This study provides an example that can be further upgraded by expanding the analysis to other jurisdictions in the future.

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¹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 186/21 and 40/23. Available at: <<https://pisrs.si/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO7733>>, last accessed in March 2025;

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Copyright law is a system of legal rules primarily aimed at encouraging the creation of literary and artistic works while achieving a delicate balance between various societal interests.

Open Science represents a modern approach to the scientific process, emphasising collaboration and innovative methods for disseminating knowledge. It enhances access to and promotes the reuse of research results by leveraging digital technologies and other modern tools for collaboration.

The European Union (hereinafter: EU) and its Member States have been actively adopting various strategies, policies, action plans, and legal measures to incentivise the development of Open Science.

Despite all these efforts, significant barriers still remain which limit the development of Open Science's full potential. Those that may provide the most significant obstacle are the ones created by copyright law.

The study analyses the copyright law of three jurisdictions. Firstly, the provisions of the Slovenian Copyright and Related Rights Act are examined, with a focus on identifying legal barriers to Open Science, as well as possible enablers within the copyright framework. The study then expands its scope to Italy and Croatia. This was done with the help of a comprehensive questionnaire that served as guidance to Italian and Croatian researchers. The questionnaire prepared by ODIPI could serve as a foundation for future analyses of copyright legislation across other European countries. It offers a framework for expanding the scope of the study to a wide range of European jurisdictions.

A significant barrier stems from the requirement for *consensual management of copyright*, which mandates unanimous consent among all rights holders for the use of a work. This requirement is particularly relevant for *co-authored works* and *compound works*, where it complicates rights management, limits the accessibility of research outputs, and creates obstacles to knowledge dissemination.

The *unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation* represents another barrier, as authors cannot renounce these rights even if they clearly wish to make their work openly accessible. This restriction allows collective management organisations to claim remuneration on the author's behalf (regardless of the author's own preferences), imposing financial and administrative burdens on repositories and other platforms committed to ensuring Open Access and facilitating the reuse of research results. This mechanism ultimately curtails the ability of authors to exercise full control over their works and restricts the adoption of open licenses.

Further barriers stem from the *requirement for specific separate transfers* of rights. Copyright law often mandates that the individual components of economic rights must be transferred separately, necessitating distinct agreements for different types of uses. This fragmentation complicates rights management and discourages researchers from pursuing Open Access

publication due to increased administrative complexity. Similarly, the *requirement for special consent of the author for subsequent transfers* imposes additional constraints. Even if a copyright holder has transferred rights, further transfers to third parties require explicit author consent unless contractually stipulated otherwise. This requirement introduces legal uncertainty and administrative inefficiencies, further limiting the potential for broader dissemination of research results.

Requirements for formality also act as barriers. These can mandate that all transfers of economic rights, as well as authorisations, be made in writing. The absence of a written agreement leads to an interpretation in favour of the author (*in dubio pro auctore*), creating potential ambiguities that complicate the negotiation and implementation of Open Access agreements. Additionally, the *presumption of the publisher's priority right* limits the ability of authors to publish their works through multiple channels. By granting publishers of physical works a privileged position regarding electronic publication, this presumption restricts the immediate availability of research outputs on Open Access platforms and conflicts with legislative efforts to introduce *Secondary Publishing Rights*.

Some legal mechanisms can function as both barriers and enablers, depending on their practical application. The *presumption of transfer of economic rights from employees to employers* is one such provision. When a copyright work is created in the course of employment, economic rights are often deemed to be transferred to the employer, typically for a set period. This presumption can restrict authors from managing their works under open licenses, as they do not retain control over their economic rights. If an employer does not actively support Open Access policies, researchers may face barriers in making their work openly available. However, this mechanism can also serve as an enabler, allowing institutions which have aligned with Open Science principles to disseminate research outputs broadly without requiring additional consent from the author. The effect of this provision is therefore contingent on the policies and commitments of the employer.

Explicit enablers for Open Science within copyright law remain largely absent. A legal framework that supports Open Access to and reuse of research results ideally includes measures such as the *Rights Retention* obligation and *Secondary Publishing Rights*, which create the right (and typically the mandate) for authors to deposit their publicly funded research outputs in Open Access repositories regardless of contractual terms with publishers.

Barriers to Open Science also extend beyond copyright law. Certain legal frameworks impose *de facto copyright-like restrictions* that limit the availability of research materials. Cultural heritage laws, for example, can introduce additional layers of protection over works in the Public Domain, requiring authorisation and, in some cases, payment of fees for the commercial use of faithful digital reproductions. This can restrict Open Science practices in disciplines that draw on such (cultural heritage) works.

Conversely, certain legislative measures outside the scope of copyright law function as enablers for Open Science. The introduction of the *Rights Retention* obligation and *Secondary Publishing Rights* within research legislation (as opposed to copyright law) in Slovenia aims to facilitate Open Access to and reuse of publicly funded research results. The list of laws with potential impacts considered here is by no means exhaustive. Some of these enablers may

even function as incentives for Open Science, as their implementation is linked to financial rewards within research funding frameworks or to legal sanctions for non-compliance.

Overall, the interplay of these barriers, conditional enablers, and external legal constraints and opportunities highlights the need for a more coherent and supportive legal framework for Open Science. While certain provisions protect the rights of authors and other stakeholders, they often conflict with the objectives of Open Access dissemination. Aligning copyright law with Open Science principles requires addressing the structural barriers that impede access while leveraging existing mechanisms to promote openness where possible.

The findings reveal that, despite growing recognition of Open Science principles, copyright laws in all three jurisdictions continue to impose significant legal barriers to their effective implementation.

In particular, this study illustrates the gap between political and strategic commitments to Open Science and legal realities that can severely limit the delivery of these commitments. All three countries have adopted national strategies that promote Open Science, but copyright law has not yet been aligned with these objectives. Instead, researchers must navigate a complex landscape where legal uncertainties and contractual restrictions imposed by law or legal presumptions hinder the management of copyright in publicly funded research results in accordance with Open Science principles.

The study demonstrates that national differences in copyright law pose significant challenges for cross-border cooperation among researchers, including when conducting work aligned with Open Science principles. What is legally permitted in one country may be restricted in another, resulting in an uneven legal landscape that hinders the international dissemination of scientific knowledge and reduces the overall impact of investments in open knowledge production.

Researchers and scientists have been calling for several decades now for a better legal environment for their research and scientific activities in order to achieve the full potential of science and research for the development of society. Open Science initiatives based on bottom-up approaches, such as institutional policies (which rely on open licenses as a tool to open up research results) and the negotiation of more favourable agreements, can have a mitigating effect, particularly in the absence of a more balanced copyright framework with legally certain, broad, and harmonised research exceptions. Yet this study highlights that even Open Science efforts and activities can be severely hindered by the failure to properly update copyright law.

This study lays the groundwork for discussions on the need to align copyright law with Open Science objectives. The researchers, research institutions and others aligned with them will need to continue to advocate for a more balanced copyright system with legally certain, broad and harmonised research exceptions. This study highlights that even the efforts and activities of Open Science, which legally depend on private licences and contracts, are potentially severely hindered by copyright regimes today. Copyright regimes should be better framed to support research and science and rapidly reformed not to hinder Open Science.

I. INTRODUCTION

Copyright law strikes a precarious balance.² To encourage authors to create and disseminate original expression, it accords them a bundle of proprietary rights in their works. But to promote public education and creative exchange, it invites audiences and subsequent authors to use existing works in every conceivable manner that falls outside the province of the copyright owner's exclusive rights.³ Copyright law's perennial dilemma is to determine where exclusive rights should end, and unrestrained public access should begin.⁴

Research is one key area where copyright laws can have a structuring role. Open Science represents a modern approach to the scientific process, emphasising collaboration and innovative methods for disseminating knowledge. This stands in contrast to proprietary models that use copyright to enforce scarcity and charge for access and use. Open Science approaches promote access to and reuse of research results, leveraging the potential of digital technologies and other modern tools for collaboration.⁵

The European Union (hereinafter: EU) and its Member States have been actively adopting various strategies, policies, action plans, and legal measures to support and incentivise the development of Open Science. These efforts aim to promote accessibility, transparency, and collaboration in research, reflecting a growing recognition of Open Science as a key driver for innovation and societal progress.⁶

Despite a plethora of EU and national strategies, political frameworks and legislation to support Open Science, significant barriers remain which prevent the full realisation of the potential of Open Science's. Barriers that may provide the most significant obstacle are those created by copyright law.

This is not the first time this challenge has been addressed – multiple EU studies⁷ have already extensively covered the topic of improving access to and reuse of research results, as well as

² Bogataj Jančič, Maja. *Avtorsko pravo v digitalni dobi : problematika zaščite avtorskih del s tehnološkimi ukrepi* / Maja Bogataj Jančič. – Ljubljana : Pasadena, 2008, page 3;

³ Netanel, Neil Weinstock, *Copyright and a Democratic Civil Society* (1996), page 285;

⁴ *Ibid.*;

⁵ Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI: *Exceptions and Limitations in Copyright Law*. Available at: <<https://www.odipi.si/en/izjeme-in-omejitve-v-avtorskem-pravu/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁶ See for example the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Available at: <https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. *Improving access to and reuse of research results, publications and data for scientific purposes – Study to evaluate the effects of the EU copyright framework on research and the effects of potential interventions and to identify and present relevant provisions for research in EU data and digital legislation, with a focus on rights and obligations*. Publications Office of the European Union, 2024. Available at: <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/633395>>, last accessed in March 2025; Angelopoulos, Christina. *Study on EU copyright and related rights and access to and reuse of scientific publications, including Open access: exceptions and limitations, rights retention strategies and the secondary publication right*, Independent expert report commissioned by European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022; Senftleben, Martin. *Study on EU copyright and related rights and access to and reuse of data*, Independent expert report commissioned by the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022; Lundqvist, Björn. *Study on the Digital Services Act and Digital Markets Act and their possible impact on research*, Independent expert report commissioned by European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and

the importance of Open Science principles. While those studies focused on the EU level, this study examines specific provisions within the copyright laws of Member States. The objective is to determine which national copyright law provisions act as barriers to Open Science, as well as those which may in fact provide an enabler.

While this study focuses specifically on barriers and enablers for Open Science, it is important to note that many of the identified barriers are not exclusive to Open Science but reflect broader structural issues affecting research more generally. Nonetheless, given the current political priority placed on Open Science and its prominent role in shaping research policy agendas, it remains both appropriate and necessary to highlight the impacts of these barriers in this specific context.

Open Science strategies, policies and principles aim to address the challenge that legacy copyright frameworks are arguably not well-suited to a model of research based on collaborative creation and dissemination of knowledge.⁸ Yet Open Science exists within the framework created by copyright. Where national copyright laws hinder access to and reuse of knowledge by complicating and, in some cases, effectively preventing its broad availability, or more specifically, where making such knowledge available under open licenses is impeded, achieving Open Science becomes significantly more difficult.

Accordingly, this study pinpoints legal barriers to Open Science within the copyright law provisions of national legal systems that need to be amended in the future. It also identifies provisions that serve as enablers for Open Science and should therefore be maintained or strengthened.

The study analyses three different jurisdictions, in order to reflect the fact that national copyright laws are not fully harmonised. Firstly, it analyses the provisions in the Slovenian Copyright and Related Rights Act (Slo. *Zakon o avtorski in sorodnih pravicah*, hereinafter: ZASP).⁹ It then looks at two neighbouring jurisdictions, namely Italy and Croatia. To ensure a structured and methodologically consistent approach, ODIPI developed a comprehensive questionnaire that served as guidance for national researchers analysing the national copyright law provisions in these two other jurisdictions.

For the purposes of the study '*Barriers and Enablers for Open Science in the Copyright Law*', we define:

- 'barriers' to Open Science as a multitude of reasons hindering the uptake of Open Access to and reuse of publications, such as lack of time or resources, constraints imposed by the policies of scholarly journals and other publishers, perceived lack of benefits,¹⁰ the

Innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022. Available at: <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/751853>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸ Lazarova, Ana. Introducing a zero-embargo Secondary Publication Right in Bulgaria. Kluwer Copyright Blog, 2024. Available at: <<https://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2024/02/09/introducing-a-zero-embargo-secondary-publication-right-in-bulgaria>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 16/07;

¹⁰ One of the challenges for implementing Open Science policies is the perception among some policymakers that the benefits of Open Science are uncertain or not immediately measurable. This can delay the adoption of national policies and investment in necessary infrastructures. See: UNESCO. Open Science Outlook 2023: Status and Trends Around the World, page 13. UNESCO Publishing, 2023. Available at: <<https://opusproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/OSOutlook->

absence of funder or employer requirements, and concerns regarding copyright or licensing provisions;¹¹

- ‘enablers’ to Open Science as a range of measures, policies and strategies designed to encourage the uptake of Open Access to and reuse of publications. For example, these enablers could include legislative measures, such as national law provisions that establish *Rights Retention* or *Secondary Publishing Rights*. Such mechanisms make it easier for researchers to share their work Open Access, promoting wider dissemination and greater access to scientific knowledge.

The study is structured in five main sections. The first section is an introduction to the study and addresses general issues as well as describing general terms applicable to the study. Next, there are three sections exploring the copyright framework of a specific jurisdiction: Slovenia, Italy and Croatia. This is the main body of the study. Each part starts with a description of the structural and political framework for Open Science of each country and is followed by legal analysis of the relevant national copyright law provisions.

The second section, titled ‘Report on Barriers and Enablers for Open Science in Slovenian Copyright Law’, provides an in-depth analysis of the Slovenian Copyright and Related Rights Act (Slo. *Zakon o avtorski in sorodnih pravicah*),¹² identifying provisions that may either hinder or promote Open Science. This section lays down the foundation for the comparative analysis of the other two jurisdictions. Based on this Report a comprehensive questionnaire was prepared by ODIPI that guided researchers in providing answers for their respective jurisdictions. The questionnaire prepared by ODIPI could serve as a foundation for future analyses of copyright legislation across other European countries. It offers a framework for expanding the scope of the study to a wide range of European jurisdictions.

The third section is the ‘Report on Barriers and Enablers for Open Science in the Italian Copyright Law’. This extends analysis to the jurisdiction of Italy, highlighting relevant legal provisions within the Italian Law [of] Protection of Copyright and Other Rights Related to Its Exercise (Ita. *Legge [sulla] Protezione del diritto d'autore e di altri diritti connessi al suo esercizio*)¹³ and their impact on Open Science.

The fourth section contains the ‘Report on Barriers and Enablers for Open Science in the Croatian Copyright Law’. This examines the Croatian Copyright and Related Rights Act (Cro. *Zakon o autorskom pravu i srodnim pravima*)¹⁴ in the context of Open Science.

2023_combined-draft-4-Sept-for-review.pdf#:~:text=The%20benefits%20of%20open%20science,the%20open%20science%20actors%20considered>, last accessed in April 2025;

¹¹ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Improving access to and reuse of research results, publications and data for scientific purposes – Study to evaluate the effects of the EU copyright framework on research and the effects of potential interventions and to identify and present relevant provisions for research in EU data and digital legislation, with a focus on rights and obligations, page 78. Publications Office of the European Union, 2024. Available at: <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/633395>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹² Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 16/07;

¹³ Legge 22 aprile 1941, n. 633 “Protezione del diritto d'autore e di altri diritti connessi al suo esercizio” (LdA);

¹⁴ Official Gazette of the Republic of Croatia, 111/21, in application since October 22, 2021;

The final section of the study, titled “Conclusions and Recommendations”, consists of a summary of the general results, and lists main recommendations for legislators on how to lift (or at least minimise) barriers and enhance enablers for Open Science.

II. REPORT ON BARRIERS AND ENABLERS FOR OPEN SCIENCE IN THE SLOVENIAN COPYRIGHT LAW

II.1. Structural, political and legal framework for Open Science in Slovenia

Slovenia has adopted a comprehensive strategic and political framework for Open Science to align with broader European trends. First, with the National Strategy of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Slovenia 2015–2020 (Slo. *Nacionalna strategija odprtega dostopa do znanstvenih objav in raziskovalnih podatkov v Sloveniji 2015–2020*),¹⁵ and later with the Resolution on the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy 2030 (Slo. *Resolucija o znanstvenoraziskovalni in inovacijski strategiji Slovenije 2030*; hereinafter: ReZrIS30).¹⁶

In addition to the strategic and political framework, Slovenia has many top-down legislative and non-legislative enablers. The most important legislative enabler is the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act (Slo. *Zakon o znanstvenoraziskovalni in inovacijski dejavnosti*; hereinafter: ZZrID),¹⁷ adopted in 2021, which was the first to introduce a top-down *Rights Retention* requirement. This requirement was later elaborated on and complemented by the governmental Decree on the Implementation of Scientific Research in Accordance with the Principles of Open Science (Slo. *Uredba o izvajanju znanstvenoraziskovalnega dela v skladu z načeli odprte znanosti*; hereinafter: Decree on Open Science).¹⁸ This further details the framework and obligations for *Rights Retention*, as well as other aspects of Open Science. The Action Plan for Open Science¹⁹ is the most important structural top-down enabler, aimed at providing financial and structural support for more effective implementation of Open Science principles. The project ‘Support for the Implementation of Open Science Principles in Slovenia’ (hereinafter: project SPOZNAJ),²⁰ is part of this Action Plan and aims to align research activities at the institutional level with the Open Science principles embedded in

¹⁵ Government of the Republic of Slovenia (2015). National Strategy of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Slovenia 2015–2020. Available at: <<https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MVZI/Znanost/do-2020-Strategije-predpisi-in-drugi-dokumenti/National-strategy-of-open-access-to-scientific-publications-and-research-data-in-Slovenia-2015-2020.pdf>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹⁶ Government of the Republic of Slovenia (2022). Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 49/22. Available at: <<https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MIZS/Dokumenti/ZNANOST/Nacionalni-dokumenti/Resolution-on-the-Slovenian-Scientific-Research-and-Innovation-Strategy-2030>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹⁷ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 186/21 and 40/23. Available at: <<https://pisrs.si/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO7733>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹⁸ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 59/23; Available at: <<https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina/2023-01-1828/uredba-o-izvajanju-znanstvenoraziskovalnega-dela-v-skladu-z-naceli-odprte-znanosti>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹⁹ Government of the Republic of Slovenia (2023). The Action Plan for Open Science for the implementation of Objective 6.2: Open Science to improve research quality, efficiency, and responsiveness of the Resolution on the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Strategy 2030. Available at: <<https://www.gov.si/assets/ministrstva/MVZI/Znanost/Nacionalne-strategije-in-dokumenti/2023-Action-Plan-Open-Science-Slovenia.pdf>>, last accessed in March 2025;

²⁰ Project SPOZNAJ. Available at: <<https://projekt-spoznaj.si/en/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

Slovenian law. It involves all of Slovenia's public universities and public research organisations.

In May 2025, the National Assembly of the Republic of Slovenia (Slo. *Državni zbor Republike Slovenije*) unanimously adopted an amendment to the ZZrID (amendment ZZrID-C),²¹ thereby officially incorporating *Secondary Publishing Rights* into the Slovenian legal framework.²² The amendment ZZrID-C entered into force in June 2025.

Despite a plethora of EU and national strategies and political frameworks that translate into a variety of different actions, as well as the establishment of legislation that supports Open Science, significant barriers still remain which limit the realisation of Open Science's full potential. Some of the most significant are those that come from copyright law.

This study therefore identifies the provisions in the Slovenian Copyright and Related Rights Act (Slo. *Zakon o avtorski in sorodnih pravicah*, hereinafter: ZASP),²³ that may hinder Open Science. In addition to the barriers, it aims to identify potential enablers for Open Science that exist already in the copyright law as well.

II.2. Barriers and enablers for Open Science in Slovenian Copyright Law

In the context of Open Science, where access is ensured through free and open licenses following the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary",²⁴ certain provisions of copyright law function as barriers, restricting the availability and use of scientific and scholarly content. At the same time, some aspects of copyright law serve as enablers, fostering openness by enabling flexible licensing frameworks. A clear understanding of these legal barriers and enablers is crucial for balancing the rights of creators with the broader societal interest in knowledge dissemination and innovation.

II.2.1. Barriers stemming from the requirement of consensual management of copyright

The requirement for consensual management of copyright presents a significant barrier for Open Science by mandating unanimous consent among all rights holders for the use of a work. This barrier arises in the context of co-authored works. In certain cases, similar barriers can arise in the cases of compound works.

²¹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 40/25;

²² Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI. Secondary Publishing Rights Adopted into Slovenian Legislation. Available at: <<https://www.odipi.si/en/secondary-publishing-rights-adopted-into-slovenian-law/>>, last accessed in May 2025; Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Slovenia. Amendment to the Scientific Research and Innovation Activity Act Confirmed. Available at: <<https://www.gov.si/novice/2025-05-21-dokoncno-potrjena-novela-zakona-o-znanstvenoraziskovalni-in-inovacijski-dejavnosti/>>, last accessed in May 2025;

²³ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 16/07;

²⁴ European Research Executive Agency. Open Science. Available at: <https://rea.ec.europa.eu/open-science_en>, last accessed in March 2025;

Co-authored works are those created through joint creative collaboration among multiple authors. Videos involving multiple collaborators serve as a good example of co-authored works.

Requiring unanimous consent for the use of such works complicates rights management, reducing flexibility in sharing research outputs, restricting access to knowledge, and impeding collaboration and innovation.

The following points will examine how the requirement for consensual management of copyright under Articles 12 and 13 of ZASP creates barriers for Open Science, particularly in the context of co-authored works (and in certain cases compound works), where unanimous consent is required for use.

II.2.1.1. Requirement of consensual management for co-authors

Co-authors
Article 12 of ZASP

(1) If a copyright work created by the collaboration of two or more persons constitutes an inseparable whole, all co-authors of this work shall have joint copyright in it.

(2) The right to decide on the use of such a work belongs jointly to all co-authors; this notwithstanding, individual co-authors may not obstruct such decisions, as this would be contrary to the principles of good faith and fairness.

(3) Co-authors' shares shall be determined in proportion to the extent of their respective contributions to the creation of the work unless they are set otherwise by contract.

Article 12 of ZASP regulates co-authorship in the fields of literature, science, and art. Co-authorship arises when a work is created through the collaboration of multiple authors, making it necessary to regulate the rights of co-authors and their interactions with third parties. As a co-authored work constitutes an 'inseparable whole', it is particularly important to clearly delineate the rights among co-authors.

Article 12(2) of ZASP provides that economic rights in a co-authored work are held jointly by all co-authors. Therefore, any use of the work requires the unanimous consent of all co-authors, as a majority decision is insufficient. The law mitigates this requirement by stipulating that a co-author may not obstruct the use of the work if doing so would violate the principles of good faith and fairness.

In this context, Article 12(2) of ZASP acts as a barrier for Open Science. When a single co-author objects to making the work openly accessible, this objection prevents the work's publication on open-access platforms or repositories, even if all other co-authors support such publication. This issue is particularly relevant as an increasing number of research outputs are being shared in video format on platforms dedicated to video content.

Thus, this restriction can significantly limit the dissemination of research results to the wider scientific community and the public.

Another barrier, akin to the requirement of consensual management for co-authors, arises with derivative works. While derivative works (Slo. *predelave*) are legally recognised under ZASP, they are not explicitly classified as “co-authored works”. In some cases, a derivative work may involve contributions from both the original author and the author of a derivative work, resembling a form of co-authorship.

Article 33(3) of ZASP is particularly relevant in this context. It requires the original author’s consent for the transformation of a pre-existing work and, consequently, for the creation and use of a derivative work, but does not explicitly establish co-authorship between the original author and the author of a derivative work. Instead, Article 33(3) of ZASP affirms that the original author retains exclusive rights over the derivative work, unless otherwise provided by ZASP or contract.

This requirement creates a potential barrier to Open Science practices (and indeed research in general) by restricting the reuse of pre-existing scientific works, which is essential for the proper functioning of the scientific process and the advancement of knowledge. Since the original author’s consent is mandatory, researchers may face obstacles in translating, improving, repurposing, or otherwise transforming scholarly content – activities that drive scientific progress by enabling broader dissemination of research results. This can hinder knowledge-sharing, complicate open licensing, and restrict interdisciplinary research, ultimately conflicting with certain Open Science principles.

Right of transformation

Article 33 of ZASP

(1) The right of transformation shall be the exclusive right to translate, adapt for stage, musically arrange, alter or otherwise transform a pre-existing work.

(2) The right referred to in the preceding paragraph shall also apply to cases where a pre-existing work is included or incorporated in a new work in unaltered form.

(3) The author of the pre-existing work shall retain the exclusive right to use the work derived from his work unless otherwise provided by this Act or by contract.

In contrast, ZASP explicitly regulates joint authorship of audiovisual works (e.g., films and TV productions) by specifying who qualifies as a “co-author of an audiovisual work” and who as an “author of contributions to an audiovisual work.”

Article 105 of ZASP designates specific contributors as co-authors of an audiovisual work. These are creators whose creative input is deemed so essential that they are recognised as co-authors of the audiovisual work as a whole, rather than merely as authors of their individual contributions (e.g., the script). In other words, without these contributions, the identity of the audiovisual work would fundamentally change, so the law grants them co-authorship status.

Co-authors of an audiovisual work

Article 105 of ZASP

(1) The following shall be considered as co-authors of an audiovisual work:

- 1. the author of the adaptation,*
- 2. the author of the screenplay,*
- 3. the author of the dialogue,*
- 4. the director of photography,*
- 5. the principal director,*

6. *the composer of music specifically created for use in the audiovisual work.*
(2) *If animation represents an essential element of the audiovisual work, the principal animator shall be considered as a co-author of that work.*

This entails the requirement of consensual management for co-authors. All the co-authors listed in Article 105 of ZASP must manage their rights in the audiovisual work consensually, meaning that no single co-author can unilaterally decide on the use of the audiovisual work without the consent of all the others. Co-authors can either grant their consent for the use of the audiovisual work or are entitled to remuneration.

Authors of contributions to an audiovisual work (e.g., scenographers, costume designers, and film editors) form a separate category under Article 106 of ZASP. These are creators who contribute artistic or creative elements to the audiovisual work but are not recognised as co-authors of the audiovisual work as a whole. Instead, they retain copyright only in their individual contributions.

In practice, both co-authors of an audiovisual work and authors of contributions to an audiovisual work rely on collective management organisations to manage certain rights (e.g., remuneration rights) on their behalf.²⁵

The requirement of consensual management for co-authors of an audiovisual work has significant implications for Open Access to and reuse of audiovisual works. If a co-author of an audiovisual work withholds consent, the work cannot be shared in accordance with Open Science principles, creating a barrier to Open Science. Even when co-authors of an audiovisual work agree to such distribution, the rights of authors of contributions to an audiovisual work must also be considered. These contributors retain copyright over their individual contributions (such as music, sets, costumes or editing). While they may have transferred the right to use their work within the audiovisual work, they still hold rights over uses beyond this context. For Open Access to and reuse of such works – enabling broader dissemination, adaptation, or remixing – additional consent or licensing may be required. This process is often managed through collective management organisations, which adds another layer of complexity and rigidity when seeking to align the use of audiovisual works with Open Science principles.

With research in different disciplines relying on access to and use of such audiovisual materials, the restrictions imposed by rightsholders here also serve to complicate research work in general, and in particular that taking place under Open Science principles.

II.2.1.2. Requirement of consensual management for compound works

Authors of compound works
Article 13 of ZASP

(1) *The provisions of the preceding Article shall apply, mutatis mutandis, in cases where several authors combine their works for exploitation in common.*

²⁵ In Slovenia, the collective management organisations AIPA, k.o. (for co-authors of an audiovisual work) and SAZAS Society, k.o. (for authors of contributions to an audiovisual work) are relevant in this regard;

According to Article 13 of ZASP, the rules set out in Article 12 of ZASP apply *mutatis mutandis* in cases where several authors combine their works for exploitation in common. Compound works may become less accessible if the authors cannot agree on their use. For instance, if one author wishes to make a compound work available under an open license, they cannot do so without the consent of all other authors. This can negatively affect the accessibility of research results for Open Science, limiting the dissemination of scientific information and hindering further research and innovation.

II.2.2. Barriers stemming from the unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation

Right to remuneration

Article 37 of ZASP

(1) The author shall have a right to **fair compensation** for sound or visual recording and photocopying of his work done within the scope of private or other internal use referred to in Article 50 of this Act.

(2) Remuneration referred to the preceding paragraph with respect to sound or visual recording shall be paid:

1. upon the first sale or importation of new devices for sound or visual recording and
2. upon the first sale or importation of new blank audio or video fixation media.

(3) Remuneration referred to in paragraph one of this Article with respect to photocopying shall be paid:

1. upon the first sale or importation of new devices for photocopying and
2. on photocopies made for sale, i.e. monthly depending on their probable number.

(4) For the purposes of this Act, importation shall be considered to be the release of goods into free circulation in accordance with the customs regulations of the European Community and any entry of goods into the territory of the Republic of Slovenia from other EU Member States.

(5) Photocopying under this Article shall be considered as equivalent to other similar reproduction techniques; devices for sound or visual recording shall be considered as equivalent to other devices which achieve the same effect.

(6) The right to remuneration under paragraph one of this Article may not be waived or assigned inter vivos or be subject to execution.

The rule of separate transfers

Article 76 of ZASP

(4) When the right of rental of phonograms or videograms containing a copyright work is transferred (Article 25), the author shall retain the right to equitable remuneration for each such rental. **The author may not waive this right.**

(5) Where the author transfers the right of rebroadcasting (Article 31), he shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each use of the work in the case of rebroadcasting. **The author may not waive this right.**

The right of audiovisual adaptation

Article 104 of ZASP

(3) Notwithstanding the provisions of the preceding paragraph, the author of a pre-existing work shall have:

3. the right to claim equitable remuneration from the film producer for each rental of videograms of an audiovisual work.

5. the right to receive equitable remuneration from the online content-sharing service provider for each communication to the public of the audiovisual work in the context of an online content-sharing service;

(4) The author of a pre-existing work may not waive the rights referred to in the preceding paragraph.

Film production contract

Article 107 of ZASP

(4) Notwithstanding the provisions of the preceding paragraphs:

3. the co-authors shall have the right to equitable remuneration from the film producer for each rental of videograms of an audiovisual work;

4. the co-authors shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each rebroadcasting of an audiovisual work;
5. the co-authors shall have the right to receive equitable remuneration from the online content-sharing service provider for each communication to the public of the audiovisual work in the context of an online content-sharing service;
6. the co-authors shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each communication to the public of the audiovisual work in the context of video-on-demand services;
7. the co-authors shall have the right to receive equitable remuneration for each act of making the audiovisual work available to the public for direct or indirect economic advantage other than that referred to points 5 and 6 of this paragraph.

(5) Co-authors and authors of contributions may not waive the rights referred to in the preceding paragraph.

The right to remuneration for communicating to the public a phonogram and videogram

Article 122 of ZASP

(1) A performer shall have the right to a share of the remuneration received by the phonogram producer for communicating to the public a phonogram in which his performance is fixed.

(2) A performer shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each broadcasting or any other communication to the public of a videogram of his performance. The remuneration shall be paid by the user to the performer.

(3) The performer may not waive the right under this Article.

The right to remuneration

Article 123 of ZASP

(1) A performer shall have the right to remuneration for the reproduction for private or other internal use under paragraph two of Article 37 of this Act.

(2) Where the performer has transferred to the phonogram producer or film producer the right to rent out phonograms or videograms containing his performance, the phonogram producer or film producer shall pay the performer fair compensation for such.

Presumption of transfer

Article 124 of ZASP

(1) By entering into a contract for film production, a performer shall be presumed to have transferred to the film producer, exclusively and without limitations, all economic rights in his performance unless otherwise provided by contract.

(2) For each economic right which was transferred under the preceding paragraph, the performer shall have the right to demand equitable remuneration from the film producer.

(3) The performer may not waive the right referred to in the preceding paragraph.

In the context of copyright law, unwaivability refers to the inability of authors or performers to renounce certain rights, even voluntarily. While unwaivability is typically intended to protect authors, it can create significant barriers for Open Science, by restricting the flexibility in rights management needed to ensure Open Access to and reuse of works. Unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation presumes that remuneration must be paid to the author for the use of a copyright work.

Within the Slovenian Copyright and Related Rights Act (ZASP), two distinct concepts of remuneration are recognised: 'fair compensation', as outlined in Article 37 of ZASP, and 'equitable remuneration,' addressed in other relevant Articles of ZASP. The unwaivability of this right applies to both copyright and related rights. Notably, in the context of related rights, such provisions are particularly common in rules pertaining to performers.

The unwaivability of rights enables collective management organisations to claim and collect remuneration/compensation on the author's behalf, irrespective of the author's clear intent to share their work freely under an open license. As a result, authors are unable to fully

exercise control over their works. This burdens providers – such as institutional repositories – who make available these works to the public, by imposing an obligation to pay remuneration/compensation, thereby limiting the availability of scientific and creative outputs to the wider community.

It is crucial, however, to differentiate between the concepts of ‘fair compensation’ and ‘equitable remuneration’. As confirmed in Recital 35 of the InfoSoc Directive,²⁶ ‘fair compensation’ is not interchangeable with ‘equitable remuneration’. The notion of ‘fair compensation’ is closely linked to the concept of harm, meaning that its determination should account for the “possible harm” or “prejudice to the rightsholders” resulting from the act in question. Hugenholtz, Guibault, and van Geffen emphasize that ‘fair compensation’ is required only when rightsholders suffer actual or potential harm, particularly in the context of private copying.

This is in contrast to ‘equitable remuneration,’ which is rooted in principles of natural justice and the German copyright doctrine of *Vergütungsprinzip*, under which authors are entitled to remuneration for every act of usage of their copyright works, irrespective of any actual harm. Consequently, whereas ‘equitable remuneration’ may be due even in cases where no demonstrable harm occurs, ‘fair compensation’ is only required where harm can be reasonably established. The distinction between these concepts introduced by the InfoSoc Directive, was also reflected in Slovenian copyright law, where the December 2006 Amendment to ZASP replaced the term “equitable remuneration” (Slo. *ustrezno nadomestilo*) in Article 37 with “fair compensation” (Slo. *pošteno nadomestilo*), thereby aligning with the principle that compensation should be tied to harm rather than a general entitlement to remuneration.

It follows that ‘fair compensation’ is not intended to address unauthorised uses such as piracy or private copying beyond applicable exceptions. Rather, it applies exclusively to legitimate private copying. Furthermore, logically, no ‘fair compensation’ should be due for content that is freely available on the web, nor should levies apply to digital private copies of Public Domain materials. More fundamentally, it should be conceptually impossible to collect ‘fair compensation’ when an author clearly wants to share their work under open licenses. By doing so, the author provides an agreement that they do not see themselves as suffering harm from uses such as use, sharing, reproduction, and more. Therefore, it should also be conceptually impossible to make the right to ‘fair compensation’ unwaivable, as is currently the case under Article 37 of ZASP. Since ‘fair compensation’ is premised on compensating harm, its collection in these circumstances is not only legally questionable but also contradicts the very principle upon which it is based. Moreover, it poses a significant barrier to Open Science principles, forcing authors and institutions committed to the open and free

²⁶ Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society, Official Journal L 167, 22/06/2001. Recital 35: “In certain cases of exceptions or limitations, rightsholders should receive fair compensation to compensate them adequately for the use made of their protected works or other subject-matter. When determining the form, detailed arrangements and possible level of such fair compensation, account should be taken of the particular circumstances of each case. When evaluating these circumstances, a valuable criterion would be the possible harm to the rightsholders resulting from the act in question. In cases where rightsholders have already received payment in some other form, for instance as part of a licence fee, no specific or separate payment may be due. The level of fair compensation should take full account of the degree of use of technological protection measures referred to in this Directive. In certain situations where the prejudice to the rightsholder would be minimal, no obligation for payment may arise.”;

dissemination of knowledge to comply with a compensation framework designed for an entirely different context. This ultimately takes away authors' control over their works, complicates rights management, and restricts access to scientific and creative outputs.

II.2.3. Barriers stemming from the requirement for specific, separate transfers of rights

In copyright law, the requirement for specific, separate transfers of rights can create significant barriers for Open Science by complicating rights management and limiting the flexibility authors need to make their works openly accessible. Instead of transferring a unified set of rights, authors must engage in separate negotiations for certain components, making the process more time-consuming and complex. This fragmentation can discourage authors from pursuing Open Access publication, ultimately restricting the dissemination and reuse of scientific outputs.

II.2.3.1 Requirement for specific, separate transfers of the right to remuneration

The rule of separate transfers

Article 76 of ZASP

(6) Where the author transfers the rights of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service (Article 163c), they shall have the right to receive equitable remuneration from the online content-sharing service provider for each use of the work in the case of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service.

Article 76(6) of ZASP presumes that the author retains the right to remuneration in cases where he transfers the rights of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service, such as a repository (Article 163c of ZASP). There needs to be a separate, specific transfer of this right otherwise, for example through an explicit agreement in a contract.

For instance, by uploading their work to a repository or similar platform, an author may believe they have transferred all economic rights (and with them the right to remuneration) to a particular work, assuming that full control over its use rests with the transferee. However, as the right to remuneration is not included in the transfer of other economic rights, this enables collective management organisations to claim and collect remuneration on behalf of the author.

Such a framework undermines the author's ability to fully align their work with Open Science principles and creates additional complexity in rights management, even in cases where the author has a clear intention to make their work freely accessible under an open licence.

II.2.3.2. Requirement for specific, separate transfers of rights for the use of copyright works

The rule of separate transfers

Article 76 of ZASP

(2) A transfer of the right of reproduction of a work (Article 23) shall not include the transfer of the right to save it in electronic form, or the right to its sound or visual fixation, unless otherwise provided by law or contract.

(3) A transfer of the right of distribution of copies of a work (Article 24) shall not include the transfer of the right of importation of such copies unless otherwise provided by law or by contract.

Article 76(2) of ZASP fragments the right of reproduction (Article 23 of ZASP) by dividing it into distinct components: ‘the right to save the work in electronic form’ and ‘the right to its sound or visual fixation’. It stipulates that a transfer of the right of reproduction does not automatically include these specific rights unless explicitly provided by law or agreed upon in a contract.

This fragmentation complicates rights management, as authors or rights holders must negotiate separate agreements or provisions for each of these components. Even if authors wish to make their works freely accessible under open licenses, the need to manage these divided rights individually can create additional legal and procedural hurdles. These complexities undermine the principles of Open Science.

Article 76(3) of ZASP provides another example of fragmentation of copyright, which concerns the right of distribution (Article 24 of ZASP). It should be noted that the right of distribution under ZASP covers only physical representations of works. Article 76(3) of ZASP states that transferring the right to distribute (physical) copies of a work does not include the right to import those copies unless explicitly provided by law or agreed upon in a contract. This subdivision separates ‘the right to distribute copies’ from ‘the right to import them’, adding complexity to rights management.

Although the right of distribution (which according to Slovenian law concerns physical copies of works) rarely applies to Open Science, the fragmentation of the right of reproduction in Article 76(3) of ZASP, should be highlighted, as it creates additional barriers for authors who wish to make their works freely accessible under open licenses, thereby undermining the principles of Open Science.

II.2.4. Barriers derived from the requirement for special consent of the author for subsequent transfers

Subsequent transfers

Article 78 of ZASP

(1) A right-holder to whom an economic right or other author’s right has been transferred may not further transfer this right to a third party without the consent of the author unless otherwise provided by contract.

The provision of Article 78 of ZASP grants the author control over the use of their work, even after transferring certain rights. Article 78(1) of ZASP stipulates that a right-holder to whom an economic right or another author's right has been transferred may not further transfer this right to a third party without the explicit consent of the author, unless otherwise provided by contract.

This represents a barrier for Open Science, as the restriction on subsequent transfers to a third party without the author's explicit consent complicates the dissemination of scientific works. For instance, if a research institution or individual holds the economic rights to a work but cannot easily transfer them to other researchers or institutions without obtaining the author's explicit consent, the accessibility of the work for Open Science purposes may be restricted.

Additionally, the requirement to secure the author's explicit consent for every subsequent transfer of rights to a third party creates significant administrative burdens in rights management. This provision, which was originally aimed to protect authors, can present a significant barrier to Open Science, as it complicates the process of clearing copyrights and hinders the process of dissemination of research results.

II.2.5. Barriers stemming from the requirement of formality

Formality
Article 80 of ZASP

(1) All transfers of economic rights or other author's rights and all authorisations shall be in writing unless otherwise provided by law.

(2) In the case of non-compliance with the preceding paragraph, any controversial or unclear stipulations shall be interpreted in favour of the author.

The provision on formality in Article 80 of ZASP requires that all transfers of economic rights or other author's rights, as well as all authorisations, must be made in writing unless otherwise provided by law. Furthermore, if the requirement for written form is not met, any controversial or unclear stipulations are presumed to be interpreted in favour of the author.

This implies a considerable additional administrative burden, with each of the (potentially numerous) transfers of rights requiring documentation. Researchers are unlikely to have the time or inclination to do this, while institutions and libraries are also not necessarily resourced to take on this responsibility. Such provisions represent a complication of processes that risks creating either legal uncertainty or a considerable drag on efforts to advance Open Science.

II.2.6. Barriers stemming from the presumption of the publisher's priority right

Publisher's priority right
Article 89 of ZASP

(1) The publisher who has acquired the right to publish a work in book form shall have, in relation to other publishers offering the same conditions, the priority right to publish the work in electronic form.

(2) The priority right under the preceding paragraph shall run for a period of three years from the agreed date of publication of the literary work. The publisher shall give a written statement of the author's written offer within 30 days of its receipt.

The provision of Article 89 of ZASP, which grants a publisher who has acquired the right to publish a work in book form a priority right to publish the work in electronic form, can pose a barrier for Open Science for several reasons.

First of all, it reduces flexibility for authors who wish to distribute their work through multiple channels. Secondly, it limits authors' ability to choose the best method of distribution for their work. Third, it grants the publisher a privileged position regarding the publication of the work in electronic form. Fourth, if the publisher fails to exercise the priority right or does so with delay, authors may still be unable to immediately publish their work in electronic form on other platforms, thereby restricting their rights. Finally, it represents a limitation as it gives a publisher who has acquired the right to publish the work in book form a preferential position over other publishers, including those offering potentially more favourable conditions for the electronic publication of the work.

This provision conflicts with the May 2025 amendment to the ZZrID (amendment ZZrID-C),²⁷ which introduced *Secondary Publishing Rights* into the Slovenian legal framework. As a result, ZZrID and ZASP are misaligned, creating legal uncertainty and potentially hindering the effective implementation of *Secondary Publishing Rights*.

²⁷ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 40/25;

II.3. Provisions in Slovenian Copyright Law that can be both barriers and enablers of Open Science

While certain provisions of copyright law unequivocally create barriers that restrict the openness and accessibility of scientific knowledge, some legal mechanisms can function both as barriers and enablers for Open Science, depending on how they are applied in practice. These provisions may initially appear to limit the ability of authors to manage their rights with open or free licences, yet in specific circumstances, they can also facilitate broader dissemination of research outputs. Whether a provision acts as a barrier or an enabler often depends on how rights holders – such as employers, publishers, or collective management organisations – interpret and enforce these rules. When aligned with Open Science principles, certain legal frameworks can encourage greater accessibility and reuse of scientific knowledge.

II.3.1. Barriers that might also act as enablers stemming from the presumption of transfer of economic rights from employees to employers

Copyright work created in the course of employment

Article 101 of ZASP

(1) When a copyright work is created by an employee in the execution of his duties or following instructions given by his employer (a copyright work created in the course of employment), it shall be deemed that the economic rights and other rights of the author to such work are exclusively transferred to the employer for a period of ten years from the completion of the work, unless otherwise provided by contract.

(2) After the expiry of the period referred to in the preceding paragraph, the rights referred to in the preceding paragraph shall revert to the employee; however, the employer may claim a new exclusive transfer of these rights for equitable remuneration.

Special rights

Article 102 of ZASP

(1) Notwithstanding the provisions of the preceding Article,

1. an employee shall retain the exclusive right to use a work created in the course of employment as part of his collected works.

2. it shall be deemed that economic rights and other rights of the author to a database and in a collective work are transferred exclusively and without limitations to the employer, unless otherwise provided by contract.

Article 101 of ZASP governs copyright works created in the course of employment. It stipulates that in cases where an employee creates a copyright work as part of their duties or following instructions from their employer, the economic rights and other rights of the author are deemed to be exclusively transferred to the employer for a period of ten years from the completion of the work, unless otherwise agreed by contract.

Article 102 of ZASP establishes that economic rights and other rights of the author (i.e., employee) to databases and collective works are transferred exclusively and without limitations to the employer, unless otherwise agreed by contract.

These provisions can present a significant barrier for rights management with open licences. They grant the employer full control over the economic rights to the works during the initial ten-year period. Thus, during this time, authors/employees cannot manage copyright on works created as part of their duties or following instructions from their employer, with open licences, as they do not own the rights. Any transfer of rights or licence of rights, including licence with open licenses, is null and void.

In specific cases where the obligations from the *Rights Retention* provisions within the Slovenian Decree on Open Science²⁸ apply, the provisions of Article 101 and 102 of ZASP can provide a barrier in cases where the employer and publisher do not agree to publish the work according to principles of Open Science. In such a case, the author is effectively unable to prevent/correct the situation, meaning that the legal mechanisms for *Rights Retention* in the Slovenian legal framework lose their effectiveness, as the decision ultimately rests with the employer.

Thus, the impact of Article 101 of ZASP on Open Science depends largely on the stance of the employer. While it has the potential to hinder Open Science when employers are not supportive, it could, in some cases, serve as a tool for advancing Open Science in cases when employers are committed to Open access principles even if the authors are not.

The same provisions can also serve as an enabler for Open Science in cases where the employer actively supports Open Access policies (even if the author does not). In this scenario, the exclusive rights held by the employer could facilitate open dissemination of the work, as the employer would have the authority to make it openly available without requiring any express permissions from the author (i.e., employee). Notably, after ten years, the rights revert to the employee; however, pursuant to Article 101(2) of ZASP, the employer may claim a new exclusive transfer of these rights in exchange for equitable remuneration (i.e., a form of compulsory licence).

Thus, the impact of Article 101 of ZASP on Open Science depends largely on the stance of the employer. While it has the potential to hinder Open Science when employers are not supportive, it could, in some cases, serve as a tool for advancing Open Science in cases when employers are committed to Open access principles even if the authors are not.

Comparable rules on the transfer of rights are also provided for specific types of copyright works, namely computer programs (Article 112. of ZASP) and databases (Article 141.e of ZASP), when these are created within an employment relationship or under certain contractual arrangements.

Employment and the contract to commission a copyright work

Article 112

Where a computer program is created by an employee in the execution of his duties or following instructions given by his employer, or where it is created by an author under a contract to commission a copyright work, it shall be deemed that the economic rights and other rights of the author to such a program are transferred to the employer or person commissioning the work, exclusively and without limitations, unless otherwise provided by contract.

²⁸ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 59/23;

Employment and contracts for work

Article 141e

Where a database is made by an employee in the execution of his duties or following instructions given by his employer, or where it is made by a person under a contract for work, it shall be deemed that the exclusive rights to such a database are exclusively and without limitations transferred to the employer or to the commissioning party, unless otherwise provided by contract.

Article 112 of ZASP stipulates that where a computer program is created by an employee in the execution of his duties or following instructions from the employer, or by an author under a contract to commission a copyright work, the economic rights and other rights of the author are deemed to be exclusively and without limitations transferred to the employer or commissioning party, unless otherwise agreed by contract.

Article 141e of ZASP adopts a similar approach for the so-called *sui generis* databases. It provides that where a *sui generis* database is made by an employee in the execution of his duties or following instructions from the employer, or by a person under a contract for work, the exclusive rights are deemed to be exclusively and without limitations transferred to the employer or commissioning party, unless otherwise agreed by contract.

As with Articles 101 and 102 of ZASP, these provisions may present a barrier for Open Science practices, as they establish a legal presumption that economic rights are, by default (i.e., unless otherwise provided by contract), exclusively transferred to the employer or commissioning party. Unlike Article 101 of ZASP, however, these transfers are not limited to a ten-year period, but apply without any time restriction, which may pose an even greater barrier to Open Science practices. As a result, authors do not hold the rights and therefore have no legal control over rights management, including decisions on whether the work can be disseminated under open licences. The possibility of enabling Open Science principles in such cases ultimately depends on the stance of the employer or the person commissioning the work.

II.4. Enablers in the Slovenian Copyright Law

For the purposes of this study, we define the ‘enablers’ to Open Science as a range of measures, policies, and strategies designed to encourage the adoption of Open Access publication. Examples of such enablers include legislative measures, such as national provisions establishing *Rights Retention* or *Secondary Publishing Rights*. These mechanisms simplify the process for researchers to share their work through open or free access, fostering broader dissemination and greater access to scientific knowledge, which are core principles of Open Science.

One enabler for Open Science within the Slovenian Copyright Law was identified: the exception for text and data mining (TDM) for scientific research under Article 57b ZASP. Apart from this exception.

The *Rights Retention* obligation and *Secondary Publishing Rights* are provided in the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Activity Act (ZZrID).²⁹ The absence of clear legal enablers for Open Science within ZASP leaves Slovenian Open Science initiatives dependent on national research law (i.e., ZZrID), which can at times conflict with ZASP, as well as on institutional policies and non-binding guidelines. This ultimately diminishes their overall effectiveness.

II.4.1. Enabler stemming from the exception for text and data mining for scientific research

Text and data mining for scientific research

Article 57b of ZASP

(1) Research organisations, publicly accessible archives, libraries, museums, film or audio heritage institutions and public broadcasting organisations, as well as persons belonging to research organisations and cultural heritage institutions, may freely reproduce works to which they have lawful access under the conditions laid down in this Article and shall carry out text and data mining operations referred to in paragraph one of the preceding Article on works to which they have lawful access for the purposes of scientific research under the conditions laid down in this Article, including the digitisation of analogue content and remote access to such content where this is necessary for the purposes of text and data mining.

(4) [...] If the use of any security and protection measures prevents a person from carrying out acts permitted under this Article, the author shall provide that person with access to and use of the works in accordance with this Article within a time limit not exceeding 72 hours.

(5) The sharing and making available to the public of the results of the text and data mining referred to in paragraph one of this Article shall be permissible provided that the extent of the text and data mining is limited by the intended purpose, is compatible with fair practice, does not conflict with normal use of the work and does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author.

(6) Any contractual stipulation contrary to this Article shall be null and void.

Article 57b of ZASP, which implements Article 3 of the DSM Directive,³⁰ introduces a specific exception allowing text and data mining (TDM) for scientific research, which can act as a powerful enabler of research, science and, of course, Open Science. It grants research organisations, publicly accessible archives, libraries, museums, film or audio heritage institutions, public broadcasting organisations, and persons affiliated with these institutions the right to freely reproduce works and carry out TDM operations, provided they have lawful access to the works. The exception allows for the digitisation of analogue content and the remote access to content where necessary for the purposes of TDM. This provision represents a significant legal basis for broadening access to knowledge and enabling data-driven research across institutions.

Further enabling the aims of Open Science, Article 57b(5) of ZASP expressly allows sharing and making available to the public the results of TDM, provided four cumulative conditions are met: (i) the use is limited by the intended purpose, (ii) it is compatible with fair practice, (iii) it does not conflict with the normal use of the work, and (iv) it does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author. Any contractual provision excluding or limiting this exception is null and void, which ensures that rights holders cannot contractually restrict its application. Rights holders also need to ensure that the beneficiaries of the

²⁹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 186/21 and 40/23;

³⁰ Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Text with EEA relevance.);

exception can effectively perform TDM and need to act within 72 hours or face sanctions.³¹ This strengthens the position of the beneficiaries of the exception and supports non-discriminatory access to legal tools for data analysis.

Despite its enabling potential, the repetition of conditions from the general rule of Article 46 of ZASP may result in this part of the exception being applied excessively restrictively, as institutions or publishers may default to more conservative licensing models out of legal caution or ambiguity.

General rule
Article 46 of ZASP

Limitations to copyright shall be permissible in cases laid down in this Section, provided that the extent of such use of copyright works is limited by the intended purpose, is compatible with fair practice, does not conflict with normal use of the work and does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author.

II.5. Barriers and enablers outside of copyright law in Slovenia

While copyright law directly governs the use and reuse of works, various legal frameworks outside copyright can create *de facto* copyright-like barriers that hinder Open Science principles by restricting access, reuse, and the dissemination of knowledge. These barriers, often found in national cultural heritage laws, impose restrictions that function similarly to copyright.

The cultural heritage laws in several EU Member States impose restrictions on the Public Domain by introducing an additional layer of protection for works that are no longer under copyright or were never under copyright.³² These laws impose the requirement to seek authorisation and, in many cases, payment of a fee for commercial use of faithful digital reproductions of cultural heritage works, including those in the Public Domain.³³ Essentially, legal or natural persons wishing to use these Public Domain works for commercial purposes or other uses specified by the law must obtain something that closely resembles a license.³⁴

The Slovenian Cultural Heritage Protection Act (Slo. *Zakon o varstvu kulturne dediščine*; hereinafter: ZVKD-1),³⁵ imposes limitations on uses of heritage that is protected as national monuments. Article 44 ZVKD-1 prohibits “the use of the image and name of a monument without the consent of the owner” for commercial purposes, stating that “[t]he owner may also determine the amount of compensation for use by consent.” Under this law, a “cultural monument” is defined as a heritage asset that has been declared a monument or is listed in the inventory book of an authorised museum and encompasses all kinds of cultural heritage.³⁶

³¹ Bogataj Jančič, Maja ‘Exceptions with teeth: the new Slovenian text and data mining provisions’ (2023). Available at: <<https://www.knowledgerights21.org/blog/exceptions-with-teeth-the-new-slovenian-text-and-data-mining-provisions/>>, last accessed in April 2025;

³² Communia Association. The right to use Public Domain heritage (Policy paper #20), page 2;

³³ Ibid.;

³⁴ Ibid.;

³⁵ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 16/08, 123/08, 8/11;

³⁶ For an overview of the varying national implementations of Article 14 across the EU, see COMMUNIA’s Post-DSM Copyright Report as well as the Europeana Knowledge Base, last accessed in March 2025;

Additionally, restrictions extend to research and non-commercial uses. If a new work is created based on such cultural heritage, it cannot be licensed under a CC-BY license, which permits both commercial and non-commercial uses.³⁷ Instead, it must be licensed under a CC-BY-NC license, which restricts commercial use. This legal requirement creates a barrier for Open Science by limiting the ability to freely share research outputs under open licenses that allow for unrestricted use, including commercial applications. In essence, while ZVKD-1 permits the use of protected cultural heritage for research purposes, such as integrating it into new works resulting from research, these new works cannot be made available under an open license permitting commercial use. This restriction presents a significant barrier to the potential for broader dissemination, reuse, and alignment with the principles of Open Science.

On the other hand, there are certain enablers for Open Science in the wider Slovenian legal framework. Namely, the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Activity Act (ZZrID)³⁸ mandates *Rights Retention* – a crucial mechanism for ensuring that publicly funded research remains openly accessible. The concept of *Rights Retention* is further detailed in the Decree on Open Science.³⁹ Compliance with the *Rights Retention* obligation functions not only as an enabler, but as an incentive for Open Science principles, reinforcing its uptake through financial conditions tied to research funding eligibility and legally prescribed sanctions for non-compliance.

In May 2025, an amendment to the ZZrID (amendment ZZrID-C)⁴⁰ was unanimously adopted by the National Assembly of the Republic of Slovenia (Slo. *Državni zbor Republike Slovenije*),⁴¹ officially implementing *Secondary Publishing Rights* into Article 41 of ZZrID.⁴² The amendment ZZrID-C entered into force in June 2025. *Secondary Publishing Rights* were recognised as a recommended and desirable solution in the EU Council Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy, and equitable academic publishing of May 2023,⁴³ as they provide additional legal support for ensuring Open Access to and reuse of publicly funded research outputs. Similar legislation has already been adopted in countries such as

³⁷ Creative Commons. Available at: <https://creativecommons.org>, last accessed in March 2025;

³⁸ The *Rights Retention* obligation was introduced in Slovenia already in 2021 with the ZZrID; Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 186/21 and 40/23;

³⁹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 59/23;

⁴⁰ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 40/25;

⁴¹ Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODPI. *Secondary Publishing Rights Adopted into Slovenian Legislation*. Available at: <https://www.odipi.si/en/secondary-publishing-rights-adopted-into-slovenian-law/>, last accessed in May 2025; Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Slovenia. *Amendment to the Scientific Research and Innovation Activity Act Confirmed*. Available at: <https://www.gov.si/novice/2025-05-21-dokoncno-potrjena-novela-zakona-o-znanstvenoraziskovalni-in-inovacijski-dejavnosti/>, last accessed in May 2025;

⁴² Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Slovenia (2024). *Act Amending and Supplementing the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act*. Available at: <https://e-uprava.gov.si/si/drzava-in-druzba/e-demokracija/predlogi-predpisov/predlog-predpisa.html?id=16439>, last accessed in May 2025;

⁴³ Council of the European Union (2023). *Council conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing*. Available at: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf>, last accessed in March 2025;

Bulgaria,⁴⁴ the Netherlands,⁴⁵ Italy,⁴⁶ Germany,⁴⁷ France,⁴⁸ Belgium,⁴⁹ and Austria⁵⁰ – Slovenia now joins them with the amendment ZZrID-C.⁵¹ However, unlike those countries, which amended their copyright legislation to introduce *Secondary Publishing Rights* into their respective national legal frameworks, Slovenia chose a different approach by incorporating *Secondary Publishing Rights* into its national research legislation (i.e., the ZZrID). The introduction of *Secondary Publishing Rights* significantly strengthens the legal certainty for researchers and research institutions with regard to fulfilling Open Science obligations. It complements and reinforces the existing *Rights Retention* obligation with an important legal presumption. This enables more effective rights management in line with Open Science principles.

Secondary Publishing Rights, as adopted in the newly added paragraphs 6 and 7 of Article 41 of the ZZrID,⁵² provide a legal basis for enabling Open Access to and reuse of publicly funded scientific publications and research data (i.e., research co-funded by public resources to a level of at least 50%). This right may be exercised by the author/researcher (or their employer) or by the provider of scientific research activities.

Secondary Publishing Rights in ZZrID establish a legal presumption that the transfer of copyright cannot be so exclusive as to prevent the author from depositing the work in an Open Access repository, since the author retains the necessary rights for such a deposit – even if, for example, the publisher demands exclusive transfer of economic rights. This measure serves not only as an enabler, but as an incentive for Open Science principles. It introduces financial rewards for compliance and legal consequences for non-compliance.

In particular, the adopted provision explicitly stipulates that any contractual provision preventing researchers or providers of scientific research activities from publishing or making available to the public the results of the research in a public Open Access repository shall be null and void. This legal presumption strengthens the position of researchers who might otherwise lack the negotiating power or legal knowledge to effectively retain the necessary rights to publish their research in a public Open Access repository. With the introduction of *Secondary Publishing Rights*, they are thus better positioned to comply with the *Rights Retention* obligation.

⁴⁴ Available at: <<https://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2024/02/09/introducing-a-zero-embargo-secondary-publication-right-in-bulgaria/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁴⁵ Available at: <<https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/stb-2015-257.html>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁴⁶ Available at: <<https://zenodo.org/records/5764841#.YidpCXrP13g>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁴⁷ Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_urhg/englisch_urhg.html>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁴⁸ Available at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_c/LEGIARTI000033205794/2016-10-09>, last accessed in March 2025,

⁴⁹ Available at:

<https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_g.pl?language=fr&la=F&table_name=loi&cn=2013022819>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵⁰ Available at: <<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10001848>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵¹ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 40/25;

⁵² Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 40/25; paragraphs 6 and 7 of Article 41 of the ZZrID: “(6) If the provider of scientific research activities or the researchers do not individually manage the rights in accordance with the first paragraph of this Article, the researcher or the provider of scientific research activities may publish or make available to the public the results of the scientific research activity in a public open access repository as soon as the result of the research has been accepted for publication, with due acknowledgement of the researcher and the source of the first publication. (7) Contractual provisions contrary to the preceding paragraph shall be null and void.”;

This amendment to the ZZrID provides an additional legal instrument that enables Open Access to and reuse of publicly funded scientific publications and research data. Going forward, researchers and research institutions in Slovenia will need further guidance on *Secondary Publishing Rights*, and repositories will need to be adapted accordingly.

III. REPORT ON BARRIERS AND ENABLERS FOR OPEN SCIENCE IN THE ITALIAN COPYRIGHT LAW

III.1. The structural, political and legal framework for Open Science in Italy

Aligning with European policies, Italy has adopted initiatives adapting national frameworks to ensure that research outputs, data, and knowledge are openly accessible. These initiatives are designed to enhance collaboration, improve transparency, and facilitate the sharing of research across borders, while fostering a more inclusive and accessible research environment. However, there is a lack of specific regulations that effectively enforce these principles, limiting the potential for greater dissemination of research and its broader impacts.

As an initial response to the objectives set out by the European Commission in the Recommendation of 17 July 2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information (2012/417/EU), the Italian Government issued the Decree-Law No. 91/2013, Article 4.⁵³ As will be explained later in the chapter about the enablers to Open Science outside of copyright law, this Decree-law establishes that public entities responsible for providing or managing research funding must independently adopt the necessary measures to promote Open Access to research results published in scientific journals, when the work is at least 50% publicly funded. However, this provision does not ensure that researchers have the actual right to make their work freely available to the public Open Access, regardless of other contractual obligations.

The Open Science National Plan⁵⁴ recommends including a requirement for Open Access to articles and monographs produced through publicly funded research in all calls for tenders and ensuring budget allocation for related costs, as well as establishing mechanisms for timely verification. Furthermore, the Plan aims to promote the interconnection of existing open repositories and ensure their interoperability at both national and European levels, leveraging developments such as OpenAIRE,⁵⁵ and linking publications, research projects, and expertise. Finally, the Plan encourages the creation of a national research data infrastructure to support the implementation of Open Science guidelines across all disciplines, as well as a public portal that consolidates, searches, and provides access to scientific outputs stored in repositories, in compliance with copyright regulations.

Unlike the Slovenian experience, Italy has not implemented *Rights Retention* strategies at the legislative level. Despite this, there are some universities which include this in their own

⁵³ Available at: <<https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2013-08-08;91>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵⁴ Available at: <<https://www.mur.gov.it/atti-e-normativa/decreto-ministeriale-n-268-del-28-02-2022>> and at: <https://www.mur.gov.it/news/lunedì-20062022/pubblicato-il-piano-nazionale-della-scienza-aperta>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵⁵ Available at: <<https://www.openaire.eu/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

institutional policies for OA. None of these make *Rights Retention* mandatory, but they do come close to this kind of strategy (the oldest are those of Trento, Turin, Florence and Bologna). The library of the European University Institute (EUI) of Florence⁵⁶ also supports researchers in *Rights Retention*, although it has a special legal regime because it is based in Italy but is not an “Italian institution”.

From a search in the Directory of Open Access Journals DOAJ,⁵⁷ with the following search filters “author retains all rights”, “without fees”, and “law journals”, there are twenty-one Italian journals that somehow adopt a *Rights Retention* strategy. However, their Right Retention statements should be evaluated individually, since they include different approaches.

In addition to universities, other research entities, institutions, and infrastructures support Open Science in Italy, such as the Italian National Research Council (CNR), the Conference of Italian University Rectors (CRUI), the Council of Presidents of Public Research Institutions (CoPer), the Italian Open Science Support Group (IOSSG) and the Nexa Centre for Internet & Society.

Another initiative to advocate and promote the adoption of Open Science is represented by the project “*Balancing Publication Rights: The Voice of the Scientific Community on Rights Retention and Secondary Publishing Right*”.⁵⁸ The project, funded by Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21), aims to support *Secondary Publishing Rights* (SPR) in the scientific field and promote *Rights Retention* by authors, backed up by national legislative change.

Finally, another concrete action toward adopting Open Science policies in education, research, and access to cultural heritage is represented by the Collective Initiative Supporting the Free Sharing and Dissemination of Knowledge,⁵⁹ promoted by the Italian KR21 National Coordinator and the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems of the National Research Council (IGSG-CNR), in collaboration with the Creative Commons Italy Chapter, Wikimedia Italy, AISA (Italian Association for the Promotion of Open Science), and the Open Education Italy Network. The collective initiative aims to achieve concrete and shared goals in the fields of Open Science, open culture, open education, and research data sharing. Through a series of concrete recommendations from a broad group of signatories, and addressed to policymakers, universities, research institutions, and researchers themselves, this Initiative aims to encourage a constructive dialogue between institutions, the wider scientific community and policymakers. Through this, the goal is to advocate for rules and policies that support an inclusive and accessible model of knowledge sharing, by highlighting critical issues in the current regulatory framework for research, education, and the protection of the Public Domain. The Initiative emphasises the need for legislative changes to make a

⁵⁶ See the right retention strategy of EUI library:

<<https://www.eui.eu/Research/Library/PublishingAndOpenScience/CopyrightAndOpenAccess>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵⁷ Available at: <<https://doaj.org/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵⁸ Available at: <<https://www.right2pub.eu/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁵⁹ Collective Initiative supporting the free sharing and dissemination of knowledge. Available at: <<https://www.igsg.cnr.it/2025/01/iniziativa-collettiva-a-sostegno-della-libera-condivisione-e-diffusione-della-conoscenza/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

reality of right to research, promote the use and sharing of open educational resources, and ensure that what is in the Public Domain remains free from restrictions.

The hope is that, through widespread endorsement, a shared commitment to a significant and lasting change will emerge in the landscape of research, free access to cultural heritage, and education in Italy. The document, which has already garnered numerous signatures, remains open for additional endorsements, in order to secure broad support before its formal submission to the relevant institutions. The recent endorsement by the President of CoPER (the Council of Presidents of Research Institutions) further underscores the growing strength and cohesion of the Italian network for Open Science and highlights the urgent need for active policy implementation in this direction.

III.2. Barriers and enablers for Open Science in Italian Copyright Law

In Italy, Law No. 633 of April 22, 1941, on the *Protection of Copyright and Other Rights Related to Its Exercise*⁶⁰ (hereinafter referred to as LdA) presents some challenges, containing certain provisions that may hinder or complicate the adoption of Open Science practices.

In this context, a comprehensive evaluation of Italy's copyright legal framework is crucial to identify provisions that either act as barriers to or enablers of Open Science. Italian Copyright Law, in force since 1941, has undergone numerous revisions, particularly from the late 1980s onward. However, without a comprehensive overhaul, it remains challenging to interpret, even for experts. The law often employs different terms to refer to the same concept (for example, visual art is also referred to as figurative works or works of art) and uses identical terms for different concepts and different terms for the same concept (for instance, terms like fair compensation, equitable remuneration, separate remuneration, and remuneration can overlap despite having distinct implications, such as when remuneration is intended to function as compensation). It is noted how the use of the terminology of fair compensation and equitable remuneration is confused in the LdA while in the Slovenian legislation it appears clearer.

The comparative analysis of Slovenian and Italian copyright laws revealed numerous similarities and a few notable differences.

⁶⁰ Law No. 633 of April 22, 1941, "Protection of Copyright and Other Rights Related to Its Exercise", Italian updated text available at: <<https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:1941-04-22;633!vig=>>>. The English translation can be found here: <<https://www.wipo.int/wipolex/en/text/477668>>. It leads to a version that is not updated (but it is a version updated in 2003)>, last accessed in March 2025;

III.2.1. Barriers stemming from the requirement for consensual management of copyright

The law requires consensual management when a work is created by two or more collaborators with the intention of regulating the joint exercise of copyright. Italian Copyright Law distinguishes between simple and complex works. Simple works result from a single creative contribution within the same artistic genre. They may originate from the creative efforts of a single author or from multiple authors collaborating. When multiple individuals contribute to the creative process, the outcome is considered joint work.

In legal doctrine, complex works are generally categorised into compound (or composite), collective, and derivative works.

Compound works consist of multiple creative contributions from different genres that maintain their autonomy. These contributions can be used separately, yet they also integrate into a unified work as essential elements. A classic example of a composite work is a cinematographic work, where various artistic elements (e.g., script, music, cinematography) come together while retaining individual significance.

Collective works are created by assembling works or parts of works that possess the character of autonomous creation. This assembly results from a deliberate selection and coordination aimed at achieving a specific literary, scientific, didactic, religious, political, or artistic purpose. Examples include encyclopaedias, dictionaries, anthologies, magazines, and newspapers. Collective works are protected as original creations independently and without prejudice to the copyright of the individual works or parts from which they are composed.

Finally, derivative works emerge from the creative elaboration of a pre-existing work of authorship. These works built upon existing material while introducing new, original elements are regulated under Article 4 of LdA, which, without prejudice to existing rights on the original work, also protects creative elaborations of the work itself.

While the need to regulate the rights arising from the creation of a joint work, compound work or collective work is clear, such measures create barriers to the dissemination of research and scientific collaboration, particularly in the context of Open Science.

III.2.1.1. Requirement of consensual management for co-authors

Co-authors
Article 10 of LdA

(1) If the work has been created by the indistinguishable and inseparable contributions of two or more persons, the copyright shall belong to all the joint authors in common.

(2) In the absence of proof of a written agreement to the contrary, the indivisible shares shall be presumed to be of equal value.

(3) The provisions which regulate property owned in common shall be applicable. Furthermore, moral right may be asserted, at any time individually by any one joint author; and the work, if unpublished, may not be published, nor be modified or utilized in a form differing from that of first publication, without the agreement of all the co-authors. However, in the event of unjustified refusal by one or more joint authors, publication, modification or new utilization of the work may be authorized by the judicial authority upon such conditions and terms as that authority may order.

In Italian copyright law, the regulation of co-authorship is governed by Art. 10 of LdA, which echoes the principles established in the Art. 12 of ZASP. In particular, similarly to the Slovenian framework, Italian law requires the consent of all co-authors for the exploitation of a work. This can create challenges for Open Science, particularly as research collaboration becomes deeper and more international. The same issue arises when one co-author refuses to allow a work to be shared openly, which could prevent the broader dissemination of knowledge within the scientific community.

III.2.1.2. Requirement of consensual management for compound works

Authors of musical compound works
Article 33 of LdA

(1) In the absence of specific agreements between the collaborators, the provisions of the following three articles shall apply to operas, operettas, melodramas, musical compositions with lyrics, and musical dances and ballets.

Authors of musical compound works
Article 34 of LdA

(1) The exercise of economic exploitation rights belongs to the author of the musical part, without prejudice to the rights arising from joint ownership between the parties.

(2) The profit from economic exploitation is divided in proportion to the value of the respective literary or musical contribution.

(3) In operas, the musical part is considered to represent three-quarters of the overall value of the work.

(4) In operettas, melodramas, musical compositions with lyrics, and musical dances and ballets, the value of both contributions is considered equal.

(5) Each collaborator has the right to use their work separately and independently, except as provided in the following cases.

Authors of musical compound works
Article 35 of LdA

(1) The author of the literary part may not use it in conjunction with another musical text, except in the following cases:

1. If, after delivering the final manuscript of the literary part to the composer, the latter does not set it to music within five years for an opera or operetta, or within one year for any other literary work intended for musical composition.

2. If, after the work has been set to music and deemed by both parties ready for performance or representation, it is not performed or staged within the time limits specified in the previous point, unless longer periods have been granted for performance or representation pursuant to Articles 139 and 141.

3. If, after an initial performance or execution, the work ceases to be performed or staged for a period of ten years in the case of an opera, oratorio, symphonic poem, or operetta, or for a period of ten years in the case of any other composition.

(2) In the cases provided for in points 2 and 3, the composer may otherwise use the music.

Authors of musical compound works

Article 36 of LdA

(1) In the case provided for in point 1 of the previous article, the author of the literary part regains full disposal of their work, without prejudice to any claim for damages against the composer.

(2) In the cases provided for in points 2 and 3, and without prejudice to the claim for damages mentioned in the previous paragraph, the joint ownership established over the already set-to-music work remains in effect. However, the work may only be performed or staged with the consent of both collaborators.

Authors of choreographic or pantomimic works

Article 37 of LdA

(1) In choreographic or pantomimic works, as well as in other compositions involving music, words, and dance or mime – such as musical revues and similar works – where the musical component does not play a primary role or hold principal value, the exercise of economic rights, unless otherwise agreed, belongs to the author of the choreographic or pantomimic part and, in the case of musical revues, to the author of the literary part.

(2) With the necessary adaptations, the provisions of Articles 35 and 36 apply to these works.

Definition and regulation of collective work

Article 3 of LdA

(1) Collective works, consisting of the bringing together of works or parts of works, which have the character of an independent creation, as a result of the selection and coordination for a specific literary, scientific, educational, religious, political or artistic purpose, such as encyclopedias, dictionaries, anthologies, magazines and newspapers, shall be protected as original works, independently and without prejudice to the copyrights in the works or parts of works of which they are composed.

The author of a collective work

Art. 7 of LdA

(1) The person who organises and directs the creation of the collective work shall be considered the author of the work.

Collective works, journals and magazines

Art. 38 of LdA

(1) In the collective work, unless otherwise agreed, the economic exploitation rights shall belong to the publisher of the work itself, without prejudice resulting from the application of Art. 7 LdA.

(2) Individual contributors to the collective work shall have the right to use their work separately, subject to the agreed covenants, and in default, to the following rules.

Authors of collective literary work

Art. 42 of LdA

(1) The author of the article or other work that has been reproduced in a collective work has the right to reproduce it in separate excerpts or collected in a volume, provided he or she indicates the collective work from which it is taken and the date of publication.

(2) In the case of articles that have appeared in magazines or newspapers, the author, unless otherwise agreed, also has the right to reproduce them in other magazines or newspapers.

The authors of a cinematographic works

Article 44 of LdA

(1) The author of the subject-matter, the author of the screenplay, the composer of the music and the artistic director shall be considered joint-authors of a cinematographic work.

The exercise of economic rights of cinematographic works

Art. 45 of LdA

(1) The exercise of the economic exploitation rights of a cinematographic work belongs to the person who organized the production, within the limits specified in the following articles.

(2) The person indicated as the producer on the film is presumed to be the producer of the cinematographic work.

The concept of compound works, which often involves the collaboration of multiple authors combining their individual contributions into a single work, is widespread across various creative and scientific fields.

Notably, the Italian Copyright Law does not provide the definition of compound works but, as it has been mentioned above, they are considered as those composed of multiple creative contributions of different types that retain their own autonomy, allowing them to be used separately while, at the same time, merging into a single work as essential elements of it.

Unlike Slovenian legislation, which provides a general rule (Article 13 of ZASP) requiring the unanimous consent of all involved authors for any decision regarding the use of a combined work, Italian Copyright Law offers detailed regulations on the different types of compound works, adding further complexity to the legal landscape in this area. In this context, the law could present barriers to the right to share publicly funded scientific work through deposit in public repositories.

Regarding the field of musical works, Articles 33 to 37 of LdA address dramatic musical works with words, as well as choreographic and work of pantomime.

These works, generally created by one or more authors, fall under the category of “compound works”.

The general rule establishes that the economic exploitation rights are exercised by the author of the musical component, without prejudice to the rights arising from joint ownership among contributors.

Furthermore, those provisions are dispositive rather than imperative, meaning they apply only in the absence of a specific agreement between collaborators. This framework governs

operas, operettas, monologues, musical compositions with words, and dance and ballet music.

A specific regulation is dedicated to collective works, as defined and regulated by Art. 3 and Art. 7 of LdA. They consist of the bringing together of works or parts of works, which have the character of an independent creation, as a result of the selection and coordination for a specific literary, scientific, educational, religious, political or artistic purpose. They are protected as original works, independently and without prejudice to the copyrights in the works or parts of works of which they are composed. The author of the work is the one who organises and directs the creation of the collective work.

Moreover, Chapter IV of LdA is dedicated to “Special rules on the rights of economic use for certain categories of works”. In this, Section II, Art. 38, is dedicated specifically to “Collective works, journals and magazines”. This includes provisions to the effect that in a collective work, unless otherwise agreed, economic exploitation rights belong to the publisher of the work itself, without prejudice resulting from the application of Art. 7 of LdA. Individual contributors to the collective work shall have the right to use their work separately, subject to the agreed covenants, and in default, to the following rules.

In the field of collective literary works, Art. 42 of LdA is relevant. This provides that the author of the article or other work that has been reproduced in a collective work has the right to reproduce it in separate excerpts or collected in a volume, provided he or she indicates the collective work from which it is taken and the date of publication.

In the case of articles that have appeared in magazines or newspapers, the author has the same right to reproduce them in other magazines or newspapers, unless otherwise agreed. (par. 2, Art. 42 of LdA).

This means that, in the presence of a publishing contract for printed works, the author may lose the freedom to share their work Open Access, based on the agreement signed with the publisher. This is a common situation, considering the author's weaker position in negotiations with the publisher. Art. 42 of LdA has been the subject of proposed amendments aimed at overcoming its contractual override effect, as well as at extending its scope. In particular, there was a proposal to introduce a new Article 42-bis, intended to recognise an Open Access republication right for authors of scientific articles. However, the bill presented during the XVIII Legislature was not approved.⁶¹

These developments highlight the complexity of the issue and the need for an open and constructive dialogue among various stakeholders. The comparison with legislative models adopted in other European countries which have introduced or are considering introducing *Secondary Publishing Rights* has provided a valuable benchmark for evaluating potential solutions within the Italian context. It has also inspired a new proposal to adopt a system that enables open sharing of scientific knowledge. The understanding that knowledge sharing is the fundamental prerequisite for the very existence of science – as a collective process of

⁶¹ DDL n. 1146, “Modifiche all’articolo 4 del decreto-legge 8 agosto 2013, n. 91, convertito, con modificazioni, dalla legge 7 ottobre 2013, n. 112, nonché introduzione dell’articolo 42-bis della legge 22 aprile 1941, n. 633, in materia di accesso aperto all’informazione scientifica.

research and creation based on collaboration and critical review of results – is the foundation on which to build legislative tools that facilitate Open Access to and reuse of scientific knowledge.

Advocates for Open Science in Italy are in particular promoting the introduction of a new Article 42 bis to LdA, which could offer the opportunity for specific regulations regarding scientific works, granting authors the right – protected from override by terms to the contrary in agreements – to deposit their work in institutional repositories when the research is publicly funded.

The wording of the law proposal is the following:

- 1. The author of a scientific work created as part of research funded wholly or partially by public funds retains the right to disseminate it, in whole or in part, in educational or scientific repositories, not for profit, after acceptance for publication by a publisher, with the obligation to mention the journal and the publisher where the publication took place.*
- 2. Any agreement contrary to the provisions of the previous paragraph is null and void.*

Finally, as a compound work, cinematographic works are also subject to specific regulations. Art. 44 of LdA recognises as joint-authors all of the authors of the subject-matter, the author of the screenplay, the composer of the music and the artistic director. In this regard, Article 45 of the LdA facilitates the management of economic exploitation rights by assigning the exercise of these rights to the film producer.

The rules governing rights in compound and collective works, along with the legal requirements governing the use and dissemination of such works, can pose significant barriers to the principles of Open Science. They can raise significant possibilities to restrict the uses that researchers can make of works, as well as making it harder to make outputs Open Access with legal certainty. These barriers are particularly problematic in collaborative research environments, where the timely sharing of data and findings is essential for scientific progress and innovation.

III.2.2. Barriers stemming from the unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation

Equitable Remuneration for public performance of broadcasted works
Art. 58 of LdA

(1) For the performance in public premises by means of sound radio receivers, equipped with loudspeakers, of broadcasted works, an equitable remuneration is payable to the author, which is determined periodically by agreement between the Italian Society of Authors and Publishers (S.I.A.E.) and the representation of the relevant trade union association.

Reprography
Art. 68 of LdA

(1) The reproduction of a work or excerpts of works for personal use by readers, whether by hand or by means of reproduction that are not suitable for distribution or public dissemination of the work, is free.

(2) The photocopying of works available in public libraries, school libraries, public museums, or public archives is free, provided that such copying is carried out by these institutions for their own services, without any direct or indirect economic or commercial benefit.

(2-bis) Cultural heritage institutions, as referred to in Article 70-ter, paragraph 3, for preservation purposes and to the extent necessary for this purpose, always have the right to reproduce and make copies of works or other protected materials that are permanently present in their collections, in any format and on any medium. Any agreement that limits or excludes this right is null and void.

(3) Without prejudice to the prohibition on reproducing musical scores and sheet music, the reproduction of works of intellectual creation for personal use, by photocopying, xerocopying, or a similar reproduction system, is permitted up to a limit of fifteen percent of each volume or issue of a periodical, excluding pages of advertisements.

(4) The operators of reproduction points or centers, who use within their premises or make available to third parties, even free of charge, photocopying, xerocopying, or similar reproduction equipment, must pay a **compensation** (n.d.r. named in the law as "compenso") to the authors and publishers of the intellectual works published in the prints that are reproduced by these machines for the uses provided for in paragraph 3. The amount of this fee and the methods for collecting and distributing are determined according to the criteria set forth in Article 181-ter of this law. Unless otherwise agreed between SIAE and the associations of the interested categories, this fee may not be less than the average price per page, as annually recorded by ISTAT for books, for each page reproduced.

(5) Reproductions for personal use of works available in public libraries, made within the libraries using the means referred to in paragraph 3, may be freely carried out within the limits set by the paragraph 3, with the payment of a lump-sum fee to the rights holders, as per paragraph 2 of Article 181-ter, determined according to the second sentence of paragraph 1 of the Article 181-ter. This fee is paid directly each year by the libraries, within the limits of the revenues collected for the service, without additional costs for the State budget or for the entities to which the libraries are accountable. The limits referred to in paragraph 3 do not apply to works outside editorial catalogs and rare works, as they are difficult to find on the market.

(6) The distribution to the public of the copies referred to in the previous paragraphs and, in general, any use in competition with the economic rights of use granted to the author is prohibited.

Right to fair compensation for summary, quotation or reproductions of excerpts or parts of a work
Art. 70, par. 2 of LdA

(1) The summary, quotation, or reproduction of excerpts or parts of a work, as well as their communication to the public, are permitted if carried out for purposes of criticism or discussion, within the limits justified by such purposes and provided they do not compete with the economic exploitation of the work. When used for teaching or scientific research purposes, the use must also be for illustrative purposes and non-commercial ends.

(2) In anthologies for scholastic use, reproduction may not exceed the amount determined by regulation, which sets the method for determining fair compensation.

The reproduction of radio and television broadcasts made by public hospitals and institutions for prevention and punishment
Article 71-quater

The reproduction of radio and television broadcasts made by public hospitals and institutions for prevention and punishment is allowed for internal use only, provided that the rights holders receive **equitable compensation** determined by a decree of the Minister for Cultural Heritage and Activities, after consulting the committee referred to in Article 190.

Rights of Artists Performers
Article 80, paragraph (2), (f)

(2) Artists Performers have, regardless of any remuneration they are entitled to for live artistic performances, the exclusive right to:

[...]

(f) authorize the rental or lending of recordings of their artistic performances and their reproductions. The artist performer, even in the case of the transfer of the rental right to a phonographic or cinematographic or audiovisual works

or moving image sequences producer, retains the right to receive **equitable remuneration (n.d.r. "equa remunerazione")** for the rental made by the producer with third parties. Any agreement to the contrary is void. In the absence of an agreement between the interested parties, this compensation is established by the Authority for Communications Guarantees, according to the procedures set out in a specific regulation to be adopted within sixty days from the entry into force of this provision.

Equitable Remuneration for photographic images

Art. 88 of LdA

(1) The photographer holds the exclusive right of reproduction, distribution, and sale of the photograph, subject to the provisions set forth in Section Two of Chapter Six of this Title regarding portraits and without prejudice to the copyright on the reproduced work in the case of photographs depicting works of visual art.

(2) However, if the photograph is created in the course of and in fulfilment of an employment or work contract, within the limits of the contract's scope and purpose, the exclusive right belongs to the employer.

(3) In the absence of agreement to the contrary, the same shall apply in favour of the person who commissions photographs of objects in his possession, subject to the payment of equitable remuneration to the photographer by any person who commercially utilizes the reproduction.

(4) The Minister of Culture, with the rules established in the regulation, may set special rates to determine the remuneration due for the use of photography protected by neighbouring right which reproduces images of persons or of aspects, elements or facts of natural or social life, obtained by the photographic or similar process, including reproductions of works of figurative art and stills from motion picture films.

Fair compensation for the reproduction of photographs in anthologies for scholastic use and in scientific or educational works or published in newspapers or other periodicals, concerning persons or facts of current interest or otherwise of public interest

Art. 91 of LdA

(1) Reproduction of photographs in anthologies for scholastic use and in scientific or educational works in general is lawful against payment of fair compensation which shall be determined in the forms prescribed by the regulations.

(2) The reproduction must indicate the name of the photographer and the date of the year of manufacture, if they result from the photograph reproduced.

(3) The reproduction of photographs published in newspapers or other periodicals, concerning persons or facts of current interest or otherwise of public interest, shall be lawful upon payment of fair compensation.

(4) The provisions of the last paragraph of Article 88 shall apply.

Fair compensation for the reproduction of plans of engineering works

Art. 99, par. 1, of LdA

(1) The author of plans of engineering works, or other similar works, which constitute original solutions to technical problems, shall be entitled, in addition to the exclusive right to reproduce the plans and drawings of the projects thereof, the right to fair compensation to be paid by those who carry out the technical project for profit without his consent. In order to exercise the right to remuneration, the author must place a reservation statement over the plan or drawing and execute the filing of the plan or drawing with the Ministry of Culture in accordance with the rules established by the regulations.

The right to compensation provided for in this article lasts twenty years from the day of filing prescribed in the second paragraph.

Fair compensation publishers of press publications for the online use of their press publications

Art. 43-bis, par. 8, of LdA

(1) A right of fair compensation is granted to publishers of press publications for the online use of their press publications by information society service providers. AGCOM shall adopt a regulation to identify the reference criteria for determining the equitable remuneration taking into account, among other things, the number of online consultations of the article, the years of activity and market relevance of the publishers and the number of journalists employed, as well as

the costs incurred for technological and infrastructure investments by both parties, and the economic benefits derived, to both parties, from the publication as regards visibility and advertising revenues.

**Separate and additional remuneration the authors of cinematographic and assimilated works
additional remuneration of performing artists**

Art. 46, par. 3 and par. 4, of LdA

(3) The authors of the music, musical compositions, and lyrics accompanying the music are entitled to receive a separate remuneration directly from those who publicly screen the work. In the absence of an agreement between the parties, the remuneration is determined according to the provisions of the regulations.

(4) The authors of the subject and screenplay, the artistic director, dialogue adapters, dubbing directors, and translators, as well as performing artists, both leading and supporting, including voice actors, are entitled to receive an additional remuneration in the form of a percentage of the revenues from the public screenings of the work. This compensation is non-waivable, and its forms and amounts are determined through agreements between the relevant categories.

Appropriate and proportionate remuneration of the authors of cinematographic and assimilated works

Art. 46-bis of LdA

(1) Without prejudice to the provisions of Article 46, in the event of transfer of the broadcasting right to the producer, the authors of cinematographic and assimilated works shall be entitled to appropriate and proportionate remuneration charged to broadcasting organizations for each use of such works by means of communication to the public over the air, by cable and by satellite.

(2) For each use of cinematographic and assimilated works other than that provided for in Paragraph 1 and Article 18-bis, par. 5, the authors of the works themselves shall be entitled to fair compensation payable by those exercising the exploitation rights for each separate economic use.

(3) For each use of cinematographic and related works originally expressed in a foreign language, it shall also be due appropriate and proportionate compensation to the authors of the elaborations constituting translation or adaptation of the Italian language version of the dialogues.

(4) Each remuneration among those provided for in paragraphs 1, 2 and 3 is unwaivable and, in the absence of an agreement to be concluded between the categories concerned as identified in Article 16, first paragraph, of the Regulation, shall be established by the Communications Guarantee Authority (AGCOM) in accordance with the procedures provided for by special regulations to be adopted within sixty days of the entry into force of this provision.

Adequate, proportionate and appropriate remuneration of performing artists

Article 84 of LdA

(1) Unless otherwise agreed by the parties, it is presumed that performing artists have transferred the rights of fixation, reproduction, broadcasting, including communication to the public via satellite, distribution, as well as the right to authorize rental, at the time of signing the contract for the production of a cinematographic or audiovisual work or a sequence of moving images.

(2) Performing artists who play a role of significant artistic importance, even if a secondary role, in a cinematographic or assimilated work (including transmitted theatrical works) are entitled to appropriate and proportionate remuneration for each use of the cinematographic or assimilated work (including transmitted theatrical works) by means of communication to the public via air, cable, and satellite, to be paid by the broadcasting organizations.

(3) For each use of cinematographic and assimilated works (including transmitted theatrical works) other than those provided for in Paragraph 2 and Article 80, Paragraph 2, Letter e), performing artists identified in Paragraph 2 are entitled to appropriate and proportionate remuneration from those exercising the exploitation rights for each distinct economic use.

(4) The remuneration provided for in Paragraphs 2 and 3 is non-waivable, and in the absence of an agreement between the parties concerned, it shall be determined by the Communications Regulatory Authority (AGCOM) according to the procedures established by a specific regulation to be adopted within sixty days of the entry into force of this provision.

Equitable remuneration in the case of rental

Art. 18 bis of Lda

(1) The exclusive right to rent has as its object the transfer for use of the originals, copies or media of works, protected by copyright, made for a limited period of time and for the purpose of achievement of direct or indirect economic or commercial benefit.

(2) The exclusive right of lending has as its object the transfer for use of originals, copies or media of works, protected by copyright, made by institutions open to the public, for a limited period of limited time, for purposes other than those referred to in paragraph 1.

(3) The author shall have the exclusive right to authorize rental or lending by third parties.

(4) The above rights and powers shall not be exhausted by the sale or distribution in any form of the originals, copies or media of the works.

(5) The author, even in the event of the assignment of the rental right to a phonogram producer or cinematographic or audiovisual works or sequences of moving images, shall retain the right to obtain equitable remuneration for the rental concluded by him in turn with third parties.

(6) Any agreement to the contrary shall be null and void. In the absence of an agreement to be concluded between the categories concerned as identified in Article 16, first paragraph of the Regulation, said remuneration shall be established by the Communications Regulatory Authority in accordance with the procedures set forth in special regulations to be adopted within sixty days from the date of entry into force of this provision.

(6) Paragraphs 1 through 4 shall not apply in relation to plans or drawings of buildings and works of applied art.

Fair compensation for the private reproduction of phonograms and videograms

Article 71 septies of LdA

(1) Authors and phonogram producers, original producers of audiovisual works, performers and executing artists, and producers of videograms, as well as their successors, are entitled to compensation for the private reproduction of phonograms and videograms as outlined in Article 71-sexies. This compensation is constituted, for devices exclusively intended for the analog or digital recording of phonograms or videograms, by a share of the price paid by the final purchaser to the retailer. For multifunctional devices, this share is calculated on the price of a device with equivalent characteristics to the internal recording component, or, if this is not possible, by a fixed amount per device. For audio and video recording media, such as analog and digital media, fixed or transferable memories intended for recording phonograms or videograms, the compensation consists of a sum proportionate to the recording capacity of the media. For remote video recording systems, the compensation is owed by the service provider and is calculated based on the remuneration obtained for the provision of the service.

(2) The compensation described in paragraph 1 is determined, in compliance with EU regulations and taking into account reproduction rights, by decree of the Minister for Culture, to be issued by December 31, 2009. The determination involves consultation with the committee referred to in Article 190 and the most representative trade associations of the producers of the devices and media mentioned in paragraph 1. When determining the compensation, consideration is given to whether technological measures pursuant to Article 102-quater are applied, as well as the differing impact of digital copying compared to analog copying. The decree is subject to a triennial update.

(3) The compensation is owed by those who manufacture or import the devices and media mentioned in paragraph 1 into the national territory for profit. These entities must submit a quarterly declaration to the Italian Society of Authors and Publishers (SIAE), showing the sales made and the remuneration owed, which must be paid simultaneously. In the event of non-payment, the distributor of the devices or recording media is jointly liable for the payment.

(4) Violation of the obligations set out in paragraph 3 is punishable by an administrative fine equal to twice the compensation owed and, in more serious or repeated cases, by the suspension of the license or authorization to operate the commercial or industrial activity for a period ranging from fifteen days to three months, or by the revocation of the license or authorization.

Remuneration of phonogram producers and performers

Art. 73 of LdA

(1) *The phonogram producer, as well as performers artists who have made the interpretation or performance fixed or reproduced in the phonograms, regardless of the distribution, rental and lending rights to which they are entitled, shall be entitled to remuneration for the profit-making use of the phonograms by means of cinematography, radio and television broadcasting, including communication to the public by satellite, at public dance parties, in public establishments and on the occasion of any other public use of the phonograms. The remuneration is recognized, for each phonogram used, separately to the phonogram producer and to the performing or executing artists. The exercise of this right belongs to each of the companies engaged in the intermediary activity of rights related to copyright, as outlined in Article 3, paragraph 2, of the decree of the President of the Council of Ministers, December 19, 2012, published in the Official Gazette No. 59 on March 11, 2013, to which the phonogram producer and the performing or executing artists have granted their respective mandates in writing.*

(2) *The amount of the remuneration, the distribution shares, and the related methods are determined according to the provisions of the regulation.*

(2-bis) *The remuneration owed to the performing or executing artists under paragraphs 1 and 2 cannot be waived by them nor can it be transferred in any way.*

(3) *No remuneration is owed for use for teaching purposes or institutional communication made by the State Administration or entities authorized by the State.*

Equitable remuneration of phonogram producers and performers in case of non-profit purposes uses

Art. 73-bis of LdA

(1) *Performing artists and the phonogram producers are entitled to equitable remuneration even when the use referred to in Article 73 is made for non-profit purposes.*

(2) *Unless otherwise agreed by the parties, this compensation is determined, collected, and distributed according to the provisions of the regulation.*

Additional, adequate, and fair remuneration of authors and performing artists

Article 110-quinquies of LdA

(1) *Without prejudice to what is established in this regard by collective agreements, authors and performing artists, directly or through collective management organizations or independent management entities referred to in Legislative Decree No. 35 of March 15, 2017, are entitled to additional, adequate, and fair remuneration from the party with whom they have entered into a contract for the exploitation of their rights or from its successors, if the agreed remuneration proves to be disproportionately low compared to the income generated over time from the exploitation of their works or artistic performances. This includes all possible types of income derived from the exploitation of the work or artistic performance, in any form and for any purpose, including the online availability of phonograms.*

(2) *The provisions of paragraph 1 do not apply to contracts concluded by collective management organizations and independent management entities referred to in Article 2, paragraphs 1 and 2 of Legislative Decree No. 35 of March 15, 2017.*

The LdA provides authors and related rights holders the right to receive a remuneration/equitable remuneration or a fair compensation in different situations. In cases where it is expected that the payment resulting from such situations cannot be waived by the rights holder benefiting from it, this may create barriers to the implementation of Open Access principles.

Italy implemented Directive 29/2001/EC on copyright and related rights in the Information Society⁶² through Legislative Decree No. 68/2003,⁶³ which amended the Copyright Law (LdA).

However, also in this occasion the legislator didn't revise the various above-mentioned terminology already existing in the Italian Copyright law with the aim to harmonise them to the principle expressed in Recital 35 of the Infosoc Directive.

LdA, while not explicitly using these terms uniformly, adopts principles that can be linked to both definitions of fair compensation and equitable remuneration. In contexts related to private copying, the law recognises the right to receive a fair compensation (named in the law as "*compenso*"). In the context of the private copying regulation, the exclusive right of reproduction is downgraded by law to the right to receive equitable compensation, in order to compensate authors and other related rights holders for the damage they suffer from potential unauthorised personal reproductions, given the difficulty of managing such types of uses individually.

In some cases, the law provides fair compensation for summary, quotation or reproductions of excerpts or parts of a work in anthologies for scholastic use (Art. 70 (2), of the LdA), named by the law as "*equo compenso*". Also, the law provides the payment of "*equo compenso*" in the case of the reproduction of photographs in anthologies for scholastic use and in scientific or educational works or published in newspapers or other periodicals, concerning persons or facts of current interest or otherwise of public interest (Art. 91 of LdA). The same "*equo compenso*" is recognised in the case of the reproduction of plans of engineering works (Art. 99 (1) of LdA) or for the publishers of press publications for the online use of their press publication (Art. 43-bis (8) of LdA).

Forms of equitable remuneration are provided in cases where it is difficult for the user to obtain authorisation from individual rights holders. In these cases, the law establishes collective bargaining for setting tariffs between collective management organisations and the representatives of the involved parties. This is, for example, the case with Article 58 and Articles 73 and 73-bis of the LdA, which respectively establish that the author, in the first case, and artists performers and phonographic producers, in the second case, are entitled to receive payment of a "*compenso*", named by the law as "*equo compenso*" (but more accurately, "equitable remuneration") in the event of public performance of broadcasted works in public premises. The amount of this payment is determined periodically by the Italian Society of Authors and Publishers (SIAE) and the representatives of the relevant trade union association. This applies, for example, to music played in bars, restaurants, and stores, where the public enters for a purpose other than enjoying the broadcasted performance.⁶⁴ These are the cases of compulsory licenses, where the author cannot oppose, within certain limits, the distribution of the work, while retaining the right to equitable remuneration.

⁶² Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society. Available at: <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2001/29/oj/eng>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁶³ Legislative Decree No. 68 of April 9, 2003, Implementation of Directive 2001/29/EC on the harmonization of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the Information Society. Available at: <<https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2003;068>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁶⁴ However, the author's consent is required when the broadcasted work is performed in venues where the public attends specifically to listen to it (such as theaters or cinemas).

In the case of reproduction of photographic images for commercial use (Article 88 of the LdA), the payment of a fair remuneration (named in the law as "*equo corrispettivo*") is required to be made to the photographer by those who commercially use the reproduction of a photograph created on commission.

A separate remuneration also pertains to cinematographic and assimilated works and phonograms. Article 46 (3) of LdA grants authors of music, musical compositions, and the lyrics accompanying the music the right to receive a separate remuneration (named by the law as "*compenso separato*") directly from those who publicly screen the work. Paragraph 4 expands the group of individuals entitled to this remuneration, including translators, dialogue adaptors, dubbing directors, primary and secondary artists, performers, and voice actors. The remuneration (named by law as "*ulteriore compenso*" referred to in paragraph 4 of Article 46 of LdA) is unwaivable (with the consequence that any waiver will be nullified), and the determination of its amount is left to agreements between the categories concerned.

Article 46-bis of LdA establishes the right of authors of cinematographic and assimilated works to receive appropriate and proportionate remuneration (named by the law as "*compenso adeguato e proporzionato*") for the use of their works from broadcasting organisations for each public communication of the work via air, cable, or satellite, when broadcasting rights are transferred to a producer.

Furthermore, Art. 84 of LdA relates to performing artists who have a part of considerable artistic importance in the cinematographic and assimilated works (including theatrical works, when broadcasted). It offers them the right to adequate and proportionate remuneration (named by the law as "*compenso adeguato e proporzionato*"). In this case, the remuneration is unwaivable, and the law delegates to the Communications Regulatory Authority (AGCOM) the task of determining it in the event of disagreement between the parties involved.

As mentioned above, the law also provides the right of an equitable remuneration in the case of rental right (Art. 18-bis of Lda) and a fair compensation for private copying (Art. 71-septies of LdA), both of which cannot be waived.

Art. 71-septies of LdA provides that phonogram authors and producers, as well as original producers of audiovisual works, performers and producers of audiovisual recordings, and their successors in title, shall be entitled to fair compensation (named by the law as "*compenso*") for the private reproduction of phonograms and videograms referred to in Article 71-sexies of LdA. The burden of paying the fee in question is on the producer of the medium that enables the analogue or digital recording of the phonogram/videogram. The amount due is determined in relation to the price of the device and its recording capacity.

Furthermore, the LdA states that it is within the competence of collective management organisations to allocate remuneration (named by the law as "*compenso*") due to performers and phonogram producers for so-called secondary uses. These include profit-making uses through cinematography, radio and television broadcasting, including public communication via satellite, in dance events, public premises, and during any other public use, respectively, of performances/interpretations and phonograms (pursuant to Article 73 of the LdA).

Additionally, they are responsible for distributing equitable remuneration (named by the law as “*equo compenso*”) in cases where such uses are made for non-profit purposes (pursuant to Article 73-bis of the LdA).

Following the implementation of Directive the on Copyright in the Digital Single Market (hereinafter referred to DSM Directive),⁶⁵ Article 110-quinquies of LdA provides that, except as established in this regard by collective agreements, authors and performers, directly or through collecting societies, are entitled to appropriate and equitable additional remuneration (named by the law as “*remunerazione ulteriore, adeguata ed equa*”) from the party with whom they have entered into a contract for the exploitation of rights or its successors in title. This applies if the agreed remuneration proves to be disproportionately low compared to the income earned over time from the exploitation of their works or artistic performance, considering all possible types of income derived from the exploitation of the artistic work or performance, in any capacity and in any form, including making the phonograms available online. Said provisions, pursuant to paragraph 2 of the Article under review, do not apply to contracts concluded through collecting societies.

The cases of unwaivability of the right to remuneration, whether framed as “fair compensation” or “equitable remuneration”, can create obstacles for Open Science. The unwaivable right to remuneration presents challenges for the Open Science movement, as it imposes financial and administrative barriers that hinder the free and widespread dissemination of research. The inability of authors to fully control their works and the additional costs for those sharing these works impede the goal of making scientific knowledge freely accessible.

In Italy, with regard to authors who release their works under a Creative Commons open license, it has been considered that they are not entitled to compensation for private copying, based on the assumption that the adoption of such licenses implies a waiver of the collection of this compensation, which is not defined by law as unwaivable.

III.2.3. Barriers stemming from the requirement for specific, separate transfers

The need for separate transfers of rights can act as a barrier to Open Science, as it adds complexity to rights management and creates administrative burdens for authors. This fragmentation requires researchers to negotiate multiple agreements, making the process of enabling Open Access and reuse of their works more time-consuming. As a result, these requirements may hinder the broader dissemination of scientific research.

III.2.3.1. Requirement for specific, separate transfers of the right to remuneration

⁶⁵ Available at: <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019L0790>>, last accessed in March 2025;

Use of protected content by online content sharing service providers

Art. 102sexies, par. 3, of LdA

(1) For the purposes of this Title, an online content sharing service provider is defined as an information society service provider that cumulatively meets the following criteria:

a) Its main purpose, or one of its main purposes, is to store and provide public access to large amounts of copyrighted works or other protected materials.

b) The copyrighted works or other protected materials are uploaded by its users.

c) The copyrighted works or other protected materials are organised and promoted with the intention of generating direct or indirect profit.

(2) The following are not considered online content sharing service providers under this Title:

- Non-profit online encyclopaedias
- Non-profit educational or scientific repositories
- Platforms for the development and sharing of open-source software
- Providers of electronic communication services
- Online marketplaces
- Business-to-business cloud services
- Cloud services allow users to upload content for personal use, unless the online marketplace or cloud service allows sharing of copyrighted works among multiple users.

(3) Online content sharing service providers, when giving public access to copyrighted works or other protected materials uploaded by their users, perform an act of communication to the public or an act of making available to the public. They must obtain authorization from rights holders, either directly or through the conclusion of a licensing agreement, which may also be obtained through collective management organizations and independent management entities as provided by Legislative Decree No. 35 of March 15, 2017.

(4) The authorization referred to in paragraph 3 includes acts performed by users who upload copyrighted works to the service provider's platform when they do not act for commercial purposes or when their activity does not generate significant revenue.

(5) The limitation of liability provided for in Article 16 of Legislative Decree No. 70 of April 9, 2003, does not apply to cases under this Title.

Liability for unauthorized acts of communication to the public and making available to the public copyrighted works

Art. 102septies of LdA

(1) Online content sharing service providers, in the absence of the authorization referred to in Article 102-sexies, are liable for unauthorized acts of communication to the public and making available to the public copyrighted works and other protected materials, unless they demonstrate that they have cumulatively satisfied the following conditions:

a) They have made best efforts to obtain authorization according to high standards of professional diligence in the sector.

b) They have, according to high standards of professional diligence in the sector, made best efforts to ensure that specific works and other materials for which they have received relevant and necessary information from rights holders are not made available.

c) After receiving a sufficiently substantiated notice from rights holders, they have promptly disabled access to or removed from their websites the works or other materials identified in the notice and, according to the level of diligence required in letter b), have made best efforts to prevent their future upload.

(2) To determine, according to the principle of proportionality, whether the online content sharing service provider is exempt from liability, consideration is given, with a case-by-case assessment, to the type, audience, and size of the service, the type of works or other materials uploaded by the service's users, as well as the availability of appropriate and effective tools and their cost for service providers. In any case, an online content sharing service provider that engages in or facilitates copyright piracy is not exempt from liability.

(3) Online content sharing service providers shall promptly provide rights holders, upon request, with complete and adequate information on the implementation of the provisions referred to in paragraph 1 and, when licensing agreements have been concluded between service providers and rights holders, information on the use of the content covered by the agreements.

(4) The application of the provisions of this Title does not entail a general obligation to monitor.

Art. 102-sexies LdA and the following articles have implemented the provisions of Article 17 of the DSM Directive.⁶⁶

⁶⁶ Directive (EU) 2019/790 on copyright in the Digital Single Market. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/LSU/?uri=oj:JOL_2019_130_R_0004>, last accessed in March 2025;

In the implementation of Article 17 of the DSM Directive, the Italian legislator, unlike the Slovenian one, adopted the regulation through a faithful translation of the text into Italian. There is no equivalent provision to paragraph 6 of Article 76 of ZASP in the LDA, which presumes that the author retains the right to remuneration when transferring the rights of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service (Article 163c of ZASP), unless explicitly agreed otherwise in a contract.

According to Art. 102 sexies (3) of the LdA, online content sharing services providers, when granting public access to copyrighted works or other protected materials uploaded by their users, perform an act of communication to the public or an act of making available to the public. For these acts, they must obtain authorisation from the rights holders, either directly or through a licensing agreement, concluded with collective management organizations or independent management entities.

Pursuant to Art. 102-septies of the LdA, in the absence of a license, online content sharing service providers are liable for unauthorised acts of communicating to the public and making available to the public copyrighted works and other materials, unless they can demonstrate that they have cumulatively met the conditions established by Art. 17 of the DSM Directive. Therefore, the same limitation found in Slovenian legislation is not present in Italian law.

III.2.3.2. Requirement for specific, separate transfers of rights for the use of copyright works

**Reproduction right
Art. 13 of LdA**

The exclusive right to reproduce has as its object the multiplication into direct or indirect, temporary or permanent copies, in whole or in part of the work, in any manner or form, such as hand copying, printing, lithography, engraving, photography, phonography, cinematography and any other reproduction process.

**Distribution right
Art. 17 of LdA**

(1) The exclusive right of distribution shall have as its object the placing on the market or in circulation, or otherwise at the disposal of the public, by any means and for any reason, of the original of the work or specimens thereof, and shall also include the exclusive right to introduce into the territory of the States of the European Community, for the purpose of distribution, reproductions made in non-Community States.

(2) The right of distribution of the original or copies of the work shall not be exhausted in the European Community, except when the first sale or the first act of transfer of ownership in the Community is made by the right holder or with his consent.

(3) The provisions of Paragraph 2 shall not apply to the making available to the public of works in such a way that each person can have access to them from the place and at the time individually chosen, even in cases where the making of copies of the work is permitted.

(4) For the purposes of the exhaustion referred to in Subsection 2, the free delivery of copies of the works, made or permitted by the owner for promotional purposes, or for teaching or scientific research, shall not constitute the exercise of the exclusive right of distribution.

There are no similar provisions in the LdA as stated in the Slovenian ZASP.

In Italian Copyright Law, the exclusive right of reproduction represents the basis for the economic exploitation of creative works. In its current formulation (adopted by Legislative Decree 68/2003,⁶⁷ which implemented the Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society, hereinafter referred to as InfoSoc Directive),⁶⁸ it applies to all forms of direct or indirect, temporary or permanent reproduction, in any manner or form, in whole or in part. The right of reproduction thus encompasses all types of works and extends to all ways in which a work can be reproduced, whether physically or digitally, when it circulates online. Therefore, all acts of reproduction of works, both offline and online, are covered by this protection.

As for the right of distribution, established in Article 17 of LdA, this was also partially amended by Legislative Decree 68/2003, implementing the InfoSoc Directive. However, upon closer examination, the Italian legislator has broadly maintained the definition previously provided by the former Article 17 (1) of LdA, which offered a broader definition than that adopted by the EU legislator. The latter, in fact, focusing on any form of public distribution of the original works or their copies, refers exclusively to fixed copies distributed on a tangible medium.

In contrast, the exclusive right of distribution, as defined by the new wording of Article 17 of LdA, concerns the commercialisation, circulation, or making available to the public, by any means and under any title, of the original work or its copies. It also includes the exclusive right to introduce reproductions made in non-EU countries into the territory of the European Community (now European Union (EU)) for distribution purposes.

In compliance with the principle of EU-wide exhaustion, paragraph 2 of the aforementioned article establishes that, concerning the original and only tangible copies of the work, the right of distribution is not exhausted within the European Community (now European Union (EU)) unless the first sale or the first act of transfer of ownership within the Community is carried out by the rightholder or with their consent. Paragraph 3 explicitly clarifies that the provisions of paragraph 2 do not apply to making the work available to the public on-demand, even when the creation of copies of the work is permitted.

Paragraph 4 reinforces a principle already present in paragraph 2 of the earlier version of Article 17 of the LdA: that the free delivery of copies of works – when made or authorized by the right holder for promotional, educational, or scientific research purposes – does not constitute an exercise of the right of distribution. This principle aligns closely with the core values of Open Science, which advocates for the free and open dissemination of scientific knowledge. By clarifying that such non-commercial sharing does not constitute exercise of the distribution right. The law supports practices like Open Access publishing, educational resource sharing, and collaborative research – all central to the Open Science movement. It underscores a legal recognition of the importance of removing access barriers in order to advance scientific progress and democratize knowledge.

⁶⁷ Legislative Decree of April 9, 2003, No. 68, Implementation of Directive 2001/29/EC on the harmonization of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society. Available at: <<https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2003;068>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁶⁸ Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society. Available at: <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2001/29/oj/eng>>, last accessed in March 2025;

III.2.4. Barriers stemming from the requirement for special consent of the author for subsequent transfers

**Assignment of the contract
Art. 1406 of the Italian Civil Code**

Each party may substitute a third party for itself in the relations arising from a contract with reciprocal obligations, provided that these obligations have not yet been performed, and provided that the other party consents.

No equivalent specific provision to that in Slovenian law is found in Italian Copyright Law, but the same principle is stated in the general contract law in the Italian Civil Code. While Italian Copyright Law does not contain a provision equivalent to that found in Slovenian law, the principles of general contract law – particularly Article 1406 of the Civil Code – can support the contractual transfer of rights necessary for Open Science practices. In this framework, contract law does not, in itself, represent a structural barrier to Open Science. Rather, it offers a degree of flexibility that can be leveraged to facilitate the sharing and reuse of scientific outputs, especially when rights are managed proactively from the outset. Nonetheless, potential obstacles may arise in cases where the agreement is founded on *intuitu personae* considerations, which emphasize the personal identity or trustworthiness of the contracting party. In such instances, limitations on the transfer of obligations or rights may inadvertently hinder the seamless dissemination and secondary use of research, suggesting a need for clearer contractual strategies or policy support to align with Open Science objectives.

III.2.5. Barriers stemming from the requirement of formality

**Written proof for transferring of rights
Art. 110 of LdA**

The transfer of exploitation rights must be proven in writing.

Just like Article 80 of ZASP, Article 110 of LdA requires that, in the case of the transfer of economic exploitation rights, the contract must be in written form. This principle applies only to acts *inter vivos* and not to acts *mortis causa*.

In Italian law, a contract subject to a written form *ad probationem* is not invalid if made orally or informally; rather, the written form is required solely for evidentiary purposes. This means that the lack of written form does not affect the legal validity or enforceability of the contract itself, but it may limit the admissibility of evidence in court to prove the contract's existence or its terms. In particular, if a dispute arises, the absence of a written document may restrict the parties' ability to use certain means of proof – such as witness testimony – unless specific exceptions apply. Therefore, the requirement of form *ad probationem* impacts procedural aspects related to the burden and admissibility of proof, not the substantive validity of the agreement.

However, the written form *ad probationem* does not preclude other types of evidence, whether oral, such as confession and oath, or documentary evidence.

The only exception is set forth in Art. 109 (2) of LdA where it is held that the transfer of a means suitable for reproducing a work of art (mould, engraved copper plate) also includes the right to reproduce the work itself, provided that such right belongs to the transferor. This provision refers specifically to the transfer of a physical object that is suitable for reproducing a work of art. This rule is narrowly tailored to the domain of visual art and the transfer of tangible reproduction tools. It is therefore not applicable to scientific works or digital outputs typically disseminated under Open Science practices, where the reproduction and sharing of content involve different legal and technological frameworks.

In conclusion, the same rule established by Article 80 of ZASP, is found in the Art. 110 of LdA which requires that all transfers of economic rights or other author's rights, as well as all authorizations, must be made in writing.

In conclusion, the same rule established by Article 80 of the Slovenian Copyright Act (ZASP) is mirrored in Article 110 of LdA, which requires that all transfers of economic rights and authorizations be made in writing. While this formal requirement is intended to ensure legal certainty and clarity in the management of rights, it also implies a considerable administrative burden.

In practice, the obligation to formalize every transfer or authorization in writing can place an obstacle on researchers, who are unlikely to prioritise or have the capacity to navigate complex legal formalities. Likewise, academic institutions and libraries may lack the resources to support the necessary documentation processes on a large scale.

III.2.6. Barriers stemming from the presumption of the publisher's priority right

The principle of independence of the economic rights
Art. 19 of LdA

The exclusive rights provided for in the preceding articles are independent of one another. The exercise of one of these rights does not exclude the exclusive exercise of each of the other rights.

Publishing contract for print
ART. 118 of LdA

The contract through which the author grants a publisher the right to exercise the publication right in print, on behalf and at the expense of the publisher, is governed not only by the provisions contained in the civil codes but also by the general provisions of this chapter and the specific provisions that follow.

There is no provision in the LdA equivalent to Article 78 of ZASP.

In Italian Copyright Law, the general principle of the independence of economic exploitation rights applies (Article 19 of LdA). This rule is particularly relevant in publishing contracts for print, where publishers typically request options and rights of first refusal.

According to Article 118 of LdA, a publishing contract for a work in book form, through which the author grants the publisher the right to publish the work in print at the publisher's expense and on the publisher's behalf, is governed not only by the provisions of the Civil Code but also by the general and specific provisions of LdA. Unless otherwise agreed, it is presumed that the exclusive rights have been transferred to the publisher.

Unless expressly agreed otherwise, the transfer does not extend to the rights of exploitation arising from any adaptations or transformations to which the work may be subject, including adaptations for cinema, broadcasting, and mechanical recording.

Unless otherwise specified, the transfer of one or more exploitation rights does not imply the transfer of other rights that are not necessarily dependent on the transferred rights, even if they belong to the same category under the provisions of Title I of the LdA.

III.3. Provisions in Italian Copyright Law that can be both barriers and enablers of Open Science

While certain provisions of copyright law may create obstacles to Open Science, some legal mechanisms can function both as barriers and enablers, depending on their application. These provisions might initially appear to limit authors' ability to manage their rights under open or free licenses. However, in specific contexts, they can also facilitate broader dissemination of research outputs. Whether such provisions hinder or support Open Science often depends on how they are interpreted and enforced by rights holders such as publishers, employers, or collective management organisations.

III.3.1. Barriers that might also act as enablers stemming from the presumption of transfer of economic rights from employees to employers

Transfer of economic right to State, Provinces, Municipalities or other private entities

Art. 11 of LdA

(1) The right of authorship on works created and published in their name and at their expense belongs to the State administrations, Provinces, and Municipalities.

(2) The same right is granted to private entities that do not pursue profit-making objectives, unless otherwise agreed with the authors of the published works, as well as to academies and other public cultural institutions regarding the collection of their proceedings and their publications.

Transfer of economic rights on computer program and database in case of employment relationship

Article 12-bis of LdA

Unless otherwise agreed, the employer holds the exclusive economic exploitation rights of the computer program or database created by the employee in the course of their duties or according to instructions given by the employer.

Transfer of economic rights on industrial design in case of employment relationship

Article 12-ter of LdA

Unless otherwise agreed, if an industrial design is created by the employee in the course of their duties, the employer holds the exclusive economic exploitation rights of the work.

Transfer of economic rights on simple photography protected by related right in case of employment relationship

Art. 88, par.1, 2, 3, of LdA

(1) *The photographer has the exclusive right to reproduce, distribute, and sell the photograph, subject to the provisions established by Section Two of Chapter Six of this Title, with regard to portraits, and without prejudice to the author's rights on the reproduced work concerning photographs that depict works of visual art.*

(2) *However, if the work was created during the course of, and in fulfilment of, an employment contract, within the scope and purpose of the contract, the exclusive right belongs to the employer.*

(3) *The same rule applies, unless otherwise agreed in favour of the client, when the photograph concerns objects owned by the client, and provided that the photographer is paid by those who commercially exploit the reproduction, an equitable remuneration.*

Although LdA specifically refers to these three categories of intellectual works (computer programs, databases, and industrial designs), both legal doctrine and case law agree that the principle whereby the economic exploitation rights of works created by an employee belong to the employer extends to all types of intellectual works. This includes, for example, photographs, musical scores, literary works, architectural designs, and so on, provided they are created within the scope of an employment relationship.

Italian Copyright Law says nothing about the fate of the economic rights of works created by a freelancer under a commission contract. To fill this gap in the legislation, several theories have emerged. A first theory suggests that, in the case of a commissioned work, only the economic rights related to the object and purposes of the contract are transferred to the client. According to this theory, if the client wishes to use the work in a way that goes beyond the agreed terms, they must (i) seek permission from the artist and (ii) pay them additional compensation.

A second theory, on the other hand, holds that, based on the agreement between the client and the artist, all economic rights to the work are automatically transferred to the client, who may use the work as they wish, beyond the use specified in the contract.

Law May 22, 2017, N. 81 on "*Measures for the protection of non-entrepreneurial self-employment and measures to promote flexible arrangements in the timing and location of subordinate work*",⁶⁹ at Art. 4 establishes that the economic rights to works created by a freelancer under a contract for the provision of services belong to the freelancer, unless the work is specifically provided for as the subject of the contract and compensated for that purpose.

Case law, in the case of a commissioned work, has repeatedly established that all economic rights to the work are automatically acquired by the client as a result of the creation of the work itself.

⁶⁹ Law, May 22, 2017, No. 81, Measures for the protection of non-entrepreneurial self-employment and measures to promote flexible arrangements in the timing and location of subordinate work. Available at: <<https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2017;81>>, last accessed in March 2025;

The provisions of the LDA above mentioned, like Article 101 and Article 102 of ZASP, can either create barriers or provide enablers for managing rights through open licenses, depending primarily on the employer's stance. The rules governing ownership of economic rights in the context of employment and commissioned works are particularly significant for Open Science, as they directly affect who has the authority to license a work openly and under what conditions.

Thus, the ability to apply open licenses in both employment and freelance contexts depends less on the law itself and more on contractual clarity and the stance of the rights holder – typically the employer or commissioning party. Without explicit contractual language allowing Open Access and reuse, these legal defaults can hinder the adoption of Open Science practices, creating friction where openness should ideally be seamless.

III.4. Enablers in the Italian copyright law

The exception for text and data mining for scientific research facilitates Open Access and the reuse of copyright-protected materials, helping to reduce legal barriers to data-driven research and support broader access to and dissemination of scientific knowledge. No other enabling factors were identified.

III.4.1. Enabler stemming from the exception for text and data mining for scientific research

Text and data mining for scientific research purposes
Article 70-ter of LdA

(1) Reproductions made by research organisations and by cultural heritage protection institutions are permitted for the purposes of scientific research, for the purpose of text and data mining from works or other materials available in networks or databases to which they have lawful access, as well as the communication to the public of the results of the research, where expressed in new original works.

(2) For this law, text and data mining refers to any automated technique for analysing large quantities of texts, sounds, images, data, or metadata in digital format to generate information, including patterns, trends, and correlations.

(3) For this law, institutions for the protection of cultural heritage include libraries, museums, and archives, provided they are open or accessible to the public, including those affiliated with educational institutions, research organisations, and public broadcasting entities, as well as institutions for the preservation of cinematographic and sound heritage and public broadcasting organisations.

(4) For this law, research organisations are defined as universities, including their libraries, research institutes, or any other entity whose primary objective is to carry out scientific research activities or to conduct educational activities that include scientific research, which alternatively:

a) operate on a non-profit basis or whose statutes provide for the reinvestment of profits into scientific research activities, including in the form of public-private partnerships;

b) pursue a public interest objective recognised by a European Union member state.

(5) Entities over which commercial enterprises exercise a decisive influence, such that they may gain preferential access to the results generated by scientific research activities, shall not be considered research organisations.

(6) Copies of works or other materials made in accordance with paragraph 1 must be stored with an adequate level of security and may be preserved and used solely for scientific research purposes, including the verification of research results.

(7) Rights holders are authorised to apply appropriate measures to ensure the security and integrity of the networks and databases hosting the works or other materials, to the extent strictly necessary for the purpose.

(8) The measures referred to in paragraphs 6 and 7 may also be defined based on agreements between associations of rights holders, institutions for the protection of cultural heritage, and research organisations.

(9) Any contractual provisions in conflict with paragraphs 1, 6, and 7 of this article shall be null and void.

Common provisions (the Italian Implementation of the Three Step Test)

Article 71-nonies of LdA

(1) The exceptions and limitations provided for in this chapter and any other provision of this law, when applied to works or other protected materials made available to the public in such a way that anyone may access them from a place and at a time individually chosen, must not conflict with the normal exploitation of the works or other materials, nor cause unjustified prejudice to the legitimate interests of the rights holders.

The exception for text and data mining (TDM) for scientific research, provided for in Article 3 of the DSM Directive, grants researchers the freedom to analyse text and data in digital format without needing to obtain authorisation, even if the works and/or materials involved are protected by copyright or related rights. This exception has been transposed into Italian law through Article 70-ter of the Copyright Law (LdA). The provision allows research institutions and cultural heritage institutions to make reproductions for scientific research purposes, to extract works or other materials available online or in databases to which they have lawful access. It also permits them to communicate the results of the research to the public, provided that such results are expressed in new, original works.

It should be noted that the Italian legislator appears to have made a lexical error when transposing Article 3 of the DSM Directive, referring to the permitted use under the TDM exception for scientific research purposes as “reproduction for the purpose of extraction”, instead of “reproduction and extraction”, as established by the European legislator and consistently reflected in the transposition of Article 4 concerning the TDM exception for other uses. This wording—along with the additional restriction limiting the scope of the exception to works and materials available in networks or databases—appears to result in a legislative formulation that is not fully compatible with the Directive.

On the other hand, the Italian legislator (like the Slovenian one) is to be commended for exercising the option granted by Article 25 of the DSM Directive to include, within the exception, the communication to the public of research results when such results are expressed in a new, original work. In this regard, a broader provision has been adopted, consistent with the exceptions and limitations provided by the InfoSoc and Database Directives. In other words, it is lawful to communicate protected materials resulting from computational research processes, provided that these results are incorporated into an original publication, a dataset, or another original work.

This exception has a clear enabling effect on Open Science, as it removes legal and procedural barriers that might otherwise hinder large-scale text and data analysis. By allowing researchers to reuse protected content without prior authorisation – within a lawful and clearly defined framework – it facilitates access to knowledge, promotes transparency and reproducibility in research, and supports the creation of new scientific outputs that can be openly shared with the broader community. The legislative choice to allow the communication to the public of research results (including of course Open Access) significantly enhances the potential for Open Science. By permitting not only the reproduction and analysis of protected content for scientific research purposes, but also the dissemination of research outcomes when expressed in new, original works, the Italian implementation

creates a legal framework in which openness is not merely tolerated but actively encouraged. This empowers researchers to share the results of computational analysis without the risk of copyright infringement, provided those results are incorporated into original scientific or creative outputs. Such a framework fosters key pillars of the Open Science movement – transparency, reproducibility, and wide accessibility of knowledge – and promotes innovative research practices grounded in large-scale data processing, interdisciplinary collaboration, and institutional cooperation.

The “three-step test” principle was incorporated by the Italian legislator during the implementation of the InfoSoc Directive. The relevant provision closes the section dedicated to exceptions and limitations and applies only to those concerning the use of protected materials made available through on-demand services (i.e., made available to the public in such a way that each individual may access them from a place and at a time of their choosing). This is in contrast to Article 7(2) of the DSM Directive, which instead extends the applicability of Article 5(5) of the Directive 2001/29/EC to the exceptions and limitations set out in its Title II. In conclusion, the placement of the provision and its literal wording have a minor impact on Open Science, unlike the more significant effects observed under Slovenian legislation.

III.5. Barriers outside of copyright law in Italy

The Italian Cultural Heritage Code (Legislative Decree No. 42 of January 22, 2004)⁷⁰ creates barriers outside of copyright law to the implementation of Open Science principles (i.e., Open Access to and reuse of works). The Code stipulates that reproductions of cultural heritage can only be used for commercial purposes after receiving authorisation from the cultural heritage institution holding the physical work, and after payment of a fee. This creates issues with releasing contents under Creative Commons recommended models of open licenses which are compatible with Open Access (CC-BY and CC-BY-SA), as both licenses allow reuse for any purpose, including commercial use. This condition limits the reuse of such contents on Wikimedia platforms.

In particular, Art. 108 of the Italian Cultural Heritage Code states that fees and charges related to the reproduction of cultural heritage are determined by the authority responsible for the cultural heritage itself, taking into account: a) the nature of the activities to which the usage concessions refer; b) the means and methods used to execute the reproductions; c) the type and duration of the use of spaces and cultural heritage; d) the use and purpose of the reproductions, as well as the economic benefits derived by the applicant. Fees and charges are generally paid in advance, and no fee is required for reproductions requested or carried out by private individuals for personal use or for study purposes, or by public or private entities for enhancement purposes, provided they are conducted on a non-profit basis. However, applicants are required to reimburse the expenses incurred by the granting administration.

⁷⁰ Available at: <<https://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2004-01-22;42>>, last accessed in March 2025;

Furthermore, Art. 108 identifies some activities that can be carried out free of charge, if without profit and for purposes of study, research, free expression of thought or creative expression, or to promote knowledge of cultural heritage. Those activities are: 1) the reproduction of cultural heritage, other than archival goods subject to accessibility restrictions under the Cultural Heritage Code, if provided in compliance with copyright laws and if it does not involve physical contact with the cultural heritage, exposure to light sources, or the use of stands or tripods inside the cultural institutions; and 2) the dissemination by any means of cultural heritage images, lawfully acquired, in such a way that they cannot be further reproduced for profit.

Finally, Article 108 specifies some additional aspects. In cases where the use could cause harm to cultural heritage, the authority responsible determines the amount of the security deposit, which may also be provided through a bank or insurance guarantee. For the same reasons, the security deposit is required even in cases of exemption from payment of fees and charges, and it is refunded when it is confirmed that the cultural heritage under concession have not been damaged, and the incurred expenses have been reimbursed. The minimum amounts of fees and charges for the use and reproduction of the assets are established by a provision of the granting administration.

However, Italian regulations governing reproductions of cultural heritage are not limited to the Cultural Heritage Code. In this sense, the Italian Ministry of Culture issued a Decree titled “*Guidelines for the determination of the minimum fees for the concession of use of cultural heritage held by national institutes and places of culture*” (D.M. April 11, 2023, no. 161).⁷¹ This Decree harms the promotion and dissemination of Italian cultural heritage, and restricts the constitutional freedoms of research and expression, limiting the rights to “benefit from cultural heritage and contribute to its enrichment” (Faro Convention, Article 4).⁷² The Decree raised concerns among numerous organisations and professionals in the cultural heritage sector because it introduces minimum fees for creating and using digital reproductions of state-owned cultural heritage for profit, including works in the Public Domain.

In opposition to this kind of restrictive approach, the Italian Court of Auditors has expressed a preference for a more open approach. The Court of Auditors, Central Section for the Control of State Administration Management, has conducted an audit on “IT Expenditures, with particular regard to the digitisation of Italian cultural heritage (2016–2020)” the results of which are outlined in the resolution n. 50/2022/G.⁷³

In the extensive report accompanying the resolution, the strategic importance of digitisation processes is highlighted, with Italy facing unacceptable delays despite considerable investments already made. In light of future EU investments within the Recovery Fund, where 20% of the total is allocated to digitisation, the strategic place of digitisation of national cultural heritage is emphasised. Italian cultural institutions are in a phase of continuous

⁷¹ Available at: <<https://www.beniculturali.it/comunicato/dm-161-11042023>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷² Available at: <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list?module=treaty-detail&treatynum=199>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷³ Available at: <<https://www.corteconti.it/HOME/Documenti/DettaglioDocumenti?id=2565b05e-1426-4258-9965-54c764788b2d>>, last accessed in March 2025;

evolution, responding – especially due to the acceleration prompted by the pandemic – to the need to open up to the public, including in the digital environment.

The Court of Auditors acknowledges that: “The need for transformation presents a challenge but also an opportunity to engage new types of users and to enhance the tangible and intangible assets that institutions preserve and produce”. From the analysis of the relevant regulations outlined therein, the Court confirmed that the power to decide on the reuse of data belongs to the entity that owns the data itself. However, it is noted that this does not allow the public administration to adopt behaviours that impose exclusive constraints limiting access to information. The Court goes on to emphasise that “the administration is always required to make its information assets of data and digital documents available with open licenses that allow reuse (including commercial use) and the greatest possible elaboration”.

Discussions with the relevant administrations also highlighted the need to adapt traditional proprietary paradigms in favour of a vision of cultural heritage more aligned with the principles of democracy, inclusivity, and horizontality. It is noted that, globally, most cultural institutions have embraced Open Access policies for sharing digital reproductions of cultural heritage images, whereas the approach of the Italian cultural administration remains resistant to the paradigm shift prompted by technological evolution.⁷⁴ The goal to be pursued, even with the Cultural Heritage Digitisation Plan, should be to foster the cultural growth of society and create long-term value.

Later, the Italian Court of Auditors returned to the issue, publishing its 2022 findings on the digitisation of Italy’s cultural heritage through Deliberation No. 76/2023/G.⁷⁵ These were issued on 20 October 2023. The report emphasises the importance of Open Access policies in enhancing and sharing images of Italy’s Public Domain cultural heritage. However, the Court raised concerns about the above-mentioned Ministerial Decree 161 of 11 April 2023, which introduces fees for using state-owned cultural heritage. This approach, according to the Court, contradicts its previous recommendations and undermines study, research, and the broader dissemination of knowledge.

The Court of Auditors highlights that Open Access has proven to be a “powerful wealth multiplier,” benefiting cultural institutions, boosting Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and serving as a strategic asset for the social, cultural, and economic growth of EU Member States. The introduction of the fee structure fails to recognise the digital economy's dynamics and conflicts with the National Plan for the Digitisation of Cultural Heritage (PND). Furthermore, the decree’s strategy appears short-sighted, limiting the scientific and cultural potential of digitisation and its role in promoting tourism.

The Court’s stance raises critical questions about the Ministry of Culture’s persistence in implementing policies that restrict Open Access, despite the success of international institutions adopting open sharing practices. As mentioned before, many cultural

⁷⁴ De Angelis, Deborah. La Corte dei conti sulla digitalizzazione del patrimonio culturale italiano sostiene l’Open Access. Available at: <<https://medium.com/@avvdda/la-corte-dei-conti-sulla-digitalizzazione-del-patrimonio-culturale-italiano-sostiene-lopen-access-c3cfb55d2141>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷⁵ Available at: <<https://www.corteconti.it/HOME/Documenti/DettaglioDocumenti?id=250a9d21-c914-43f9-8165-3c60a197b824>>, last accessed in March 2025;

professionals and organisations have already voiced their concerns over the negative impact of the decree. The hope is that the Ministry of Culture will reconsider its position, aligning with the Court of Auditors' recommendations and the broader cultural community's calls for Open Access. By fostering a more open and collaborative approach, the Ministry of Culture could significantly contribute to Italy's cultural, educational, and economic development, positioning the country as a leader in the global movement for free and accessible cultural heritage.⁷⁶

In response to these concerns from the Court of Auditors and civil society in general, the Ministry of Culture issued a new Ministerial Decree n. 108 of 21 March 2024,⁷⁷ amending the previous one. This new Decree addresses some of the issues raised by various cultural heritage organisations and other associations, such as the Italian CC Chapter,⁷⁸ MAB and others,⁷⁹ AISA,⁸⁰ FCdA (the Federation of University Archaeology Councils) for the free movement of public cultural heritage images,⁸¹ Federation of University Archaeology Councils, CUNSTA (National University Council for Art History) and SISCA (Italian Society for the History of Art Criticism).⁸² Importantly, the new decree limits the scope of mandatory fees to "goods in consignment to the institutes and places of culture of the Ministry of Culture". Cultural heritage held by cultural institutions from other ministries will no longer be subject to these provisions. The Decree also stipulates that the determination of the concession fee will remain "in the hands of the authority responsible for the cultural heritage, which must assess, on a case-by-case basis, the intended use of the work, considering factors like cultural promotion, preservation risks, and the impact on public access". Finally, the new Decree acknowledges regional differences and opportunities to promote lesser-known cultural heritage. Based on these factors, the director of the institution holding the cultural heritage may choose to reduce or waive the fee.

Despite this, the Decree poses several challenges to the effective implementation of Open Access policies and introduces ambiguities that could negatively impact cultural heritage institutions and users' rights. Furthermore, the Decree does not sufficiently address scenarios where the commercial purpose is only indirect, despite the use falling within the exceptions provided in Article 108 of the Italian Cultural Heritage Code, such as personal use, study, research, free expression, enhancement, and creative expression.

⁷⁶ De Angelis, Deborah. The Italian Court of Auditors renews its support for Open Access. Available at: <<https://medium.com/@avvdda/the-italian-court-of-auditors-renews-its-support-for-open-access-dd5f80553e28>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷⁷ Available at:

<<https://media.beniculturali.it/mibac/files/boards/be78e33bc8ca0c99bff70aa174035096/DECRETI/ANNO%202024/DM%2021%20marzo%202024%20rep.%20108-signed.pdf>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷⁸ Available at:

<<https://creativecommons.it/chapterIT/index.php/1529/?fbclid=IwAR3roAf1xsBJT4SAJbE4wVeltAnWk0Za16Nd73ziBxvLCj8CjKFotTT4JRM>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁷⁹ Available in Italian here: <<https://www.aib.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Osservazioni-sul-DM-11-aprile-2023-n.-161.pdf>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸⁰ Available In Italian here: <<https://aisa.sp.unipi.it/immagini-dei-beni-culturali-e-uso-a-scopo-scientifico-lettera-aperta-al-ministro-della-cultura/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸¹ Available in Italian here: <<https://www.change.org/p/per-la-libera-circolazione-delle-immagini-del-patrimonio-culturale-pubblico>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸² Available in Italian here: <<https://www.archaeoreporter.com/2023/04/27/pagamento-per-immagini-dei-beni-culturali-il-disappunto-delle-consulte-universitarie-appello-al-ministro-sangiuliano/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

III.6. Enablers outside of copyright law in Italy

Regarding enablers to Open Science, even if there are no specific Italian regulations that encourage it expressly, the above mentioned, Articles 4, par. 2 and 2bis, of the Decree-Law of August 8, 2013, No. 91 are relevant, as amended by the Law of October 7, 2013, No. 112 (published in the Official Gazette on October 8, 2013, No. 236).

The Articles provide for urgent provisions to promote the development of libraries and archives and to encourage recitation and reading. It states that public entities responsible for the provision or management of scientific research funding shall, within their autonomy, adopt the necessary measures to promote Open Access to research results which are at least 50% funded by public funds, when these results come in the form of articles published in scientific journals with at least two issues per year. Such articles must include a project summary listing all contributors involved in their creation. Furthermore, Art. 4 provides that Open Access is achieved through: a) publication by the publisher, at the time of first release, ensuring the article is freely accessible from the location and at the time individually chosen; b) non-commercial republication in institutional or disciplinary electronic archives under the same conditions, within eighteen months of the first publication for works in the scientific, technical, and medical fields, and within twenty-four months for works in the humanities and social sciences.

Finally, under par. 2bis, the provisions of paragraph 2 of the above-mentioned Article do not apply when the rights to the results of research, development, and innovation activities are protected under the Code pursuant to Legislative Decree No. 30 of 10 February 2005 (Industrial Property Code). Article 4 of Decree-Law No. 91/2013 provided an initial general response to the objectives set out by the European Commission in the Recommendation of 17 July 2012, on access to and preservation of scientific information (2012/417/EU).⁸³ In this recommendation, Member States and, through them, the bodies responsible for providing and managing public research funding were urged to establish “institutional policies for the dissemination of scientific publications and Open Access to them.” The regulation in question aims to govern transparency and the dissemination of knowledge, but its implementation is challenging due to the lack of an effective sanctioning regime. It stipulates that public research institutions must adopt measures to promote Open Access to the results of research funded at least 50% by public funds. However, this provision does not explicitly guarantee researchers the right to make their work freely available, regardless of other contractual obligations assumed with publishers.⁸⁴

⁸³ 2012/417/EU: Commission Recommendation of 17 July 2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information. Available at: <<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/48558fc9-d4c8-11e1-905c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸⁴ G. Peruginelli, S. Faro, L'indagine del progetto Right2Pub su rights retention e secondary publishing right e le prospettive di riforma del diritto d'autore in ambito scientifico, in *Conservazione dei diritti dell'autore e diritto di pubblicazione secondaria in ambito scientifico. Contesto, attualità e prospettive*, a cura di S. Faro, G. Peruginelli, D. De Angelis, Edizioni CNR, 2024, page 16 e ss., available in OA on Zenodo: Doi: <<https://doi.org/10.32091/VolRight2Pub2024>>, last accessed in March 2025.

IV. REPORT ON BARRIERS AND ENABLERS FOR OPEN SCIENCE IN THE CROATIAN COPYRIGHT LAW

IV.1 The structural, political, and legal framework for Open Science in Croatia

Croatia has gradually embraced Open Science principles at the strategic level, though a dedicated national Open Science policy is still emerging. The National Development Strategy of Croatia 2030 (adopted in 2021) explicitly includes goals to “strengthen scientific excellence, encourage Open Science and better connect the academic, research and business sectors” in line with EU priorities.

In 2012, Croatian research institutions and scientists signed the Croatian Open Access Declaration, affirming that results of publicly funded research should be openly available⁸⁵. This was reinforced by the Croatian Rectors’ Conference in 2015, which issued a statement supporting Open Access to publications and data and recommending an OA mandate in Croatia.

However, as of 2024 the Ministry of Science and Education had not yet adopted a unified national Open Access or Open Science policy. Instead, openness is referenced in various laws and other strategic documents and driven by stakeholder initiatives.

Notably, in late 2021 the University of Zagreb’s Computing Centre (SRCE) launched the Croatian Open Science Cloud Initiative (HR-OOZ) in collaboration with the Ministry, the Croatian Science Foundation, all public universities, and other key institutions. This bottom-up initiative produced a draft Croatian Open Science Plan in early 2023, which was submitted to the Ministry of Science and Education for adoption.⁸⁶ The proposed plan advocates Open Access to all publicly funded research outputs (publications and datasets) and promotes research data management in line with FAIR principles).⁸⁷

Croatia’s legal framework has started to incorporate Open Science concepts, but binding mandates remain limited in scope. A key milestone was the new Act on Higher Education and Scientific Activity (Cro. *Zakon o visokom obrazovanju i znanstvenoj djelatnosti*),⁸⁸ which came into force in 2022.⁸⁹ This law explicitly names Open Science and public access to research results as foundational principles of scientific activity. It requires all universities to deposit

⁸⁵ Available at: <<https://www.openaire.eu/national-policy-croatia>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸⁶ Available at: <<https://www.srce.unizg.hr/hr-zoo/en/croatian-open-science-cloud-initiative-hr-ooz-has-been-launched>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸⁷ Available at: <<https://stip.oecd.org/stip/interactive-dashboards/policy-initiatives/2023%2Fdata%2FpolicyInitiatives%2F99996851>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁸⁸ Official Gazette of the Republic of Croatia 119/2022;

⁸⁹ Article 2.4.2. of the Act on Higher Education and Scientific Activity;

digital versions of theses (undergraduate, master's, and doctoral) in an institutional or national repository within 30 days of their defence. However, the law stops short of mandating Open Access publication of those theses or other research publications, focusing only on archiving.

IV.2. Barriers and enablers for Open Science in the Croatian Copyright Law

The Croatian Copyright and Related Rights Act (Cro. *Zakon o autorskom pravu i srodnim pravima*)⁹⁰ includes provisions that may create challenges for the adoption of Open Science practices. A thorough assessment of Croatia's copyright framework is essential to identify provisions that function either as barriers or enablers for Open Science. The interpretation and application of specific provisions can affect researchers' ability to share and reuse scientific outputs openly.

The comparative analysis of Slovenian and Croatian copyright laws highlights both commonalities and differences in how these legal frameworks impact Open Science practices.

IV.2.1. Barriers stemming from the requirement for consensual management of copyright

A significant obstacle for Open Science is that all the people who own rights to a work have to agree to it being used, a requirement known as "consensual management of copyright".

This is an issue for works that were written by more than one person or so-called compound works. Co-authored works are those that were written by more than one author working together on the same project. Videos with many people working together are a good example of a work that was written by more than one person.

Articles 21 and 22 of the Croatian Copyright and Related Rights Act (Cro. *Zakon o autorskom pravu i srodnim pravima*; hereinafter: CCRRA)⁹¹ regulate compound works and co-authorship in the fields of literature, science, and art.

IV.2.1.1. Requirement of consensual management for co-authors

Co-authorship occurs when a work is produced collaboratively by multiple authors, necessitating the regulation of co-authors' rights and their relations with third parties. Given that a co-authored work represents an inseparable whole, it is essential to define clearly exactly what rights each person engaged may have.

⁹⁰ Official Gazette of the Republic of Croatia, 111/21, in application since 22nd of October, 2021;

⁹¹ Ibid.;

Co-authors

Article 21 of the CCRRA

- (1) Co-authors of a work shall be the persons who created the work jointly, and whose contributions cannot be used independently.*
- (2) Co-authors shall have a joint copyright in the created work, so a part of such copyright calculated in proportion to the whole copyright (hereinafter: co-authors' shares) shall belong to each of them.*
- (3) When in doubt as to the co-authors' shares, they shall be considered to be equal.*
- (4) The consent of all the co-authors shall be needed for the disclosure, use and alteration of their work. An individual co-author shall not refuse to give his consent for the reason, which is contrary to the principle of conscientiousness and fairness, nor shall undertake any action, which unjustifiably prejudices or could be prejudicial to the legitimate interests of other co-authors. If the consent of all the authors concerning disclosure, use or alteration of their work has not been achieved, the decision to that effect shall be made by the court, at a request of any of the co-author.*
- (5) A share of each co-author in the benefits deriving from the use of the work corresponds to his co-author's part, unless otherwise provided for by a contract regulating their mutual relations or rules of a relevant collective management organisation.*

Article 21 of the CCRRA stipulates that the consent of all co-authors is required for the disclosure, use, and modification of works. A co-author shall not withhold consent for reasons that contradict the principles of integrity and equity, nor shall they engage in any actions that unjustifiably harm or could harm the legitimate interests of other co-authors. If unanimous consent from all authors regarding the disclosure, use, or modification of work has not been obtained, the court shall decide upon the request of any co-author.

Within this provision, paragraph (4) of Article 21 of the CCRRA basically represents a barrier for Open Science objectives. When a single co-author raises an objection to making the work openly accessible, this objection prevents the work from being published on Open Access platforms or repositories. This is the case even if all of the other co-authors are in favour of such publication.

IV.2.1.2. Requirement of consensual management for compound works

Compound works are made up of separate pieces of writing by more than one author who then combine their works to be used by everyone. A book where each chapter was written by a different person is a good example of a compound work.

As mentioned before in this study (see chapter III.2.), works created by more than one author can be compound or derivative, depending on how the work was created and what was the nature and purpose of collaboration. In any case, managing rights becomes more challenging when consensus is required among all authors about the use of such works which can complicate the dissemination of the entire composite work, restrict access to information and hinder collaborative efforts and innovation.

Authors of Compound Works

Article 20 of the CCRRA

- (1) If two or more authors join their created works for the purpose of a joint use, each of them shall keep the copyright in his own work.*
- (2) Mutual relations between authors of a compound work shall be regulated by a contract. If such contract is not concluded or unless otherwise provided by a contract or by rules of a relevant collective management organisation, all the authors of a compound work shall be considered to be entitled to an equal share in the remuneration to be obtained for the use of such compound work.*
- (3) A musical work with lyrics is considered a compound work.*

Article 20 of the CRRRA stipulates that should two or more authors join their produced works into a single compound publication or other work, each of them will retain the copyright in their own contributions.

A contract will control the mutual relations among compound work authors. The article further regulates that all the authors of a compound work are regarded as being entitled to equal share in the remuneration if such contract is not concluded or unless otherwise stated by a contract or by the rules of a relevant collective management organisation.

As with the provisions of Article 21 of the CRRRA, these provisions also represent a problem for achieving Open Science objectives as they allow a single contributing author to object to a use of work in a way that is compatible with the purposes of Open Science.

IV.2.2. Barriers stemming from the unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation

Under copyright law, unwaivability is the inability of authors or performers to voluntarily renounce some rights. Although unwaivability aims to safeguard authors; by limiting the freedom in rights management required to guarantee Open Access to and reuse of works, it can significantly impede Open Science.

Unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation supposes that remuneration must be paid to the author for the usage of a copyright work.

Payment of an Appropriate Remuneration for Reproduction for Private Use

Article 184 of the CRRRA

(1) The appropriate remuneration referred to in Article 183, paragraph (2) of this Act shall be paid by manufacturers of blank sound, image or text media, manufacturers of audio and visual recording devices, manufacturers of photocopiers, and jointly with them importers of blank audio, video or text media, audio devices and visual recording, photocopiers, unless they are imports of small quantities intended for private and non-commercial use as part of personal luggage. If the listed devices and items are not manufactured in the Republic of Croatia, the fee shall be paid by the importer.

(2) The obligation to pay the appropriate remuneration arises upon the first sale in the Republic of Croatia or import into the Republic of Croatia of new blank sound, image or text carriers, new audio and visual recording devices and new photocopying devices.

(3) The obligation to pay the appropriate remuneration also arises when the devices and carriers referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article are brought into the Republic of Croatia from another Member State of the European Union.

(4) The obligation to pay the appropriate remuneration does not arise if new blank sound, image or text carriers, new audio and visual recording devices, and new photocopying devices are taken out or exported from the Republic of Croatia.

(5) The remuneration referred to in Article 183, paragraph (3) of this Act shall be paid according to the data on the number of photocopies made.

(6) The authors may not waive the right to appropriate remuneration referred to in Article 183, paragraphs (2) and (3) of this Act. The remuneration must be paid collectively.

Article 184 of the CRRRA requires the payment of “appropriate remuneration” (Cro. *odgovarajuća naknada*) for the reproduction of works for private use. This obligation lies with manufacturers and importers of blank media, audiovisual recording devices, and photocopiers. Paragraph (6) of the Article states that authors “may not waive the right to appropriate remuneration” for private copying. This remuneration needs to be paid collectively, meaning authors cannot individually choose to forgo or redirect these fees (e.g.,

to waive them in support of Open Access). Because authors cannot waive the fee or opt out of the collective scheme, they cannot freely distribute their works without the mandatory levy. This creates administrative and financial complexities for institutions and repositories that might otherwise want to host open-access content without incurring or passing on costs.

Distribution, Rental Right and Lending Right

Article 34 of the CCRRA

(1) The right of distribution shall be the exclusive right to put into circulation the original or copies of the copyright work by sale or otherwise, including rental right, and to offer them to the public for such purpose. Storage of copies of the copyright work and taking other actions to distribute copies of the copyright work is equated with distribution.

(2) The rental right is the exclusive right of giving the original or copies of a copyright work for use in a limited period, for the purpose of direct or indirect material or commercial benefit. The rental right of a copyright work shall not apply to architectural works and works of applied art already made.

(3) Public lending implies the manner of placing the original or copies of a copyright work, in respect of which further distribution is permitted, on the market when they are made available for use in a limited period through public libraries, without direct or indirect material or commercial benefit. Public lending does not require the author's approval, but an appropriate remuneration must be paid (hereinafter: the right to a public lending remuneration).

(4) The first sale of the original or copies of the copyright work or other form of transfer of ownership, by the author or with his consent, in the territory of any of the Member States of the European Union, or any of the States Parties to the Agreement Creating the European Economic Area, respectively shall exhaust the right of distribution in respect of such original and such copies respectively, for the territory of the Republic of Croatia. The exhaustion of the distribution right shall not cause the rental right of a copyright work to expire, the right of the author to authorise or prohibit the export to or the import from a third country of the original or copies of the copyright work, and the right to remuneration for public lending of the work.

(5) In respect of collections and copyright databases, the exhaustion of the distribution right shall refer only to further sale.

(6) The author who has given up his rental right in favour of a producer of phonograms or of an audiovisual producer shall retain the right to receive equitable remuneration for the rental of his copyright work. The author may not renounce the right to the equitable remuneration. Remuneration for the rental shall be paid by the person renting the copyright work. The right to the equitable remuneration for the rental shall be exercised mandatory collectively.

(7) The author may not renounce the right to the remuneration for public lending. The right to the remuneration for public lending shall be exercised mandatory collectively.

(8) Public lending referred to in paragraph (3) of this Article shall not apply to buildings and works of applied art.

(9) The right to the remuneration for public lending shall not apply to copyright works mutually lent by public libraries.

(10) By way of derogation from the provision of paragraphs (1), (3) and (7) of this Article, authors of copyright databases and authors of computer programs shall have the exclusive right of public lending of the originals or copies of their copyright databases and computer programs.

Article 34 of the CCRRA addresses the distribution right – including rental – over copyright works. Paragraphs (3), (6), and (7) specifically refer to the right to remuneration for public lending and rental.

Paragraph (6) ensures that authors who transfer or assign their rental right to a producer still retain a right to “equitable remuneration” (Cro. *odgovarajuća naknada*) for every rental of the work. The Act explicitly states that “the author may not renounce the right to equitable remuneration.”

Paragraph (7) similarly provides that “the author may not renounce the right to remuneration for public lending,” and that it must be exercised collectively.

These provisions mean authors cannot simply decide to allow free lending or no-fee rentals of their works, as the remuneration must be collected on their behalf. Even if the author intends to support Open Access distribution, the Act imposes mandatory collective licensing and remuneration.

Contract on Audiovisual Production between the Audiovisual Producer and the Principal and Other Co-Authors of an Audiovisual Work
Article 92 of the CCRRA

(1) A contract on audiovisual production between the audiovisual producer and the principal and other co-authors of an audiovisual work shall regulate the rights and obligations of contracting parties in creating an audiovisual work, the content of the right of exploitation that the principal co-author and other co-authors undertake to establish for the audiovisual producer under that contract, the duration and area for which the rights of exploitation are established, the remuneration that the audiovisual producer undertakes to pay to the principal and other co-authors for the creation of the audiovisual work under the contract and for establishing the right of exploitation of that work and other terms of the contract.

(2) If the principal co-author and other co-authors of an audiovisual work have entrusted their rental right to the audiovisual producer by the contract referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article, they shall retain the right to an equitable remuneration for the rental of their audiovisual work, which they cannot renounce.

(3) The remuneration for the rental shall be paid by the person renting the audiovisual work.

(4) The right to an equitable remuneration for the rental shall be exercised collectively.

Contract on Audiovisual Production between the Audiovisual Producer and the Authors of Contributions to an Audiovisual Work
Article 93 of the CCRRA

(1) Unless otherwise provided by the contract on audiovisual production between the audiovisual producer and the authors of contributions, it shall be considered that the audiovisual producer acquires all the economic rights of the authors of contributions to the extent necessary to fulfil the purpose of the contract.

(2) Notwithstanding the provisions laid down in paragraph (1) of this Article, the authors of contributions shall retain the right to use individually their contributions to an audiovisual work, provided that the rights of audiovisual producers of that work are not prejudiced thereby. The authors of contributions cannot renounce that right.

Under Article 92(2) of the CCRRA, if principal co-authors or other co-authors assign their rental right to an audiovisual producer, they still retain an unwaivable right to equitable remuneration for each rental. They cannot renounce this right, and it is similarly subject to collective management.

Article 93(2) of the CCRRA states that authors of contributions “*shall retain the right to use individually their contributions,*” which they cannot renounce, so long as exercising this right does not prejudice the audiovisual producer’s rights.

From the provisions of Article 92 and 93 of the CCRRA, it is provided that coauthors and contributors cannot fully waive rental remuneration and related rights even if they prefer to release their audiovisual works under an open license. This forced retention of a right to payment again undermines the flexibility needed to share works entirely free of charge, thus presenting an obstacle to Open Science goals.

Distribution, Rental Right and Lending Right
Article 135 of the CCRRA

(1) A performer shall have the exclusive right to distribute, including the rental right, of his fixed performance and the right to an equitable remuneration if the copies of his fixed performance permitted to be further distributed are being lent through public libraries.

(2) A performer, who entrusts his rental right to a producer of phonograms or to an audiovisual producer, shall retain his right to an equitable remuneration for the rental of his fixed performance. Remuneration for the rental shall be paid by the person renting the artistic performance.

(3) The performer may not renounce the right to an equitable remuneration for the public lending referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article or the right to an equitable remuneration for the rental referred to in paragraph (2) of this Article. The right to an equitable remuneration for the public lending and the right to an equitable remuneration for the rental shall be exercised collectively only.

Article 135(1) of the CCRRA gives performers the exclusive right to distribute and rent their fixed performances and to receive equitable remuneration for public lending. Paragraph (3) states that the performer “*may not renounce the right to an equitable remuneration*” for public lending or rental when such rights are transferred to a phonogram or audiovisual producer. These rights then must also be exercised collectively through established collective management organisations such as HUZIP, ZAPRAF and others.⁹² Even if a performer wishes to enable free and open sharing of their recordings or performances for research, educational, or other public-benefit purposes, they cannot waive the associated remuneration.

Termination of a Contract between a Performer and a Phonogram Producer

Article 146 of the CCRRA

(1) *If, 50 years after the phonogram was lawfully published, or failing such publication, respectively, 50 years after it was lawfully communicated to the public, the phonogram producer does not offer copies of the phonogram for sale in the quantity satisfying reasonable needs of the public or does not make it available to the public, the performer may terminate the contract which was concluded for the whole duration of the protection of the performer’s rights and by which the phonogram producer was granted the right of exploitation of the performance fixed on a phonogram.*

(2) *Prior to the termination of the contract referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article, the performer shall notify the phonogram producer that he is obliged to issue the phonogram within a period of one year, counting from the day of receipt of the written notification of the performer.*

(3) *The performer may not waive the right to terminate the contract referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article.*

(4) *If a plurality of performers participated in the creation of a performance, they may terminate the contract referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article jointly or in accordance with the provision of Article 130 of this Act.*

(5) *The performer terminated the contract in accordance with paragraph (1) of this Article, the rights of the phonogram producer in this phonogram shall expire upon the expiration of 50 years from the lawful publication of the phonogram or, failing such publication, 50 years from its lawful communication to the public.*

According to Article 146 of the CCRRA, performers have the right to terminate a contract if the phonogram producer fails to exploit the phonogram after 50 years. Paragraph (3) clarifies that the performer “*may not waive the right*” to terminate this contract.

Although these articles focus on long-term performer protections rather than everyday open-access use, they illustrate the broader legislative stance of providing inalienable (unwaivable) economic rights. Even if an artist or performer would prefer to forego future revenue to ensure unhampered sharing, the law obliges them to retain these rights.

Annual Supplementary Remuneration

Article 147 of the CCRRA

(1) *If, according to the contract between a performer and a phonogram producer, which was concluded for the whole term of protection of the performer’s rights and by which the phonogram producer was granted the right of exploitation of the performance fixed in a phonogram, the performer has acquired a right to obtain a one-off remuneration, the performer, according to this Act, shall acquire a right to obtain an annual supplementary remuneration.*

(2) *The phonogram producer shall pay to the performer an annual supplementary remuneration for each full year following the 50th year after the phonogram was lawfully published or, failing such publication, the 50th year after it was lawfully communicated to the public, respectively.*

(3) *The performer may not waive the right to obtain the annual supplementary remuneration. This remuneration shall be exercised collectively only.*

(4) *The annual supplementary remuneration shall amount to 20% of the revenue which the phonogram producer has derived from the reproduction, distribution and making available to the public of the phonogram containing the fixed*

⁹² State Intellectual Property Office of the Republic of Croatia lists registered collective management organizations, for more information see the following link: <https://www.dziv.hr/hr/intelektualno-vlasnistvo/autorsko-pravo/ostvarivanje/kolektivno/>

performance of the performer, and it shall be calculated on the basis of the revenue derived by the phonogram producer in the year preceding the year for which it is due.

(5) The phonogram producer shall give to the performer, to the person authorised by him as well as to the appropriate collective management organisation, any information necessary for payment of the annual supplementary remuneration.

Article 147 of the CRRRA deals with the issue of supplementary remuneration. If a performer has initially agreed to a one-off fee for a phonogram, after 50 years they become entitled to an “*annual supplementary remuneration*” (Cro. *dodatna godišnja naknada*). Paragraph (3) explicitly states that the performer “*may not waive the right to obtain the annual supplementary remuneration,*” and it must be exercised collectively. Although these articles focus on long-term performer protections rather than everyday open-access use, they illustrate the broader legislative stance of securing inalienable financial rights. Even if an artist or performer would prefer to forgo future revenue to ensure unhampered sharing, the law obliges them to retain these rights.

Taken together, these provisions reinforce a legislative framework in which authors and performers cannot waive rights to remuneration for private copying, rental, public lending, and certain forms of exploitation (especially regarding phonograms, audiovisual works, and contributions to audiovisual works). The CRRRA requires authors and performers to channel certain remuneration claims through collective management organisations, making it impossible completely to opt out in favour of Open Access or dedicated/open licensing.

In the context of Open Science, these unwaivable remuneration rights can impede the goal of broad, barrier-free dissemination. Institutions – such as libraries, repositories, and online platforms – may need to navigate licensing paperwork or collect fees, which runs counter to the principle of completely free and Open Access. While these unwaivable rights are designed to protect authors and performers economically, they also reduce the flexibility authors have in choosing how their works are shared and used.

IV.2.3. Barriers stemming from the requirement for specific, separate transfers

The requirement for separate transfers of rights can create obstacles for Open Science by complicating rights management and reducing flexibility for authors. Instead of a streamlined process, authors must handle multiple agreements for different rights components, making Open Access and reuse of scientific outputs more complex. This additional burden may discourage researchers from opting for Open Access publication, ultimately limiting the dissemination of knowledge.

IV.2.3.1. Requirement for specific – separate transfers of the right to remuneration

The necessity for separate rights transfers in copyright law can pose considerable obstacles for Open Science by complicating rights management and restricting authors' flexibility to make their works freely accessible.

Authors need to negotiate each specific component separately rather than transferring a unified set of rights, complicating and prolonging the process. This fragmentation may dissuade authors from engaging in Open Science principles (i.e., Open Access to and reuse of works), thereby limiting the distribution and reuse of scientific outputs.

The question is whether we find such a provision in the CCRRA? In short, the answer is no – the CCRRA does not use the same detailed “rule of separate transfers” approach found in Slovenian law. In more detail, while it does regulate private copying levies (Article 184), rental and lending rights (Article 34), rights in audiovisual works and performers’ rights (Articles 92, 93, 135, etc.), and written form requirements for licence agreements (Articles 65, 66), it seems none of these provisions expressly split off the right of communication to the public in the context of an “online content-sharing service”, nor do they reserve a separate right to remuneration for the author.

Under the Slovenian ZASP, Article 76(6), an author who transfers the right of communication to the public to an online content-sharing service still retains a separate, unwaivable right to remuneration. By contrast, CCRRA Article 34 and related provisions discuss unwaivable rights to remuneration for rental, public lending, and private copying, but do not mention online content-sharing or communication to the public in digital platforms. The CCRRA does not include a provision stating that if an author transfers the right of communication to an online platform, they specifically retain a separate right to remuneration from that online content-sharing service. The CCRRA does not carve out a separate, unwaivable remuneration right tied expressly to “online content-sharing services” or “platforms” in the manner in which the Slovenian act does.

Distribution, Rental Right and Lending Right
Article 34 of the CCRRA

(1) The right of distribution shall be the exclusive right to put into circulation the original or copies of the copyright work by sale or otherwise, including rental right, and to offer them to the public for such purpose. Storage of copies of the copyright work and taking other actions to distribute copies of the copyright work is equated with distribution.

(2) The rental right is the exclusive right of giving the original or copies of a copyright work for use in a limited period, for the purpose of direct or indirect material or commercial benefit. The rental right of a copyright work shall not apply to architectural works and works of applied art already made.

(3) Public lending implies the manner of placing the original or copies of a copyright work, in respect of which further distribution is permitted, on the market when they are made available for use in a limited period through public libraries, without direct or indirect material or commercial benefit. Public lending does not require the author’s approval, but an appropriate remuneration must be paid (hereinafter: the right to a public lending remuneration).

(4) The first sale of the original or copies of the copyright work or other form of transfer of ownership, by the author or with his consent, in the territory of any of the Member States of the European Union, or any of the States Parties to the Agreement Creating the European Economic Area, respectively shall exhaust the right of distribution in respect of such original and such copies respectively, for the territory of the Republic of Croatia. The exhaustion of the distribution right shall not cause the rental right of a copyright work to expire, the right of the author to authorise or prohibit the export to or the import from a third country of the original or copies of the copyright work, and the right to remuneration for public lending of the work.

(5) In respect of collections and copyright databases, the exhaustion of the distribution right shall refer only to further sale.

(6) The author who has given up his rental right in favour of a producer of phonograms or of an audiovisual producer shall retain the right to receive equitable remuneration for the rental of his copyright work. The author may not renounce the right to the equitable remuneration. Remuneration for the rental shall be paid by the person renting the copyright work. The right to the equitable remuneration for the rental shall be exercised mandatory collectively.

(7) The author may not renounce the right to the remuneration for public lending. The right to the remuneration for public lending shall be exercised mandatory collectively.

(8) Public lending referred to in paragraph (3) of this Article shall not apply to buildings and works of applied art.

(9) The right to the remuneration for public lending shall not apply to copyright works mutually lent by public libraries.

(10) By way of derogation from the provision of paragraphs (1), (3) and (7) of this Article, authors of copyright databases and authors of computer programs shall have the exclusive right of public lending of the originals or copies of their copyright databases and computer programs.

IV.2.3.2. Requirement for specific, separate transfers of rights for the use of copyright works

The CCRRA does not fragment the right of reproduction or the right of distribution in the same manner as Article 76 of the Slovenian ZASP (paragraphs (2) and (3)). In the CCRRA, the rights of reproduction and distribution are treated more generally and are not subdivided into separate components (e.g., separate “right to save in electronic form,” “right to fix in sound or visual form,” or “right of importation”). Thus, the author is not aware of a direct equivalent provision in Croatian law that expressly requires separate transfers for each of these specific sub-rights.

IV.2.4. Barriers stemming from the requirement for special consent of the author for subsequent transfers

Granting of Further Rights of Exploitation

Article 62 of the CCRRA

(1) The holder of the exclusive right of exploitation may, on the basis of his right, grant to another person further right of exploitation only with the written authorisation of the author. The author may not refuse to give his authorisation, if it would be contrary to conscientiousness and fairness. The authorisation shall not be necessary if the right of exploitation has been granted only for the sake of its exercising for the benefit of the author.

(2) The provision under paragraph (1) of this Article shall not apply to audiovisual works and computer programs. Audiovisual producer and the holder of the exclusive right of exploitation may grant to another person further right of exploitation only without prior authorisation of the author.

A subsequent grant of rights (i.e., sub-licensing or transferring exploitation rights to a new party) typically requires the written authorisation of the original author. The author may not refuse authorisation if doing so would be contrary to good faith (conscientiousness and fairness) principles. This creates a legal check preventing the author from arbitrarily withholding consent. Paragraph (2) of Article 62 states that for audiovisual works and computer programs, no such authorisation from the author is required to further grant rights of exploitation.

Like Article 78(1) of ZASP, Article 62(1) of the CCRRA offers authors continued control over how their work is subsequently licensed or transferred. Both provisions require either explicit

consent (ZASP) or written authorization (CCRRA). Unlike ZASP, the CCRRA introduces a stipulation that the author's refusal should not violate the principle of good faith. This potentially makes it easier for the holder of rights to obtain consent – if refusing authorisation would be deemed unfair, the author can be compelled to grant permission. The CCRRA excludes audiovisual works and computer programs from the mandatory consent rule for subsequent transfers, meaning authors in these fields do not retain the same level of control as in other creative fields.

The requirement that the rightsholder seek the author's written authorisation can be time-consuming and overly administrative. As a result, even when research outputs may need rapid dissemination or multiple transfers (e.g., to repositories, consortia, or collaborative platforms), each new requirement risks delay. The "good faith" defence can help avoid outright refusal if an author's withholding of consent appears unreasonable. This may allow sub-licenses that support open dissemination to proceed more smoothly in cases where an author's refusal would be purely obstructive.

Article 62 of the CCRRA resembles Article 78 of ZASP by generally requiring the author's authorisation before rights can be passed along to new parties. While this can preserve an author's control and help them ensure open licenses remain in place, it also adds a procedural hurdle and potentially restricts the sharing practices that Open Science requires.

IV.2.5. Barriers stemming from the requirement of formality

Copyright Contracts
Article 65 of the CCRRA

(1) A contract on the basis of which the right of exploitation of copyright (hereinafter: copyright contract) is acquired shall be concluded in a written form, unless otherwise provided by this Act.

Content of Copyright Contracts
Article 66 of the CCRRA

(1) A copyright contract shall specify at least the work it concerns, the manner of use, the remuneration for the use of the work or an explicit provision that the right of use shall be exercised without remuneration and the person authorised to use the copyright work.

(2) A copyright contract may also be concluded in respect of a work which is not yet created, provided that it defines the type of the work and the manner of use of the future work.

(3) A contractual provision concerning the grant of the right of exploitation of all author's future works shall be null and void.

Article 65, paragraph (1) of the CCRRA parallels Slovenia's requirement for a written contract to transfer or license rights. Unlike Article 80 of ZASP, the CCRRA does not explicitly say that failing to meet the formal requirements – or if the contract's meaning is unclear – triggers a presumption favouring the author. Instead, general Croatian contract law principles apply, which do not specifically include the provisions that ensure the interpretation in the favour of the author. Contract content formalities in Croatian CCRRA can potentially slow the process of making works openly accessible as each transfer or license (e.g., adopting a Creative Commons license) typically requires a contract in writing.

This can be cumbersome and prevent rapid dissemination. It is also somewhat less protective of authors as there is no explicit rule stating that unclear clauses are interpreted in the author's favour. As a result, authors may have fewer statutory safeguards in ambiguous contract situations, which would, if it existed, potentially help enable sharing.

IV.2.6. Barriers stemming from the presumption of the publisher's priority right

Publisher's Priority Right

Article 81 of the CCRRA

(1) A publisher, who has acquired the right to publish the copyright work, and he was not granted the rights of exploitation in the publishing contract according to Article 73 paragraphs (1) and (2) of this Act, has among other publishers who offer equal terms, the priority right to publish that work in an electronic or any other form.

(2) A publisher who intends to use the priority right referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article, shall submit his offer to the author, within 30 days upon receipt of the author's written invitation.

(3) The priority right referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article, shall last for a period of two years as from the date of concluding a publishing contract.

This mirrors the structure of Article 89 of ZASP, in which the publisher who has already acquired the right to publish in book form is given a priority to publish in electronic (or other) forms, provided they meet the same or equivalent terms offered by another publisher. The Croatian priority right can limit an author's ability freely to release or distribute their work in electronic form – such as uploading to Open Access repositories or publishing under open licenses – if the publisher holds and exercises this prerogative. In the absence of a publisher's decision, authors may be forced to wait for this or until the two-year window expires, hindering immediate open dissemination.

If the publisher is slow to respond or exercises the right only at the end of the prescribed 30-day period, this could affect and postpone any open-access release. This delay could be problematic for fast-moving scientific fields where timely dissemination is crucial. By granting publishers a preferential right to electronic publication, the law effectively tilts the power balance in favour of the publisher, making it harder for authors to explore alternative channels (such as Open Access publishers or direct posting on institutional repositories) without first giving the original publisher a chance to publish the work electronically.

Priority rights could also complicate or delay the introduction of *Secondary Publishing Rights* (e.g., the right of authors to place a version of their work in an open repository after an embargo period). If a publisher has two years to exercise their prerogative, this might limit or postpone authors' ability to deposit copies in open repositories during that timeframe.

It may be concluded that from the functional perspective Article 81 of the CCRRA offers an equivalent to Article 89 of ZASP. While this mechanism protects publishers' investment in disseminating works, it can create barriers to Open Science by delaying or restricting authors' options for making their works freely and immediately accessible.

IV.3. Provisions in Croatian Copyright Law that can be both barriers and enablers of Open Science

Certain copyright provisions can act as both barriers and enablers for Open Science, depending on how they are implemented in practice. While some legal requirements may initially seem restrictive, they can, under the right conditions, also support the dissemination and reuse of scientific outputs. The extent to which these provisions facilitate or hinder Open Access often depends on the approach taken by rights holders, including publishers, employers, and collective management organisations.

IV.3.1. Barriers that might also act as enablers stemming from the presumption of transfer of economic rights from employees to employers

Croatia does not have a direct parallel to Slovenia's Article 101 of ZASP – there is no universal 10-year term or automatic reversion for employee-created works. Instead, the extent to which an employer automatically obtains exploitation rights tends to be more contract-dependent (with certain categorical exceptions like computer programs).

As there is no uniform rule mandating that all rights to an employee-created work automatically vest in the employer for a fixed term, usually such arrangement depends on a written employment agreement. This can lead to various results. If a contract says the employer acquires (or retains) certain rights outright, the author-employee may have little control over releasing the work under an open license. Some employees might retain broader rights in their creations and thus have greater leeway to share them openly, assuming their employment agreement allows it. In roles or sectors where it is standard for the employer to insist on a full transfer of economic rights, the effect is much the same as in countries where the employer decides whether or not to support Open Science dissemination.

IV.4. Enablers in Croatian Copyright Law

Copyright Works Created in Scientific, Artistic, Teaching and Professional Work at Higher Education Institutions and Scientific Organisations
Article 110 of the CCRA

(1) With regard to copyright works created by scientists, associates and teachers elected to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, scientific, teaching, associate and professional titles, in the performance of their teaching, educational or similar activities, in higher education 42 institutions and scientific organisations, Articles from 100 to 103 and Article 109 of this Act shall apply.

(2) Copyright on copyright works created by scientists, associates and teachers elected to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, scientific, teaching, associate and professional titles, in accordance with the act governing scientific and artistic activity and higher education, in the performance of their scientific, research, professional, artistic or similar activities, at higher education institutions and in scientific organisations, belong to their authors, without limitations, unless provided otherwise by the employment contract, other act regulating the employment relationship, collective agreement or other contract with the author.

(3) Higher education institutions and scientific organisations may adopt rules on the management of copyright works and related copyrights at higher education institutions and scientific organisations, in accordance with this Act.

Article 110 of the CCRRA addresses a scenario for copyright works created by scientists, associates, and teachers at higher education institutions and scientific organizations.

Article 110, paragraph (1) clarifies that the general employment-related rules in Articles 100 to 103 and Article 109 concerning works made for hire also apply to these specific categories of works. Article 110, paragraph (2) states that copyright belongs to the author (the scientist, teacher, etc.) “without limitations,” unless otherwise determined by an employment contract, another act regulating the employment, a collective agreement or other contract with the author.

Article 110, paragraph (3) empowers higher education institutions and scientific organisations to adopt their own rules on managing copyright and related rights. This means that individual institutions may decide to implement policy frameworks regarding ownership, exploitation, or dissemination of works created by their employees. The default rule confers rights to the author (the researcher or educator) “without limitations,” thereby granting them the autonomy to license or publish their works under Open Access models (e.g., using a Creative Commons licence). In the absence of contrary contractual or internal regulations, the author may pursue an open dissemination strategy. Paragraph (3) permits institutions to establish internal regulations that explicitly promote or necessitate Open Science, such as mandating Open Access or Secondary Publishing in an institutional repository. Certain Croatian universities or research institutions may or already do use this to formalise pro-Open Science policies, thereby enhancing widespread free access to academic outputs.

IV.4.1. Enabler stemming from the exception for text and data mining for scientific research

Text and Data Mining for Scientific Research
Article 187 of the CCRRA

(1) It is permitted, without the right holder's authorisation and without payment of remuneration, to reproduce copyright works, including copyright databases and subject matter of related rights, including the extraction of a part and the reuse of all or a substantial part of the content of a non-original database, when performed by scientific organisations and cultural heritage institutions for the purpose of text and data mining for the needs of scientific research, in copyright works and subject matter of related rights to which they have lawful access.

(2) Scientific organisation is a university, including its libraries, a scientific institute or office, entities of the university, a hospital conducting research work or any other entity with the main goal to conduct scientific research or to perform educational activities that include the implementation of scientific research on a non-profit basis as well or the reinvestment of the entire profit into scientific research or in accordance with the mission of public interest recognised by the Republic of Croatia (for example, by public financing or a special law or public contracts), namely in the way that access to the results obtained by such scientific research cannot be granted on a privileged basis to an entrepreneur who exerts a decisive influence on such organisation.

(3) A cultural heritage institution is a publicly available library or museum, archive or film or audiovisual heritage institution. This includes national libraries and national archives, as well as archives and publicly available libraries of educational institutions, scientific organizations and public broadcasting organisations.

(4) Text and data mining implies any automated analytical technique aiming at text and data analysis in digital form to generate data, which includes patterns, trends and correlations.

(5) Lawful access implies access to the contents protected by copyright or related rights based on, inter alia, contracting relationship between a right holder and scientific organisations and cultural heritage institutions, which can be a subscription

relationship, a relationship based on an open access policy or other legitimate means of gaining access to the contents protected by copyright or related rights. All persons covered by subscriptions and use agreements shall be considered to have legal access due to their connection with scientific organizations and cultural heritage institutions.

(6) Scientific organisations and cultural heritage institutions shall store the results of reproduction and extraction made in accordance with paragraph (1) of this Article with an appropriate level of security and may keep them for the purposes of scientific research, including the verification of the results of scientific research.

(7) Right holders may apply measures to ensure the security and integrity of networks and databases on or in which works and subject matter of related rights are located, such as IP address verification measures or user authentication procedures. These measures shall be proportionate to the risks involved and shall not go beyond what is necessary to achieve the objective of ensuring the security and integrity of the system and shall not prejudice the effectiveness of the application of the limitations referred to in paragraph (1) of this Article.

(8) Right holders, scientific organisations and cultural heritage institutions shall cooperate in order to agree upon the best practices related to the application of obligations referred to in paragraph (6) and the measures referred to in paragraph (7) of this Article.

(9) Contract provisions contrary to this Article shall be null and void.

Common Provisions

Article 181 of the CCRRA

(1) Disclosed copyright work or subject matter of a related right under this Act may be used without the right holder's authorisation, or without the right holder's authorisation and without payment of remuneration, only in the cases which are expressly stipulated in this Act (hereinafter: content limitations).

(2) The provisions concerning the content limitations referred to in this Chapter of the Act cover only such uses of a copyright work or subject matter of a related right which do not conflict with regular use of the work and do not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the right holder.

Article 181 CCRRA spells out the general rules for all “content limitations” (the standard “three-step test” in copyright).

Article 187 CCRRA, titled *Text and Data Mining for Scientific Research* does seem to provide a TDM exception very similar to Slovenia's Article 57b in overall purpose and effect. This provision authorises reproductions for TDM and references lawful access and contains a provision that when applicable invalidates contractual provisions that try to override this exception.

IV.5. Barriers and enablers outside of copyright law in Croatia

Croatia does not currently have a law akin to the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Activity Act (ZZrID) that formally embeds a *Rights Retention* mechanism or *Secondary Publishing Rights* into the national legal framework. Similarly, there is no Croatian equivalent to Slovenia's Decree on Open Science or a statutory *Rights Retention* clause that compels publishers or employers to allow Open Access posting of publicly funded research.

The Act on Scientific Activity and Higher Education governs universities and public research organisations, but it does not contain explicit, mandatory rules ensuring authors can retain rights to deposit or openly re-publish research articles funded by the public. Some of the science funding bodies (e.g., the Croatian Science Foundation) encourage Open Access, but these are policy guidelines rather than statutory obligations.

Croatia's cultural heritage legislation illustrates a barrier outside copyright law that can hinder Open Science, particularly the open sharing of cultural heritage research outputs. The *Act on the Protection and Preservation of Cultural Objects*⁹³ imposes restrictions and fees on the use of Croatia's cultural heritage regulating that a person who reproduces or uses the image of a recognised cultural object for commercial purposes is required to pay a fee to the state. These provisions act as a de facto intellectual property regime over Public Domain cultural works, since they require permission fees for any commercial use of images of cultural goods. Unlike copyright (which expires after a term), this protection for cultural heritage is indefinite and can conflict with Open Science goals. Researchers who photograph artifacts or monuments for study can technically use those images for research and educational purposes freely but cannot release them under a fully open license (such as CC-BY) for wider reuse if commercial use is anticipated without triggering fees. This mirrors the situation in Italy and Slovenia, where cultural heritage laws require consent and/or fees for commercial reuse of Public Domain images. In Croatia, the requirement to pay royalties to use heritage images also poses a barrier to open educational resources, and any open-access publication that might include such images, since open licenses allow commercial reuse.

At the university and institute level, there has been a notable wave of Open Science policies and mandates across Croatia's research-performing organisations. Several major universities have recently adopted their own Open Science or Open Access policies, often in line with European University Association recommendations. For instance, the University of Zagreb (Croatia's largest university) approved an Open Science Policy in 2024⁹⁴, and the University of Split and University of Osijek⁹⁵ both established Open Science policies in 2023.

The University of Rijeka was an early mover, issuing an Open Science Policy in 2021 and in 2022 going further to enact a mandate on Open Access⁹⁶. This requires that all scientific, scholarly and educational works – as well as the underlying research data – produced at the university must be deposited in the institutional repository and made publicly available. This mandate in Rijeka ensures that faculty and researchers self-archive their articles, papers, and datasets, providing free access unless legally or ethically restricted. Other institutions (University of Zadar, University of Slavonski Brod, etc.) have likewise declared support for Open Science and set up guidelines for implementation. These institutional policies often cover aspects such as encouraging (or requiring) publication in Open Access journals or repositories, providing support for open data, and recognising Open Science activities in academic evaluations.

While compliance and enforcement vary by institution, the trend is clear – Croatian academia is embracing Open Science through internal regulations, which complement broader national strategies and funder mandates. This bottom-up momentum is important, because in the

⁹³ NN 145/24, available at: <<https://www.zakon.hr/z/340/Zakon-o-za%C5%A1titi-i-o%C4%8Duvanju-kulturnih-dobara>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁹⁴ Available at:

<https://www.unizg.hr/fileadmin/rektorat/Istrazivanja/Istrazivanje/Pravilnici/Politika_otvorene_znanosti_FINAL_19_9_24.pdf>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁹⁵ Available at: <<https://zpio.unios.hr/download/politika-otvorene-znanosti-u-sveucilistu-josipa-jurja-strossmayera-u-osijeku/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁹⁶ Available at: <<https://uniri.hr/znanost-i-istravanje/otvorena-znanost/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

absence of a single national mandate for open publications, universities are using their autonomy to fill the gap and incentivise researchers to share their work openly.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Open Science is widely recognized as a driver of innovation and societal progress. The EU and its Member States have built a strategic and political framework that supports implementation of principles of Open Science, yet legal barriers – particularly within copyright law – continue to limit its full potential.

This study has identified and analysed provisions in copyright legislation and beyond that either impede or facilitate implementation of Open Science on the national level. The study complements several existing EU studies that study potential barriers and enablers predominantly on the EU level.

The findings reveal that despite the increasing recognition of Open Science principles, copyright laws in all three jurisdictions analysed (the Slovenian, Italian and Croatian), still impose significant legal barriers. Provisions requiring unanimous consent among co-authors for the publication or sharing of research outputs frequently obstruct open dissemination, as a single author's refusal can block access to an entire collaborative work. Unwaivable rights to remuneration impose financial and administrative burdens on researchers who wish to share their work openly, creating legal uncertainty about whether institutions and/or repositories must pay compensation (usually to collective management organisations) even when authors explicitly release their work under open licenses.

Formalistic requirements for rights transfers, such as the mandatory written form for any authorisation or license, further complicate efforts to apply open licensing models. Publisher priority rights, which grant exclusive publication privileges to initial publishers for a fixed period, also restrict authors' ability to make their work openly accessible in a timely manner. These limitations, present to varying degrees in all three legal systems, significantly curtail researchers' ability to share, reuse, and build upon scientific knowledge.

At the same time presumptions of transfers of material rights from employers to employees can have both restrictive and enabling effects. Such a provision in Slovenian law can constrain authors' ability to manage their own copyrights but may also serve as an enabler of Open Science in cases when authors-researchers are reluctant or indifferent about Open Access and reuse, but their institutions actively support Open Science policies.

This study also highlights important national variations in legal frameworks for Open Science and a degree of provision of enablers for Open Science. Slovenia has incorporated a top-down *Rights Retention* provision into its national research legislation, ensuring that authors of publicly funded research retain the right to make their work openly available. In May 2025, Slovenia further strengthened its national legal framework by adopting an amendment to the ZZrID,⁹⁷ introducing *Secondary Publishing Rights* into Article 41 of ZZrID. This provision allows researchers to republish their articles in Open Access repositories after formal publication. Italy, by contrast, introduced an Open Access mandate through a 2013 decree, which requires

⁹⁷ Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Slovenia (2024). Act Amending and Supplementing the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act. Available at: <<https://e-uprava.gov.si/si/drzava-in-druzba/e-demokracija/predlogi-predpisov/predlog-predpisa.html?id=16439>>, last accessed in May 2025;

publicly funded research to be made available in open repositories after an embargo period of 18 to 24 months. This provision lacks an enforcement mechanism and does not override contractual obligations with publishers, which has limited its impact in practice. Croatia's legislation does not currently contain any specific provisions to facilitate Open Science. The management of copyright is subject to the standard framework without any legal enablers for open dissemination. As a result, Open Science in Croatia relies primarily on institutional policies and voluntary initiatives rather than top-down legislative support.

A key finding of this study is that there is a gap between Open Science strategic and political commitments and legal realities. All three countries have adopted national strategies that promote Open Science, but copyright law has not yet been aligned with these objectives. Instead, researchers must navigate a complex landscape where legal uncertainties, contractual restrictions imposed by law or legal presumptions create obstacles to the effective management of their copyrights according to principles of Open Science, including for publicly funded works.

The study demonstrates also that national differences in copyright law create challenges for cross border cooperation of researchers in general and even more so in the area of Open Science. Each jurisdiction has taken a distinct approach – or no approach at all – to integrate Open Science principles into copyright legislation.

The lack of harmonisation of copyright provisions also results in inconsistent legal conditions for researchers, making cross-border collaboration and knowledge sharing more difficult. Although all three countries are EU Member States, differences still exist. What is legally permitted in one country may be restricted in another (i.e., based on the presumption of transfer of rights, an employee from Slovenia may not have the rights to publish research results in Open Access, whereas this may be possible in Croatia), leading to an uneven landscape that complicates the international dissemination of scientific knowledge and limits the impact of efforts and resources invested in producing open knowledge.

Researchers and scientists have called for several decades now for a better legal environment for their research and scientific activities, in order to achieve the full potential of science and research for the development of society. Open Science initiatives that rely on bottom-up initiatives, for example through contract negotiation, can help mitigate some of these limitations. This is especially the case in the absence of balanced copyright frameworks with legally certain, broad, and harmonised research exceptions. This study highlights that, nonetheless, the efforts and activities of Open Science can still be severely hindered by unreformed copyright law provisions, particularly where there is a lack of political will to address these shortcomings and support research and science.

This study provides a systematic analysis of how copyright law currently interacts with Open Science in Slovenia, Italy, and Croatia. It highlights the most significant legal barriers that hinder national efforts to harness investment in Open Science.

By clarifying the challenges posed by existing copyright provisions and examining how they function in different legal and institutional settings, this study lays the groundwork for discussions on the need to align copyright law with Open Science objectives.

In the future researchers will need to continue to advocate for a more balanced copyright system with legally certain, broad and harmonised research exceptions. This study highlights that even the efforts and activities of Open Science, which legally depend on private licences and contracts, are potentially severely hindered by copyright regimes today. Copyright regimes should be better framed to support research and science and rapidly reformed not to hinder Open Science.

PARTNERS AND AUTHORS

Partners

Knowledge Rights 21

Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) is an IFLA Programme, supported by Arcadia, in partnership with LIBER and SPARC Europe. The KR21 programme is dedicated to driving legislative and practical reforms across Europe to enhance access to and use of knowledge for research, science, and society at large. By mobilising the potential of Europe's knowledge institutions – particularly libraries – KR21 fosters collaboration across the access-to-knowledge movement to build momentum for long-term copyright reform. The programme advocates for a modern legislative framework that prioritises contemporary research, education, and scientific practice, ensuring that knowledge valorisation, cultural participation, and innovation are free from unnecessary barriers in the information society.⁹⁸

Arcadia's support has been instrumental in advancing KR21's mission, enabling it to strengthen legal and policy frameworks that enhance 21st century access to research, education, and culture.

Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI

Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI is a research, educational and consultancy institution working in the fields of Internet law and society. ODIPI specializes in the field of Open Science and copyright, open data and data governance for AI, especially in relation to copyright law.⁹⁹ ODIPI is the KR21 National Coordinator for Slovenia and the KR21 Regional Coordinator for Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia and Hercegovina, North Macedonia, Montenegro and Kosovo and leads the KR21 Research Network for Central and Southeastern Europe,¹⁰⁰ and the KR21 Regional Alliance – Network of Librarians and Copyright Experts from Central and Southeastern Europe.¹⁰¹

⁹⁸ Knowledge Rights 21. Available at: <<https://www.knowledgerights21.org>>, last accessed in March 2025;

⁹⁹ Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI. Available at: <<https://www.odipi.si/en/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.;

¹⁰¹ Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI. Establishment of the Knowledge Rights 21 Regional Alliance for Central and Southeastern Europe. Available at: <<https://www.odipi.si/en/establishment-of-the-knowledge-rights-21-regional-alliance-for-central-and-southeastern-europe/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

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Laura Pipan is a research assistant at the Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute, ODIPI. She obtained her Bachelor of Laws (LL.B.) degree in 2022 and her Master of Laws (LL.M.) degree in 2024, both at the Faculty of Law, University of Ljubljana. In November 2022, she was selected to participate in a cross-faculty national project to create a deposit system for plastic waste packaging in Slovenia. She spent the last semester of her Master's degree at the Venice International University as part of an ERASMUS+ exchange programme. She also received an IViR scholarship to attend a summer course on international copyright law and policy and a grant for an ERASMUS+ traineeship, which she completed at the Slovenian embassies in Riga and Rome.

Prof. dr. sc. Tihomir Katulić, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law

Prof. dr. sc. Tihomir Katulić is a professor of information technology law at the University of Zagreb Faculty of Law, focusing on privacy and data protection, intellectual property, cybercrime, information security, electronic commerce, and electronic communications. He is a co-founder and lecturer at the University of Zagreb's Interdisciplinary Specialist Postgraduate Program in Intellectual Property. He teaches courses on information technology law, personal data protection, privacy in electronic communications, internet governance, cybersecurity, electronic commerce, and copyright in the digital environment at the University of Zagreb, including at the Faculty of Law, the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing, the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, and the Faculty of Economics & Business.

Tihomir is a member of the International Education Board and chairs the Croatian National Knowledge Chapter of the International Association of Privacy Professionals. He is a member of the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) External Pool of Experts, EU Cybernet Expert Pool and previously served on the reserve list of experts of the European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA) from 2018 to 2021, advised the Croatian Personal Data Protection Agency and the Personal Data Protection Agency of the Republic of North Macedonia, and contributed to several ALAI national reports for Croatia.

Tihomir graduated from University of Zagreb, Faculty of Law, where he also obtained his Ph.D.

Deborah De Angelis, Attorney-at-Law, KR21 National Coordinator for Italy

Deborah De Angelis¹⁰² is an attorney-at-law based in Rome, Italy. Deborah is a legal expert in international copyright law, cultural heritage, entertainment law and new technologies. She is currently the representative and legal lead of the Italian Chapter in the Creative Commons Global Network. She also worked as a legal advisor on copyright law to the previous Italian Minister of Culture in 2020. Deborah carries out teaching and training activities, has organised numerous conferences and events in copyright and entertainment law, and authored several publications. Since 2004 she is a fellow of the NEXA Center for the Internet & Society. She is a member of the working group "Digital Cultural Heritage" in ICOM ITALIA. Since July 2021, she has been the regional delegate for Italy for the project on the right to research in the field of international copyright law of the PIJIP group of the American University, Washington College of Law. From 1 December 2022, she is national delegate for Italy in the KR21 (Knowledge Rights 21) project on access to research, culture and knowledge. As of 13 June 2022, she was elected Councillor of ALAI, Italy for the term 2022-2025. From 12 January 2023, she has been a member of Europeana's Copyright Steering Committee.

¹⁰² More information available at: <<http://www.ddastudiolegale.it/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

APPENDIX 1 – MODEL QUESTIONNAIRE

This model questionnaire was developed by ODIPI and used to analyse the Slovenian, Croatian and Italian legal system and can be reused to expand the analysis to further jurisdictions.

I. Barriers and Enablers in the Copyright Law

Question 1: We kindly ask you to list the applicable copyright laws in both the original language and English. Additionally, please attach the source, also in both the original language and English.

Names of the relevant legal acts:

Links to the relevant legal acts:

I.1. Barriers in the Copyright Law

I.1.1. Barriers derived from the requirement of consensual management of copyright

The requirement for consensual management of copyright presents a significant barrier for Open Science by mandating unanimous consent among all rights holders for the use of a work. This barrier arises in the context of co-authored works and compound works. Co-authored works are created through joint creative collaboration among multiple authors. Videos involving multiple collaborators serve as a good example of co-authored works. Compound works consist of individual contributions created by multiple authors, who combine their works for exploitation in common. A good example of a compound work is a book where each chapter is authored by a different individual. Requiring unanimous consent for the use of such works complicates rights management. Consequently, it reduces flexibility in sharing research outputs, restricts access to knowledge, and impedes collaboration and innovation.

I.1.1.1. Requirement of consensual management for co-authors

In Slovenia, Article 12 of ZASP regulates co-authorship in the fields of literature, science, and art. Co-authorship arises when a work is created through the collaboration of multiple authors, making it necessary to regulate the rights of co-authors and their interactions with third parties. As a co-authored work constitutes an 'inseparable whole', it is particularly important to clearly delineate the rights among co-authors.

Article 12(2) of ZASP provides that economic rights in a co-authored work are held jointly by all co-authors. Therefore, any use of the work requires the unanimous consent of all co-authors, as a majority decision is insufficient. However, the law mitigates this requirement by stipulating that a co-author may not obstruct the use of the work if doing so would violate the principles of good faith and fairness.

In this context, Article 12(2) of ZASP acts as a barrier for Open Science. When a single co-author objects to making the work openly accessible, this objection prevents the work's publication on open-access platforms or repositories, even if all other co-authors support such publication. This issue is particularly relevant as an increasing number of research outputs are being shared in video format on platforms dedicated to video content. Thus, this restriction can significantly limit the dissemination of research results to the wider scientific community and the public.

Co-authors
Article 12 of ZASP

(1) If a copyright work created by the collaboration of two or more persons constitutes an inseparable whole, all co-authors of this work shall have joint copyright in it.

(2) The right to decide on the use of such a work belongs jointly to all co-authors; this notwithstanding, individual co-authors may not obstruct such decisions, as this would be contrary to the principles of good faith and fairness.

(3) Co-authors' shares shall be determined in proportion to the extent of their respective contributions to the creation of the work unless they are set otherwise by contract.

Another barrier, akin to the requirement of consensual management for co-authors, arises with derivative works. While derivative works (Slo. *predelave*) are legally recognised under ZASP, they are not explicitly classified as “co-authored works”. In some cases, a derivative work may involve contributions from both the original author and the author of a derivative work, resembling a form of co-authorship.

Question 2: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 12 of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.1.1.2. Requirement of consensual management for compound works

In Slovenia, Article 13 of ZASP stipulates that when several authors combine their works for exploitation in common, any decision regarding the use of the compound work requires the unanimous consent of all involved authors. This necessitates coordination and negotiation among multiple parties, which can be time-consuming and complex.

Compound works may become less accessible if the authors are unable to agree on their use. For instance, if one author wishes to make a collection (Slo. *zbirka*) available under an open license, they cannot do so without the consent of all other authors. This can negatively impact the accessibility of research results for Open Science, limiting the dissemination of scientific information and restricting further research and innovation.

Authors of compound works
Article 13 of ZASP

(1) The provisions of the preceding Article shall apply, mutatis mutandis, in cases where several authors combine their works for exploitation in common.

Question 3: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 13 ZASP in your copyright law?

I.1.2. Barriers derived from the unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation

In the context of copyright law, unwaivability refers to the inability of authors or performers to renounce certain rights, even voluntarily. While unwaivability intends to protect authors, it can create significant barriers for Open Science, by restricting the flexibility in rights management needed to ensure Open Access to works. Unwaivability of the right to remuneration or fair compensation presumes that remuneration must be paid to the author for the use of a copyright work.

Within the Slovenian Copyright and Related Rights Act (ZASP), two distinct concepts of remuneration are recognized: 'fair compensation', as outlined in Article 37 of ZASP, and 'equitable remuneration,' addressed in other relevant Articles from ZASP. The unwaivability of this right applies to both copyright and related rights. Notably, in the context of related rights, it is particularly common in provisions pertaining to performers.

The unwaivability of the right to remuneration, whether framed as 'fair compensation' or 'equitable remuneration', presents a barrier for Open Science, as remuneration must be paid, even when the author/copyright owner wishes to make their work accessible for free. The unwaivability of the right to remuneration enables collective management organizations to claim and collect remuneration on the author's behalf, regardless of the author's desire to share their work under an open license. As a result, authors are unable to fully exercise control over their works. Moreover, it burdens the providers – such as institutional repositories – who communicate these works to the public, with the obligation to pay remuneration. This complicates rights management and hinders the dissemination of information, limiting the availability of scientific and creative outputs to the wider community.

Right to remuneration

Article 37 of ZASP

- (1) The author shall have a right to fair compensation for sound or visual recording and photocopying of his work done within the scope of private or other internal use referred to in Article 50 of this Act.*
- (2) Remuneration referred to the preceding paragraph with respect to sound or visual recording shall be paid:
 1. upon the first sale or importation of new devices for sound or visual recording and
 2. upon the first sale or importation of new blank audio or video fixation media.*
- (3) Remuneration referred to in paragraph one of this Article with respect to photocopying shall be paid:
 1. upon the first sale or importation of new devices for photocopying and
 2. on photocopies made for sale, i.e. monthly depending on their probable number.*
- (4) For the purposes of this Act, importation shall be considered to be the release of goods into free circulation in accordance with the customs regulations of the European Community and any entry of goods into the territory of the Republic of Slovenia from other EU Member States.*
- (5) Photocopying under this Article shall be considered as equivalent to other similar reproduction techniques; devices for sound or visual recording shall be considered as equivalent to other devices which achieve the same effect.*
- (6) The right to remuneration under paragraph one of this Article may not be waived or assigned inter vivos or be subject to execution.*

The rule of separate transfers

Article 76 of ZASP

- (4) When the right of rental of phonograms or videograms containing a copyright work is transferred (Article 25), the author shall retain the right to equitable remuneration for each such rental. The author may not waive this right.*
- (5) Where the author transfers the right of rebroadcasting (Article 31), he shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each use of the work in the case of rebroadcasting. The author may not waive this right.*

The right of audiovisual adaptation

Article 104 of ZASP

- (3) Notwithstanding the provisions of the preceding paragraph, the author of a pre-existing work shall have:
 3. the right to claim equitable remuneration from the film producer for each rental of videograms of an audiovisual work.
 5. the right to receive equitable remuneration from the online content-sharing service provider for each communication to the public of the audiovisual work in the context of an online content-sharing service;*
- (4) The author of a pre-existing work may not waive the rights referred to in the preceding paragraph.*

Film production contract

Article 107 of ZASP

- (4) Notwithstanding the provisions of the preceding paragraphs:*

3. the co-authors shall have the right to equitable remuneration from the film producer for each rental of videograms of an audiovisual work;
 4. the co-authors shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each rebroadcasting of an audiovisual work;
 5. the co-authors shall have the right to receive equitable remuneration from the online content-sharing service provider for each communication to the public of the audiovisual work in the context of an online content-sharing service;
 6. the co-authors shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each communication to the public of the audiovisual work in the context of video-on-demand services;
 7. the co-authors shall have the right to receive equitable remuneration for each act of making the audiovisual work available to the public for direct or indirect economic advantage other than that referred to points 5 and 6 of this paragraph.
- (5) Co-authors and authors of contributions may not waive the rights referred to in the preceding paragraph.

The right to remuneration for communicating to the public a phonogram and videogram

Article 122 of ZASP

- (1) A performer shall have the right to a share of the remuneration received by the phonogram producer for communicating to the public a phonogram in which his performance is fixed.
- (2) A performer shall have the right to equitable remuneration for each broadcasting or any other communication to the public of a videogram of his performance. The remuneration shall be paid by the user to the performer.
- (3) The performer may not waive the right under this Article.

The right to remuneration

Article 123 of ZASP

- (1) A performer shall have the right to remuneration for the reproduction for private or other internal use under paragraph two of Article 37 of this Act.
- (2) Where the performer has transferred to the phonogram producer or film producer the right to rent out phonograms or videograms containing his performance, the phonogram producer or film producer shall pay the performer fair compensation for such.

Presumption of transfer

Article 124 of ZASP

- (1) By entering into a contract for film production, a performer shall be presumed to have transferred to the film producer, exclusively and without limitations, all economic rights in his performance unless otherwise provided by contract.
- (2) For each economic right which was transferred under the preceding paragraph, the performer shall have the right to demand equitable remuneration from the film producer.
- (3) The performer may not waive the right referred to in the preceding paragraph.

Question 4: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to these Articles in your copyright law?

I.1.3. Barriers derived from the requirement for specific – separate transfers

In copyright law, the requirement for separate transfers of rights can create significant barriers for Open Science by complicating rights management and limiting the flexibility authors need to make their works freely accessible. Instead of transferring a unified set of rights, authors must engage in separate negotiations for certain components, making the process

more time-consuming and complex. This fragmentation can discourage authors from pursuing Open Access, ultimately restricting the dissemination and reuse of scientific outputs.

I.1.3.1. Requirement for specific – separate transfers of the right to remuneration

In Slovenia, Article 76(6) of ZASP presumes that the author retains the right to remuneration in cases where he transfers the rights of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service (Article 163c of ZASP), unless explicitly agreed upon in a contract.

For instance, an author may believe they have transferred all economic rights to a particular work, assuming full control over the use of the work rests with the transferee. However, because the right to remuneration is not included in the transfer of other economic rights, this enables collective management organizations to claim and collect remuneration on behalf of the author.

Such a framework undermines the author’s ability to fully align their work with Open Science principles and creates additional complexity in rights management, even in cases where the author has a clear intention to make their work freely accessible under open licenses.

The rule of separate transfers

Article 76 of ZASP

(6) Where the author transfers the rights of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service (Article 163c), they shall have the right to receive equitable remuneration from the online content-sharing service provider for each use of the work in the case of communication to the public in the context of an online content-sharing service.

Question 5: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 76(6) of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.1.3.2. Requirement for specific – separate transfers of rights for the use of copyright works

In Slovenia, Article 76(2) of ZASP fragments the right of reproduction (Article 23 of ZASP) by dividing it into distinct components: ‘the right to save the work in electronic form’ and ‘the right to its sound or visual fixation’. It stipulates that a transfer of the right of reproduction does not automatically include these specific rights unless explicitly provided by law or agreed upon in a contract.

This fragmentation complicates rights management, as authors or rights holders must navigate separate agreements or provisions for each of these components. Even if authors wish to make their works freely accessible under open licenses, the need to manage these divided rights individually can create additional legal and procedural hurdles. These complexities undermine the principles of Open Science.

Article 76(3) of ZASP provides another example of fragmentation of copyright, which concerns the right of distribution (Article 24 of ZASP). It should be noted that the right of distribution under ZASP, covers only physical representations of works. Article 76(3) of ZASP states that transferring the right to distribute (physical) copies of a work does not include the right to import those copies unless explicitly provided by law or agreed upon in a contract. This subdivision separates ‘the right to distribute copies’ from ‘the right to import them’, adding complexity to rights management.

Although the right of distribution rarely applies to Open Science, the fragmentation of the right of reproduction in Article 76(3) of ZASP, should be highlighted, as it creates additional barriers for authors who wish to make their works freely accessible under open licenses, thereby undermining the principles of Open Science.

The rule of separate transfers

Article 76 of ZASP

(2) A transfer of the right of reproduction of a work (Article 23) shall not include the transfer of the right to save it in electronic form, or the right to its sound or visual fixation, unless otherwise provided by law or contract.

(3) A transfer of the right of distribution of copies of a work (Article 24) shall not include the transfer of the right of importation of such copies unless otherwise provided by law or by contract.

Question 6: Are you able to identify any provisions similar Article 76(2) and Article 76(3) of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.1.4. Barriers derived from the requirement for special consent of the author for subsequent transfers

In Slovenia, the provision of Article 78 of ZASP grants the author control over the use of their work, even after transferring certain rights. Article 78(1) of ZASP stipulates that a right-holder, to whom an economic right or another author's right has been transferred, may not further transfer this right to a third party without the explicit consent of the author, unless otherwise provided by contract.

This represents a barrier for Open Science, as the restriction on subsequent transfers to a third party without the author's explicit consent complicates the dissemination of scientific works. For instance, if a research institution or individual holds the economic rights to a work but cannot easily transfer them to other researchers or institutions without obtaining the author's explicit consent, the accessibility of the work for Open Science purposes may be restricted.

Additionally, the requirement to secure the author's explicit consent for every subsequent transfer of rights to a third party creates significant administrative burdens in rights management. The provision that is original aimed to protect authors can present a significant barrier to Open Science, as it complicates the process of clearing copyrights and hinders the process of dissemination of research results.

Subsequent transfers

Article 78 of ZASP

(1) A right-holder to whom an economic right or other author's right has been transferred may not further transfer this right to a third party without the consent of the author unless otherwise provided by contract.

Question 7: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 78 of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.1.5. Barriers derived from the requirement of formality

In Slovenia, the provision on formality in Article 80 of ZASP requires that all transfers of economic rights or other author's rights, as well as all authorisations, must be made in writing unless otherwise provided by law. Furthermore, if the

requirement for written form is not met, any controversial or unclear stipulations are presumed to be interpreted in favour of the author.

Formality

Article 80 of ZASP

(1) All transfers of economic rights or other author's rights and all authorisations shall be in writing unless otherwise provided by law.

(2) In the case of non-compliance with the preceding paragraph, any controversial or unclear stipulations shall be interpreted in favour of the author.

Question 8: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 80 of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.1.6. Barriers derived from the presumption of the publisher's priority right

In Slovenia, the provision of Article 89 of ZASP, which grants a publisher who has acquired the right to publish a work in book form a priority right to publish the work in electronic form, can pose a barrier for Open Science for several reasons: it reduces flexibility for authors who wish to distribute their work through multiple channels; it limits authors' ability to choose the best method of distribution for their work; it grants the publisher a privileged position regarding the publication of the work in electronic form; if the publisher fails to exercise the priority right or does so with delay, authors may be unable to immediately publish their work in electronic form on other platforms, thereby restricting their rights; and, finally, it represents a limitation as it gives the publisher, who has acquired the right to publish the work in book form, a preferential position over other publishers offering the same conditions for the electronic publication of the work. This provision hinders the effective implementation of *Secondary Publishing Rights*.

Publisher's priority right

Article 89 of ZASP

(1) The publisher who has acquired the right to publish a work in book form shall have, in relation to other publishers offering the same conditions, the priority right to publish the work in electronic form.

(2) The priority right under the preceding paragraph shall run for a period of three years from the agreed date of publication of the literary work. The publisher shall give a written statement of the author's written offer within 30 days of its receipt.

Question 9: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 89(2) of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.2. Barriers That Can Also Provide an Enabler in the Copyright Law

I.2.1. Barriers that might also act as enablers derived from the presumption of transfer of economic rights from employees to employers

In Slovenia, Article 101 of ZASP governs copyright works created in the course of employment. It stipulates that in cases, when an employee creates a copyright work as part of their duties or following instructions from their employer, the economic rights and other rights of the author are deemed to be exclusively transferred to the employer for a period of ten years from the completion of the work, unless otherwise agreed by contract.

Additionally, Article 102 of ZASP establishes that that economic rights and other rights of the author (i.e., employee) to databases and collective works are transferred exclusively and without limitations to the employer, unless otherwise agreed by contract.

These provisions can present a significant barrier for rights management with open licences. They grant the employer full control over the economic rights to the works during the initial ten-year period. Thus, during this time, authors/employees cannot manage copyright on works created as part of their duties or following instructions from their employer, with open licences, as they do not own the rights. Any transfer of rights or licence of rights, including licence with open licenses, is null and void.

In specific cases, when the obligations from the *Rights Retention* provisions within the Slovenian Decree on Open Science apply, the provisions of Article 101 and 102 of ZASP can provide a barrier in cases in which employer and publisher do not agree to publish the work according to principles of Open Science, the author is effectively unable to prevent/correct the situation. In such cases, the legal mechanisms for *Rights Retention* in the Slovenian legal framework lose their effectiveness, as the decision ultimately rests with the employer.

The same provisions can also serve as an enabler for Open Science in cases in which the employer actively supports open-access policies (even if author does not). In this scenario, the exclusive rights held by the employer could facilitate open dissemination of the work, as the employer would have the authority to make it openly available without requiring any express permissions from the author (i.e., employee).

Thus, the impact of Article 101 of ZASP on Open Science depends largely on the stance of the employer. While it has the potential to hinder Open Science when employers are not supportive, it could, in some cases, serve as a tool for advancing Open Science in cases when employers are committed to open-access principles even if the authors are not.

Copyright work created in the course of employment

Article 101 of ZASP

(1) When a copyright work is created by an employee in the execution of his duties or following instructions given by his employer (a copyright work created in the course of employment), it shall be deemed that the economic rights and other rights of the author to such work are exclusively transferred to the employer for a period of ten years from the completion of the work, unless otherwise provided by contract.

(2) After the expiry of the period referred to in the preceding paragraph, the rights referred to in the preceding paragraph shall revert to the employee; however, the employer may claim a new exclusive transfer of these rights for equitable remuneration.

Special rights

Article 102 of ZASP

(1) Notwithstanding the provisions of the preceding Article,

1. an employee shall retain the exclusive right to use a work created in the course of employment as part of his collected works;

2. it shall be deemed that economic rights and other rights of the author to a database and in a collective work are transferred exclusively and without limitations to the employer, unless otherwise provided by contract.

Question 10: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 101 or Article 102 of ZASP in your copyright law?

I.3. Enablers in the Copyright Law

I.3.1. Enabler derived from the exception for text and data mining for scientific research

Text and data mining for scientific research

Article 57b of ZASP

(1) Research organisations, publicly accessible archives, libraries, museums, film or audio heritage institutions and public broadcasting organisations, as well as persons belonging to research organisations and cultural heritage institutions, may freely reproduce works to which they have lawful access under the conditions laid down in this Article and shall carry out text and data mining operations referred to in paragraph one of the preceding Article on works to which they have lawful access for the purposes of scientific research under the conditions laid down in this Article, including the digitisation of analogue content and remote access to such content where this is necessary for the purposes of text and data mining.

(4) [...] If the use of any security and protection measures prevents a person from carrying out acts permitted under this Article, the author shall provide that person with access to and use of the works in accordance with this Article within a time limit not exceeding 72 hours.

(5) The sharing and making available to the public of the results of the text and data mining referred to in paragraph one of this Article shall be permissible provided that the extent of the text and data mining is limited by the intended purpose, is compatible with fair practice, does not conflict with normal use of the work and does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author.

(6) Any contractual stipulation contrary to this Article shall be null and void.

Article 57b of ZASP, which implements Article 3 of the DSM Directive, introduces a specific exception allowing text and data mining (TDM) for scientific research, which can act as a powerful enabler of research, science and, of course, Open Science. It grants research organisations, publicly accessible archives, libraries, museums, film or audio heritage institutions, public broadcasting organisations, and persons affiliated with these institutions the right to freely reproduce works and carry out TDM operations, provided they have lawful access to the works. The exception allows for the digitisation of analogue content and the remote access to content where necessary for the purposes of TDM. This provision represents a significant legal basis for broadening access to knowledge and enabling data-driven research across institutions.

Further enabling the aims of Open Science, Article 57b(5) of ZASP expressly allows sharing and making available to the public the results of TDM, provided four cumulative conditions are met: (i) the use is limited by the intended purpose, (ii) it is compatible with fair practice, (iii) it does not conflict with the normal use of the work, and (iv) it does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author. Any contractual provision excluding or limiting this exception is null and void, which ensures that rights holders cannot contractually restrict its application. Rights holders also need to ensure that the beneficiaries of the exception can effectively perform TDM and need to act within 72 hours or face sanctions. This strengthens the position of the beneficiaries of the exception and supports non-discriminatory access to legal tools for data analysis.

Despite its enabling potential, the repetition of conditions from the general rule of Article 46 of ZASP may result in this part of the exception being applied excessively restrictively, as institutions or publishers may default to more conservative licensing models out of legal caution or ambiguity.

General rule

Article 46 of ZASP

Limitations to copyright shall be permissible in cases laid down in this Section, provided that the extent of such use of copyright works is limited by the intended purpose, is compatible with fair practice, does not conflict with normal use of the work and does not unreasonably prejudice the legitimate interests of the author.

Question 11: Are you able to identify any provisions similar to Article 57b of ZASP in your copyright law?

II. Barriers and Enablers outside of the Copyright Law

We kindly ask you to identify provisions in any legal act outside of copyright law that may function as either a barrier or an enabler for Open Science.

The cultural heritage laws in several Member States impose restrictions on the Public Domain by introducing an additional layer of protection for works that are no longer under copyright or were never under copyright. These laws require authorization and, in many cases, payment of a fee for commercial use of faithful digital reproductions of cultural heritage works, including those in the Public Domain. Essentially, legal or natural persons wishing to use these Public Domain works for commercial purposes or other uses specified by the law must obtain something that closely resembles a license.

The Slovenian Cultural Heritage Protection Act (Slo. *Zakon o varstvu kulturne dediščine*; hereinafter: ZVKD-1), imposes limitations on uses of heritage that is protected as national monuments. Article 44 of ZVKD-1 prohibits “the use of the image and name of a monument without the consent of the owner” for commercial purposes, stating that “[t]he owner may also determine the amount of compensation for use by consent.” Under this law, a “cultural monument” is defined as a heritage asset that has been declared a monument or is listed in the inventory book of an authorised museum and encompasses all kinds of cultural heritage.

Additionally, restrictions extend to research and non-commercial uses. If a new work is created based on such cultural heritage, it cannot be licensed under a CC-BY license, which permits both commercial and non-commercial uses. Instead, it must be licensed under a CC-BY-NC license, which restricts commercial use. This legal requirement creates a barrier for Open Science by limiting the ability to freely share research outputs under open licenses that allow for unrestricted use, including commercial applications. In essence, while ZVKD-1 permits the use of protected cultural heritage for research purposes, such as integrating it into new works resulting from research, these new works cannot be made available under an open license permitting commercial use. This restriction presents a significant barrier to the potential for broader dissemination, reuse, and alignment with the principles of Open Science.

On the other hand, there are certain enablers for Open Science in the wider Slovenian legal framework. Namely, the Slovenian Scientific Research and Innovation Activity Act (ZZrID)¹⁰³ mandates *Rights Retention* – a crucial mechanism for ensuring that publicly funded research remains openly accessible. The concept of *Rights Retention* is further detailed in the Decree on Open Science.¹⁰⁴ Compliance with the *Rights Retention* obligation functions not only as an enabler, but even as an incentive for Open Science principles, reinforcing its uptake through financial conditions tied to research funding eligibility and legally prescribed sanctions for non-compliance.

In May 2025, an amendment to the ZZrID (amendment ZZrID-C)¹⁰⁵ was unanimously adopted by the National Assembly of the Republic of Slovenia (Slo. *Državni zbor Republike Slovenije*),¹⁰⁶ officially implementing *Secondary Publishing Rights* into

¹⁰³ The *Rights Retention* obligation was introduced in Slovenia already in 2021 with the ZZrID; Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 186/21 and 40/23;

¹⁰⁴ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 59/23;

¹⁰⁵ Official Gazette of the Republic of Slovenia [Uradni list RS], No. 40/25;

¹⁰⁶ Open Data and Intellectual Property Institute ODIPI. *Secondary Publishing Rights Adopted into Slovenian Legislation*. Available at: <<https://www.odipi.si/en/secondary-publishing-rights-adopted-into-slovenian-law/>>, last accessed in May 2025; Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Slovenia. Amendment to the Scientific

Article 41 of ZZrID.¹⁰⁷ The amendment ZZrID-C entered into force in June 2025. *Secondary Publishing Rights* were recognised as a recommended and desirable solution in the EU Council Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy, and equitable academic publishing of May 2023.¹⁰⁸ Similar legislation has already been adopted in countries such as Bulgaria,¹⁰⁹ the Netherlands,¹¹⁰ Italy,¹¹¹ Germany,¹¹² France,¹¹³ Belgium,¹¹⁴ and Austria¹¹⁵ – Slovenia now joins them with the amendment to the ZZrID. However, unlike those countries, which amended their copyright legislation to introduce *Secondary Publishing Rights* into their respective national legal frameworks, Slovenia chose a different approach by incorporating *Secondary Publishing Rights* into its national research legislation (i.e., the ZZrID). The introduction of *Secondary Publishing Rights* significantly strengthens the legal certainty for researchers and research institutions with regard to fulfilling Open Science obligations. It complements and reinforces the existing *Rights Retention* obligation with an important legal presumption that any contractual provision preventing researchers or research institutions from publishing or making publicly available the results of research in a public Open Access repository shall be null and void. This enables more effective rights management in line with Open Science principles.

Question 12: Are you able to identify any provisions that act as enablers for Open Science outside of the copyright law of your country?

Research and Innovation Activity Act Confirmed. Available at: <<https://www.gov.si/novice/2025-05-21-dokoncno-potrjena-novela-zakona-o-znanstvenoraziskovalni-in-inovacijski-dejavnosti/>>, last accessed in May 2025;

¹⁰⁷ Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Slovenia (2024). Act Amending and Supplementing the Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act. Available at: <<https://e-uprava.gov.si/si/drzava-in-druzba/e-demokracija/predlogi-predpisov/predlog-predpisa.html?id=16439>>, last accessed in May 2025;

¹⁰⁸ Council of the European Union (2023). Council conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing. Available at: <<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-9616-2023-INIT/en/pdf>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹⁰⁹ Available at: <<https://copyrightblog.kluweriplaw.com/2024/02/09/introducing-a-zero-embargo-secondary-publication-right-in-bulgaria/>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹¹⁰ Available at: <<https://zoek.officielebekendmakingen.nl/stb-2015-257.html>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹¹¹ Available at: <<https://zenodo.org/records/5764841#.YidpCXrP13g>>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹¹² Available at: <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_urhg/englisch_urhg.html>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹¹³ Available at: <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_c/LEGIARTI000033205794/2016-10-09>, last accessed in March 2025,

¹¹⁴ Available at: <https://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_g.pl?language=fr&la=F&table_name=loi&cn=2013022819>, last accessed in March 2025;

¹¹⁵ Available at:

<<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=10001848>>, last accessed in March 2025.